

Political Economy Analysis for Transboundary Water Management in Iraq and Jordan

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction.....	5
1.1 Objective	6
1.2 Methodology.....	6
1.2.1 Stakeholders Mapping and Analysis Methodology	8
2 Background on Jordan’s Water Sector.....	11
2.1 Supply and Demand	11
2.1.1 Surface Water Resources and their uses	12
2.1.2 Ground Water Resources and their uses	14
2.1.3 Treated Wastewater and its uses.....	15
2.1.4 Transboundary Water Resources.....	16
2.2 Strategies, Policies and Regulations Governing Water Sector	17
2.2.1 Strategies	17
2.2.2 Policies	18
2.2.3 Laws and Regulations	23
2.2.4 Agreements governing transboundary water resources	23
3 Stakeholders Mapping and Analysis.....	27
3.1 Stakeholders Mapping	27
3.2 Power- Interest Analysis.....	29
3.3 Stakeholders Value Map.....	30
4 Political Economy Analysis.....	32
4.1 Political Factors Analysis	32
4.1.1 Geopolitical Relations	32
4.1.2 Jordan’s Commitment Toward Water Diplomacy and Cooperation	35
4.1.3 SDG 6.5 and Existing Agreements.....	36
4.1.4 Political Landscape and Power Dynamics	39
4.2 Economic Factors	41
4.2.1 Jordan’s Economic Situation Impact on Transboundary Water Management	41
4.2.2 Economic Dependence on Water	42
4.2.3 Economic Costs and Benefits.....	46
4.2.4 Investment in Water Infrastructure	47
4.3 Social Factors.....	48
4.3.1 Impacts on Communities	48
4.3.2 Intra-Community and Cross-Border Conflicts Over Water	49
4.3.3 Environmental Impacts.....	50

4.3.4	Public Perception and Advocacy.....	50
5	Challenges and Opportunities.....	52
5.1	Challenges.....	52
5.2	Success Stories.....	55
5.3	Opportunities (Strengths).....	57
6	Areas for Improvement and Suggested Actions.....	60
6.1	Areas for Improvement.....	60
6.2	Actions.....	62
7	Conclusion and Recommendations.....	67
7.1	Conclusion.....	67
7.2	Recommendations.....	69
8	Iraq’s Water Resources.....	71
8.1	Supply and Demand.....	71
8.1.1	Surface Water Resources.....	72
8.1.2	Ground Water Resources.....	72
8.1.3	Non-Conventional Water Resources.....	73
8.2	Strategies and Policies.....	73
8.2.1	Transboundary Water Agreements.....	75
9	Stakeholders Mapping and Analysis.....	77
9.1	Stakeholders Mapping.....	77
9.2	Power- Interest Analysis.....	80
9.3	Stakeholders’ Value Map.....	81
10	Political Economy Analysis.....	82
10.1	Political Factors Analysis.....	82
10.1.1	Geopolitical Relations and Transboundary Water Negotiations.....	82
10.1.2	Iraq’s Commitment towards Water Diplomacy and Cooperation.....	84
10.1.3	Political Landscape and Power Dynamics.....	85
10.2	Economic Factors.....	86
10.2.1	Water Pricing Mechanism, Subsidy System, and their Implications.....	86
10.2.2	Economic Impacts.....	87
11	Challenges and Opportunities.....	89
11.1	Challenges.....	89
11.2	Coordination and Governance.....	92
11.3	Opportunities.....	94
12	Areas for Improvement and Suggested Actions.....	96
12.1	Gaps.....	96

12.2	Actions	100
12.2.1	Integrating Economic Considerations in Water Management in Iraq and Kurdistan	101
12.2.2	Approaches Toward Economic Sustainability and Efficiency	101
12.2.3	Technical solutions and Actions.....	102
13	Conclusions and Recommendations	105
13.1	Conclusions	105
13.2	Recommendations	106
13.2.1	Short-Term Recommendations.....	106
13.2.2	Long-Term recommendations	107
	References.....	109

List of Tables

Table 1:	Evaluation Criteria for power and interest of stakeholders.....	9
Table 2:	Water categories and amount of consumption per use (MWI, 2023).....	11
Table 3:	Design Capacity of Storage Dams in Jordan (MWI, 2023)	13
Table 4:	Transboundary basins and aquifers (Source: Jordan SDG 6.5.2 report, 2023)	16
Table 5:	Agreements and their effectiveness according to evaluation criteria	38
Table 6:	Water Tariff Categories, Ranges, Tariffs, Subsidies, and Sanitation Fees (Data Source: MWI, Water Tariff)	43
Table 7:	Water Tariff according to well type, consumption, and salinity (MWI, Water Tarriff for private wells)	44
Table 8:	Successful Case Studies on Transboundary Water Management.....	55
Table 9:	Detailed List of Gaps in Transboundary Water Management.....	60
Table 10:	Strategies and Actions to Improve Transboundary Water Management	62
Table 11:	Legal and Institutional Gaps	98
Table 12:	Areas for Improvements, Actions for Improvement, and Recommendations.....	100
Table 13:	Actions and Research for Technical Aspects	102

List of Figures

Figure 1:	Methodology for conducting political economy analysis.....	7
Figure 2:	Steps to do stakeholders' mapping and analysis.....	8
Figure 3:	Demand increase for all sectors from 2020 to 2040 (Data source: MWI Water Strategy 2023-2040).....	12
Figure 4:	Surface Water Basins in Jordan (Source: Al-Bakri et. Al, 2013).....	13
Figure 5:	Surface water uses of different sector in MCM (MWI, 2023)	14
Figure 6:	Groundwater Basins in Jordan with their Annual safe Yield (Fanack, 2022)	15
Figure 7:	Groundwater uses of different sectors in MCM (MWI, 2022).....	15
Figure 8:	Stakeholders Categories Based on Power- Interest Analysis.....	30
Figure 9:	Jordan Transboundary Water Management Stakeholders' Value Map.....	32
Figure 10:	Sketch of the infrastructure in the Yarmouk tributary basin (Source: Zeitoun et al. 2019)	34
Figure 11:	IWRM Score for SDG6.5.1 for Jordan	36
Figure 12:	SDG Indicator 6.5.2 worldwide (UN,2023)	37

Figure 13: Tigris-Euphrates River Basin (source: I. E. Issa 2014)	72
Figure 14: Stakeholders' Management Strategies.....	81
Figure 15: Iraq Stakeholders Value Map.....	82
Figure 16: Employment in agriculture in Iraq, including Kurdistan Region of Iraq, 2000–2017 (% of total employment) (Source: Jongerden et al., 2019)	88
Figure 17: Total fisheries production (tons) in Iraq between 2008-2018 (World Bank, 2020).....	89

List of Acronyms

AAWDCO	Aqaba- Amman Water Desalination & Conveyance Project
ACC	Agriculture Credit Corporation
AFD	Agence Française de Développement
CSA	Climate Smart Agriculture
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit
GoJ	Government of Jordan
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IFC	International Finance Corporation
IMF	International Monetary Fund
INWRDAM	Inter-Islamic Network on Water Resources Development and Management
IWRM	Integrated Water Resources Management
JCC	Jordan Cooperative Corporation
JCCME	Japan Cooperation Center for the Middle East
JICA	The Japan International Agency
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
JUST	Jordan University of Science and Technology
JVA	Jordan Valley Authority
JWC	Joint Water Committee
KFW	Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau
KRG	Kurdistan Regional Government
KRI	Kurdistan Region of Iraq
MCM	Million Cubic Meter
Med	Mediterranean
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
MoA	Ministry of Agriculture
MoAWR	Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources
MoEnv.	Ministry of Environment
MoF	Ministry of Finance
MoFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MoPIC	Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation
MoWR	Ministry of Water Resources
MRC	Mekong River Commission
MWI	Ministry of Water and Irrigation
NARC	National Agriculture Research Center
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
ORASECOM	Orange-Senqu River Commission

PMU	Project Management Unit
PPPs	Public-Private Partnerships
SDC	Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SEMED	Southern and Eastern Mediterranean
SIDA	Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency
UfM	Union for the Mediterranean
UJ	University of Jordan
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WAJ	Water Authority of Jordan
WDC	Water Diplomacy Center
WEFE	Water- Energy- Food- Ecosystem
WUA	Water Users Association

Executive Summary

This report is to present the results of analysis of the complex interactions among political, economic, and social factors that affect the management of transboundary water management in Jordan and Iraq. For this study, desk review of existing literature, reports, policies, regulations, agreements, and/ or treaties have been reviewed. In addition, a list of best practices for transboundary water management has been compiled by reviewing international reports dealing with transboundary water management. Interviews with key informants were conducted to gather information regarding transboundary water management. Comparison between existing situation, and best practices have been conducted to identify areas for improvements.

Jordan

Jordan is positioned amidst regional conflict and growing water scarcity, leading to the challenges in managing transboundary water resources. Significant percentage of Jordan's total water resources originate from outside the Kingdom's borders, depending on shared rivers and aquifers with Israel, Syria, Saudi Arabia, and other countries. Around 26% of the shared water resources are covered by operational arrangements. Key agreements, such as the 1994 Peace Treaty with Israel and those over the Yarmouk River with Syria, have clearly stated the water allocations, but the implementation of such agreements, high political tension, and excessive upstream extractions deeply limit Jordan's access to these crucial resources.

Over-dependence on groundwater, inefficient agricultural practices, and the impacts of climate change are additional factors that further worsen Jordan's water scarcity. Driven by population growth, inflows of refugees, and economic development, the country's water demand has been increasing continuously beyond its available resources, inducing a constant deficit. Further, the over-extraction of groundwater aquifers such as Disi leads to the degradation of aquifers, a factor adding to the water scarcity and quality problems.

Governance, legal frameworks, and policies further point out several gaps that characterize Jordan's transboundary water management from political and economic analytical standpoints. The gaps include lack of comprehensive framework governing all transboundary water issues in Jordan, climate change integration is lacked in signed treaties and agreements, poor mechanisms related to compliance and enforcement, and other gaps. Despite these gaps, Jordan has its strength points in water management. Jordan has the National Water Strategy (2023- 2040) that covers all governance aspects that are required for improved water sector. In addition, the Government of Jordan (GoJ) has undertaken steps towards implementing actions that align with the new strategy goals. Furthermore, has good models for private sector participation, like Miyahuna. Therefore, in order to improve the effectiveness of transboundary management, there are several actions recommended. Some of these include Data Collection and Sharing, Data for Decision for transboundary water management as a tool for improving decision-making and cooperation, Multi-Stakeholder Dialogues which bring on board different perspectives: governmental, nongovernmental, civil society, and the private sector. In addition to strengthening legal and policy frameworks using harmonization of water laws in neighboring countries, clearly defining the roles played by the institutions involved. In addition, institutional capacities are required to be built at various levels, involving capacity-building programs and adequate allocation of resources. The other key element of improved regional cooperation in the management of transboundary water resources is the strengthening of regional institutions to coordinate shared water resources at a regional level. This can be done through

the formulation of joint management plans, binding agreements that set up regular communication through institutionalized meetings and shared electronic platforms, encouraging joint data collection, enhancing transparency through shared databases, and promoting equitable mechanisms for sharing benefits so that countries build trust and have equal representation in the management of such important resources.

Iraq

Iraq faces an acute and worsening water crisis driven by declining inflows from the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, climate change, poor governance, aging infrastructure, and upstream damming by Turkey and Iran. These factors have led to severe water scarcity, deteriorating water quality, and growing competition among provinces and communities, particularly in southern Iraq. The Ministry of Water Resources (MoWR) is the primary institution responsible for managing Iraq's water sector. The MoWR has undertaken several initiatives and actions to cope with water scarcity and address the challenges in the water sector. Iraq's national water strategy (2015–2035) emphasizes the importance of good governance, modern irrigation methods, and equitable sharing of water with upstream countries. It acknowledges the country's vulnerability to water scarcity due to reduced river flows, outdated infrastructure, and environmental degradation. While the strategy provides a framework for addressing these issues, implementation remains weak, largely due to political instability and competing priorities.

Transboundary water relations are a major concern for Iraq, as it shares the Tigris and Euphrates River basins with Türkiye and Iran. Both countries have constructed dams and reservoirs that significantly reduce downstream flows into Iraq. Although Iraq has engaged in diplomatic discussions with its neighbors, progress toward legally binding water-sharing agreements has been limited.

Recent developments, such as Iraq joining the United Nations Water Convention and signing a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with Türkiye on joint water projects, offer potential for improved cooperation. However, without enforceable agreements and mutual commitments, Iraq remains vulnerable to unilateral actions by upstream states. Water quality is another critical challenge, especially in southern regions where salinity intrusion, pollution, and inadequate treatment facilities compromise public health and agricultural productivity. In cities like Basra, contaminated water has caused widespread illness and fueled public discontent. Efforts to improve water quality include rehabilitating treatment plants and expanding wastewater recycling, but these initiatives require sustained investment and technical support. Stakeholder engagement at the local level is essential for conflict prevention and sustainable management. Tribal mediation and community-based mechanisms play a significant role in resolving disputes, although their effectiveness varies depending on local conditions and political dynamics. National authorities must work closely with provincial governments, civil society, and international partners to strengthen these mechanisms and ensure more inclusive decision-making. International support has been instrumental in advancing water diplomacy and capacity-building in Iraq. For example, the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC) have provided technical expertise, facilitated dialogue, and promoted best practices in transboundary water management. Additionally, Iraq's recent accession to the UN Water Convention opens new avenues for regional cooperation and access to global standards and support. However, substantial gaps remain in policy implementation, institutional coordination, and data sharing. Iraq lacks a unified legal framework for water rights and usage, contributing to inefficiencies and disputes. Investment in infrastructure, particularly in rural and marginalized areas, is urgently needed to improve service delivery and reduce disparities. Climate-resilient solutions, such as wastewater reuse,

groundwater protection, and desalination, should be prioritized to diversify water sources and enhance long-term sustainability.

ملخص

يهدف هذا التقرير إلى تقديم نتائج تحليل للعلاقات المتشابكة بين العوامل السياسية والاقتصادية والاجتماعية التي تؤثر على إدارة الموارد المائية العابرة للحدود (المياه المشتركة) في الأردن والعراق. اشتملت الدراسة على مراجعة شاملة للأدبيات السابقة، والتقارير، والسياسات، واللوائح، والاتفاقيات أو المعاهدات ذات الصلة. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، تم إعداد قائمة بأفضل الممارسات العالمية لإدارة المياه العابرة للحدود من خلال دراسة التقارير الدولية التي تعالج هذا الموضوع. كما تم إجراء مقابلات مع خبراء من القطاعين الحكومي والخاص لجمع بيانات ومعلومات دقيقة حول واقع إدارة المياه المشتركة. وبعد ذلك، تم إجراء مقارنة بين الوضع الحالي وأفضل الممارسات الدولية لتحديد المجالات التي تحتاج إلى تحسين وتطوير.

الأردن

تقع الأردن وسط صراعات إقليمية وازدياد شح المياه، مما يؤدي إلى تحديات كبيرة في إدارة الموارد المائية العابرة للحدود/ المشتركة. يعتمد جزء كبير من موارد المياه الكلية للأردن على مصادر خارج حدود المملكة، معتمدة على الأنهار والطبقات الجوفية المشتركة مع إسرائيل وسوريا والمملكة العربية السعودية ودول أخرى. حوالي 26٪ من هذه الموارد المائية المشتركة تحكمها اتفاقيات مع الدول المجاورة. تشمل الاتفاقيات الرئيسية اتفاقية السلام لعام 1994 مع إسرائيل والاتفاقيات المتعلقة بنهر اليرموك مع سوريا، والتي حددت بوضوح الحصص المائية. لكن تنفيذ هذه الاتفاقيات والتوترات السياسية العالية والاستخراج المفرط للمياه في المنبع يحد بشدة من وصول الأردن لهذه الموارد الحيوية.

الاعتماد المفرط على المياه الجوفية والممارسات الزراعية غير الفعالة وتأثيرات تغير المناخ هي عوامل إضافية تقام من أزمة شح المياه في الأردن. مدفوعة بالنمو السكاني وتزايد تدفق اللاجئين والتنمية الاقتصادية، مما زاد الطلب على المياه بشكل مستمر ليتجاوز الموارد المتاحة، مما أدى إلى عجز دائم. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، الاستخراج المفرط للمياه الجوفية مثل طبقة "الديسي" يؤدي إلى تدهور الطبقات الجوفية، مما يزيد من مشكلة نقص المياه وسوء جودتها.

تشير الحوكمة والإطار القانوني والسياسات إلى العديد من الفجوات التي تميز إدارة المياه العابرة للحدود في الأردن من وجهات نظر سياسية واقتصادية. تشمل هذه الفجوات عدم وجود إطار شامل لإدارة جميع قضايا المياه العابرة للحدود، وعدم دمج تأثيرات تغير المناخ في المعاهدات والاتفاقيات الموقعة، وضعف آليات الامتثال والتنفيذ، وغيرها. وعلى الرغم من هذه التحديات، فإن للأردن نقاط قوة في إدارة المياه، حيث يوجد استراتيجية وطنية للمياه (2023-2040) تغطي جميع جوانب الحوكمة اللازمة لتحسين قطاع المياه. كما قامت الحكومة الأردنية باتخاذ خطوات نحو تنفيذ إجراءات تتماشى مع أهداف الاستراتيجية الجديدة. بالإضافة إلى وجود نماذج جيدة لمشاركة القطاع الخاص، مثل شركة "مياها". لذلك، من أجل تحسين فعالية إدارة المياه العابرة للحدود، هناك عدة توصيات مقترحة، منها: جمع البيانات وتبادلها، واستخدام البيانات كأداة لدعم اتخاذ القرارات وإدارة المياه العابرة للحدود، والحوار متعدد الأطراف الذي يجمع وجهات نظر مختلفة: الحكومية وغير الحكومية والمجتمع المدني والقطاع الخاص. كما يتطلب تعزيز الإطار القانوني والسياسي إلى تنسيق القوانين المائية مع الدول المجاورة وتحديد أدوار المؤسسات المشاركة بوضوح. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، يجب بناء القدرات المؤسسية على مختلف المستويات من خلال برامج بناء القدرات وتخصيص الموارد بشكل كافٍ. العنصر الآخر الرئيسي لتعزيز التعاون الإقليمي في إدارة المياه العابرة للحدود هو تعزيز المؤسسات الإقليمية لتنسيق الموارد المائية المشتركة على المستوى الإقليمي. يمكن تحقيق ذلك من خلال وضع خطط إدارة مشتركة، واتفاقيات ملزمة تضمن التواصل المنتظم عبر الاجتماعات المؤسسية والمنصات الإلكترونية المشتركة، وتشجيع جمع البيانات بشكل مشترك، وتعزيز الشفافية من خلال قواعد بيانات مشتركة، وتعزيز آليات تقاسم المنافع بشكل عادل لبناء الثقة بين الدول.

العراق

يعاني العراق من أزمة مائية متزايدة. يرجع ذلك إلى انخفاض تدفق المياه من نهر دجلة والفرات، وتغير المناخ، وضعف الحوكمة، وتدهور البنية التحتية، بالإضافة إلى بناء السدود من قبل تركيا وإيران على المنبع. هذه العوامل أدت إلى شح كبير في المياه وتدهور جودتها.

وزارة الموارد المائية هي الجهة الرئيسية المسؤولة عن إدارة قطاع المياه في العراق. وقد باشرت الوزارة عدة مبادرات وخطوات للتعامل مع مشكلة ندرة المياه ومعالجة التحديات التي يواجهها القطاع المائي. تركز الاستراتيجية الوطنية للمياه (2015-2035) على أهمية الحوكمة الجيدة وأساليب الري الحديثة وتوزيع عادل للمياه مع الدول المجاورة. تعترف الاستراتيجية بضعف العراق أمام ندرة المياه نتيجة انخفاض تدفق الأنهار وشبكة البنية التحتية القديمة والتدهور البيئي. وعلى الرغم من أن الاستراتيجية توفر إطاراً لمعالجة هذه القضايا، إلا أن التنفيذ ضعيف إلى حد كبير بسبب عدم الاستقرار السياسي والأولويات المتضاربة.

تُعد العلاقات المائية العابرة للحدود قضية رئيسية بالنسبة للعراق، حيث يشترك في أحواض نهري دجلة والفرات مع تركيا وإيران. قامت كلتا البلدين ببناء سدود وبحيرات اصطناعية تقلل بشكل كبير من تدفق المياه نحو العراق. وعلى الرغم من مشاركة العراق في محادثات دبلوماسية مع جيرانه، إلا أن التقدم نحو التوصل إلى اتفاقيات ملزمة لتوزيع المياه كان محدودًا.

تشمل التطورات الأخيرة انضمام العراق إلى اتفاقية الأمم المتحدة للمياه، وتوقيع مذكرة تفاهم مع تركيا حول مشاريع مائية مشتركة، مما يفتح آملًا لتعزيز التعاون. ومع ذلك، ما لم يتم التوصل إلى اتفاقيات قابلة للتنفيذ والتزامات متبادلة، يظل العراق معرضًا للإجراءات الأحادية من الدول الموجودة على المنبع.

تُعد جودة المياه تحديًا آخر بالغ الأهمية، خاصة في المناطق الجنوبية التي تعاني من ارتفاع نسبة الملوحة والتلوث وعدم كفاءة محطات المعالجة، مما يؤثر على صحة الإنسان والإنتاج الزراعي. وفي مدن مثل البصرة، أدت المياه الملوثة إلى انتشار الأمراض وزيادة الاستياء الشعبي. تشمل الجهود المبذولة لتحسين جودة المياه إعادة تأهيل محطات المعالجة وتوسيع عمليات إعادة استخدام مياه الصرف الصحي، لكن هذه المبادرات تحتاج إلى استثمارات مستمرة ودعم تقني.

يشكل مشاركة أصحاب المصلحة على المستوى المحلي عاملاً أساسياً في الوقاية من النزاعات وإدارة الموارد بشكل مستدام. تلعب الوساطة القبلية والآليات المجتمعية دورًا مهمًا في حل الخلافات، رغم اختلاف فعاليتها حسب الظروف المحلية والديناميكيات السياسية. يجب على السلطات الوطنية العمل بشكل وثيق مع الحكومات المحلية ومنظمات المجتمع المدني والشركاء الدوليين لتعزيز هذه الآليات وضمان اتخاذ قرارات أكثر شمولية.

كان للدعم الدولي دور محوري في تعزيز الدبلوماسية المائية وبناء القدرات في العراق. على سبيل المثال، ساعدت وكالة التنمية والتعاون السويسرية في تقديم خبرات تقنية وتسهيل الحوار وترويج الممارسات الجيدة في الإدارة المائية العابرة للحدود. كما أن انضمام العراق الأخير إلى اتفاقية الأمم المتحدة للمياه يفتح آفاقًا جديدة للتعاون الإقليمي وللحصول على المعايير العالمية والدعم الفني.

ومع ذلك، لا تزال هناك فجوات كبيرة في تنفيذ السياسات والتنسيق المؤسسي وتبادل البيانات. ويخو العراق من إطار قانوني موحد ينظم حقوق واستخدام المياه، مما يسهم في الهدر والخلافات. يحتاج الاستثمار في البنية التحتية، وخاصة في المناطق الريفية والمهمشة، إلى تحسين الخدمات وتقليل الفوارق. يجب التركيز على حلول مرنة أمام تغيرات المناخ، مثل إعادة استخدام مياه الصرف الصحي وحماية المياه الجوفية وتقنيات التحلية، لتنويع مصادر المياه وتعزيز الاستدامة على المدى الطويل.

1 Introduction

The Mediterranean (Med) region is characterized by fragile ecosystems and overexploitation of natural resources. Increasing population, urbanization, and industrialization imposed severe stresses on the water resources, reducing water availability and deteriorating water quality. Besides the aforementioned factors, the impacts of climate change exert additional pressure on already strained ecosystems and on vulnerable economies and societies. According to several studies, the Med basin is one of the most sensitive areas towards climate change, with the projection of double or triple increase in water demand, particularly in the agricultural sector, by the end of 2050 (MedECC, 2020; UNEP, 2022; Diffenbaugh and Giorgi, 2012).

Jordan

Jordan is considered as one of the most water scarce countries with share of fresh water of 60 m³ per capita per year falling below the water absolute scarcity threshold of 500 m³ per capita (MWI, 2023). Jordan faces numerous challenges in managing and allocating its water resources. In addition, Jordan depends on shared water resources, where approximately 26% of Jordan's shared water resources are covered by operational arrangements (MWI, 2022). Throughout history, accessing its fair share of these shared resources has been a persistent challenge for Jordan due to upstream neighbors' overexploitation of these water sources.

Iraq

The dynamics of water management in Iraq are complicated by regional politics and historical agreements, such as the 1975 Algiers Agreement with Iran and the 1980 Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation with Syria. Iraq is highly dependent on the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, where these rivers originate in Türkiye and flow into the Shatt al-Arab basin in southern Iraq. The Euphrates River crosses Syria and Iraq, with Türkiye and Syria contributing 90% and 10% of the water flow, respectively. On the other hand, the Tigris River flows from Türkiye to Iraq, with Türkiye, Iraq, and Iran contributing 40%, 51%, and 9% of its flow, respectively (YRIS, 2023). The situation in Iraq is getting worse, as these rivers are drying up. Iraq has contended that its upstream neighbors are diverting water, worsening its water challenges, whereas Türkiye and Iran have countered by attributing Iraq's water issues to climate change and mismanagement within Iraq. Internally, Iraq's water infrastructure is outdated, leading to inefficiencies and significant losses in water supply (CSIS, 2023). Moreover, the country's water sector suffers from lack of coordination, contributing to contamination and scarcity. The Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG) pursues its water management strategy independently, further complicating efforts to address water scarcity within Iraq. The consequences of water mismanagement within Iraq's borders are already evident, with water scarcity, conflict between tribes, and tensions between local communities. In 2023, Iraq has joined the Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (known as the UN Water Convention) with the aim of improving transboundary water management to contribute to its sustainable development and to enhance regional stability and peace.

Transboundary Water Management

Transboundary water management is crucial for addressing the complex challenges presented by shared waterways. Transboundary water management plays a pivotal role, facilitating diplomatic, environmental, and socio-economic cooperation among nations. Its objectives are diverse, including fair distribution, sustainable usage, conflict prevention, economic growth, and environmental preservation of shared water resources. By overseeing rivers or aquifers that span multiple countries, transboundary water management aims to distribute water equitably, thereby mitigating conflicts arising from perceived imbalances.

Moreover, it emphasizes long-term planning to ensure water availability for present and future generations, tackling issues such as over-extraction, pollution, and the ecological health of water bodies. Effective cooperation among nations serves as a means of conflict prevention, fostering dialogue, negotiation, and the establishment of mutually beneficial agreements. Additionally, optimizing the utilization of shared resources can stimulate economic development, particularly in sectors like agriculture and industry. Furthermore, transboundary water management promotes environmental conservation by addressing shared challenges such as pollution control, habitat preservation, and the overall well-being of ecosystems. Its relevance has grown in the face of climate change, assisting countries in adapting to shifting conditions such as altered precipitation patterns and increasing water scarcity, thereby enhancing resilience to environmental changes.

1.1 Objective

For doing effective and efficient transboundary water management, a comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics in transboundary water management is necessary. The overall objective of this report is to present the results of analysis of the complex interactions among political, economic, and social factors that affect the management of transboundary water resources. The specific objectives are as follows:

- Assess the political landscape and dynamics influencing water governance, management, and decision-making at the national and transboundary levels.
- Identify key stakeholders, their roles, and the power dynamics among them.
- To analyze the institutional framework and governance structures related to the water sector, particularly in the context of transboundary water cooperation

1.2 Methodology

The Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC) Political Economy Analysis (PEA) framework has been employed for this study (SDC, 2023). The framework provides a structured methodology for conducting political economy, and social analysis. The steps include identification of the issues, specify objectives, analysis of political landscape, analysis of institutional framework, and analysis of stakeholders their power, interests, incentives, and external influences. For this study, desk review of existing literature, reports, policies, regulations, agreements, and/ or treaties have been reviewed. In addition, a list of best practices for transboundary water management have been compiled by reviewing international reports dealing with transboundary water management. Interviews with key informants were conducted to gather information regarding transboundary water management. Comparison between existing situation, and best practices have been conducted to identify areas for improvements. Recommendations for improvements were also obtained from successful case studies. A detailed stakeholders mapping and analysis has been developed in a separate report. The employed methodology is explained in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Methodology for conducting political economy analysis

The best practices and principles for transboundary water management according to United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) include:

- **Reasonable and Equitable Use:** Water use should be reasonable and equitable, considering the transboundary nature of the resource.
- **Regular Data and Information Exchange:** Watercourse States should regularly exchange readily available data and information on the condition of the watercourse, including hydrological, meteorological, hydrogeological, and ecological data.
- **Prevention of Transboundary Impact:** Parties must take appropriate measures to prevent, control, and reduce any significant adverse environmental effect from changes in transboundary waters.
- **Ecologically Sound Water Management:** Transboundary waters should be used with the aim of ecologically sound and rational water management, conservation, and environmental protection.
- **Joint Bodies:** Establishing joint bodies with responsibilities such as data collection and evaluation, joint monitoring, development of emission limits, and establishing water quality objectives.
- **Public Information:** Parties should make information on transboundary water conditions and measures taken accessible to the public.
- **Ecological Integrity:** States are obligated to take measures to protect the ecological integrity of ecosystems dependent on particular waters
- **Legal and Institutional Frameworks:** Effective transboundary water management depends on robust legal and institutional frameworks that facilitate cooperation
- **Shared Benefits and Costs:** Cooperation should be based on the equitable sharing of both the benefits and costs associated with transboundary water management
- **Cross-Sectoral Cooperation:** Various water-dependent sectors, including agriculture, industry, energy, and water supply and sanitation, need to cooperate at the supranational level for effective transboundary water management.

1.2.1 Stakeholders Mapping and Analysis Methodology

Desk review was conducted to identify and categorize stakeholders involved in water management, governance, and transboundary water issues. This research included reviewing existing literature, reports, policy documents, and previous studies to compile a comprehensive list of relevant actors and their roles within the water sector. Additionally, information from stakeholders’ websites was also collected.

Semi- structured interviews with key stakeholders to gain direct insights into their level of engagement and influence within the water sector. In Jordan, these stakeholders included government bodies such as the Ministry of Water and Irrigation, the Water Authority of Jordan, and the Jordan Valley Authority. Each of these entities plays a crucial role in water policies, distribution, and resource management in Jordan. Interviews were also held with international donors like the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), and the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), which provide funding and technical assistance for water projects. Additionally, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) such as Blue Peace Middle East and the Jordan Environment Society were engaged to understand their advocacy and cooperative efforts over shared water resources. The private sector, including various water companies, was interviewed to assess their involvement in water supply, treatment, and management services. These interviews were essential for understanding the roles and contributions of different organizations at both national and international levels. In Iraq, surveys and interviews were conducted with representatives from Iraqi Ministry of Water Resources, Ministry of Agriculture, and Ministry of Environment, and other institutions directly relevant to water policy, distribution, and resource management in Iraq. **Figure 2** shows the steps that were followed to conduct the stakeholders mapping and analysis.

Figure 2: Steps to do stakeholders' mapping and analysis

The analysis that was conducted included:

- **Power- Interest Analysis:** This analysis was conducted to define the stakeholders' power in water management and their interest in transboundary water management.
- **Power- Predictability:** This analysis was conducted to relate power to the predictability of behavior or response.

For the power-interest analysis, the Borealis tool was used to help in measuring the scoring of each entity in terms of power and interest. For power analysis, the below criteria were considered:

- **Formal power:** Comprises the power that is emitted from the control over resources and official positions or roles in the organization, government, and other institutions. Examples include government officials or any other form of decision-makers.
- **Resource power:** Based on the authority of critical resources, whether it is the source of finance, technology, or information, stakeholders enjoy an influential position in case they can dominate crucial resources.
- **Expert Power:** This power lies in stakeholder expert knowledge or skills. For example, professionals or organizations with special skills that can appropriately drive stakeholder decisions.
- **Coercive Power:** Depends on Forcing others to act in desired ways with threats or sanctions that only regulatory bodies or powerful groups can hold.
- **Legitimate Power:** This is derived from the social norms, cultural values, or recognized authority giving some stakeholders the right to influence based on controlling policies and strategies.

For the interest analysis, the below factors were considered:

- **Goal alignment:** If a project will help the stakeholder meet their goals or will affect their bottom line.
- **Perceived benefits:** High with potential of economic gain, social/environmental impact, or reputation enhancement.
- **Perceived risks:** Projects that pose risks toward financial, operational, or reputational.
- **Values and Beliefs:** Cultural issues, ethical considerations, and social responsibility are vital in shaping interest.
- **Resource Allocation:** Projects that need resource allocation or have the resource allocation potential, interest them.
- **External Influences:** Interest is created by outside influences such as public opinion, market trends, or even regulatory changes.
- **Involvement and Influence:** Those stakeholders who are either part of the decision-making team or hold an influential effect on the decision will be most interested.
- **Uncertainty and Information:** High uncertainty with access to key information can heighten interest.

Each entity has been scored against the above-mentioned criteria. The scoring ranged from 1 (low) to 5 (high). Rating of 4 and 5 is considered high, 3 is medium, 2 and 1 are low. **Table 1 Error! Reference source not found.** outlines the evaluation criteria.

Table 1: Evaluation Criteria for power and interest of stakeholders

Rate	Power Criteria	Interest Criteria
5	Control over transboundary water resources: The entity has direct decision-making power over water allocations, policies, and agreements that impact transboundary water	High, direct interest in transboundary water management: The entity is highly involved in addressing and resolving transboundary water issues, through direct

	<p>systems. It can influence legal frameworks, cross-border treaties, and high-level negotiations.</p> <p>Role in decision-making on transboundary water issues: The entity plays an important role in shaping policies, strategies, or regulations related to transboundary water management but may not have final control over decisions.</p>	<p>engagement in projects or benefiting from outcomes. They have a clear and vested interest in the sustainable management of shared water resources.</p>
4	<p>Influence through significant resources: The entity has considerable influence due to its ability to provide substantial resources such as financial investments, which significantly impact the water sector. Its role is impactful in shaping how projects are implemented, though it may not have direct control over decision-making.</p>	<p>Strategic interest in transboundary water management: The entity maintains a significant interest in water-sharing agreements or projects related to transboundary water issues. While not directly controlling decisions, it supports and invests in initiatives that affect transboundary water systems.</p>
3	<p>Moderate influence through resources: The entity holds resources (financial, knowledge, technical) or can influence local water management projects or other projects/initiatives that in-directly impact transboundary water systems.</p>	<p>Indirect contribution to transboundary water management: The entity implements projects or initiatives that contribute to water management in general, with potential secondary benefits to transboundary water issues but with no direct focus on transboundary challenges. Individuals or entities who are interested in the availability of water. Their engagement might be indirect, focusing on the impact of transboundary water agreements or policies on local water availability and their agricultural productivity. They benefit from improved water practices but have limited influence on cross-border water policies.</p>
2	<p>Supportive power: The entity supports water management projects or initiatives but lacks direct control or strong influence over transboundary issues.</p>	<p>Interest in water management: The entity contributes to implementing projects or activities that are not directly targeting water management but support sustainable practices and have some beneficial impact on overall water resource management.</p>
1	<p>Limited or no direct power: The entity has minimal influence over transboundary water decisions. They are mainly beneficiaries or have a limited voice in water management discussions.</p>	<p>Low or no interest: The entity is primarily a beneficiary of water management initiatives and has minimal direct involvement or interest in transboundary water issues. Their role is largely passive, receiving benefits without active engagement.</p>

2 Background on Jordan's Water Sector

2.1 Supply and Demand

Jordan is considered as one of the most water scarce countries with available fresh water of 60 cubic meter (m^3) per capita falling below the water absolute scarcity threshold of 500 m^3 per capita (MWI, 2023). This share has declined significantly from 1946 to 2023. In 1946, the share per capita was 3600 m^3 per year.

Jordan majorly depends on surface and ground water resources for the supply of water to its different sectors. The total water consumption reached 1202 million Cubic Meter (MCM) (324.6 million m^3 surface water, 683 million m^3 groundwater, and 194.5 million m^3 treated wastewater) in 2023 (MWI, 2023). The water uses are categorized as municipal and tourism, irrigation, industry, and remote areas and livestock (**Table 2**). Of the total surface water, 44.82% is used for municipal purposes, 51.66% for irrigation (74.78 % of which in the Jordan Valley, and 25.22% in the highlands), 1.94% for remote areas, and the remaining 1.58% for industrial uses (MWI, 2023). Regarding groundwater resources, 55.78% of which are used for municipal and tourism, 38.56% is used for irrigation purposes, 4.83% for industrial purposes, and the remaining 0.83% are used for remote areas and livestock production. Regarding treated wastewater, 80.37% of which are used for irrigation in the Jordan Valley.

Table 2: Water categories and amount of consumption per use (MWI, 2023)

Use	Surface Water (million m^3)	Ground Water (million m^3)	Treated Waste Water (million m^3)
Municipal and Tourism	145.5	381	
Irrigation	167.7	263.4	192.3
Remote Areas and Livestock	6.3	5.7	
Industry	5.1	33	2.17
Total (million m^3)	324.6	683.1	194.47

Water demand is continuously rising due to rapid population growth, influx of refugees, economic development, and continuous need of agricultural areas expansion (MWI, 2023). As shown in **Figure 3**, the water demand is expected to increase for all sectors. Furthermore, climate change exerts additional stress on the already strained ecosystem. Research has proved that climate change will have direct and indirect impacts on different sectors. The impact of climate change on precipitation varies from region to another. Historical precipitation analysis (1971-2016) revealed extreme droughts in the Amman Azraq Basin (AZB) in 1995 and moderate drought events in other years (Shatanawi, et al., 2022). Standard Precipitation Index (SPI) assessments in Mafraq governorate (1995-2017) identified severe and extreme droughts (Qtaishat, et al., 2023). Future predictions (2071-2100) indicate increased meteorological drought frequency in northern basins under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, along with heightened severity and occurrence (Rajsekhar & Gorelick, 2017). The anticipated changes in precipitation and rainfall will affect water scarcity.

Figure 3: Demand increase for all sectors from 2020 to 2040 (Data source: MWI Water Strategy 2023-2040)

In addition to the aforementioned reasons, Jordan's water supplies have been impacted by geopolitics. Jordan shares its surface and groundwater resources with its neighbors, Israel, Palestine, Saudi Arabia, and Syria, most of which are found outside of its boundaries. This increases Jordan's susceptibility to outside political forces and adds uncertainty to the supply of water, both now and in the future. For instance, among riparian countries, namely Israel and Syria, Jordan's downstream location along the Jordan River and the Yarmouk River has generated a divided power dynamic. This has affected Jordan's historical access to and management of water resources.

Jordan has run a continual water deficit, supplementing the discrepancy between supply and demand by over-extracting groundwater, resorting to expensive desalinization and exploiting non-renewable resources. This has led to 10 of 12 groundwater aquifers being “over-pumped” past their safe yield (the point at which the basin can recover the previous year’s withdrawals) (MWI, 2023). Continuous over-extraction of groundwater basins also results in increased water salinity. Examples of aquifers include Azraq and Hamad Basins (Goode and Subah, 2013; IWMI, 2016).

2.1.1 Surface Water Resources and their uses

There are 15 surface water basins (MWI, 2022) (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The surface water resources in Jordan include internal resources (runoff, drain water and springs) and transboundary or regional resources (Yarmouk River and Jordan River). The country’s three main rivers, the Jordan, Yarmouk and Zarqa, are a major part of the country’s surface water system.

Figure 4: Surface Water Basins in Jordan (Source: Al-Bakri et. Al, 2013)

Surface water volumes are mainly dependent on rainfall, which fluctuates in time and space, as well as on the aquifers’ characteristics that feed base flow and springs. Such characteristics define the quality, quantity, and durability of discharged water. There are 14 storage dams, with total design capacity of 356.8 million m³, and storage percentage of 32% (MWI, 2022). **Table 3** lists these dams and their design storage capacity (MWI, 2023).

Table 3: Design Capacity of Storage Dams in Jordan (MWI, 2023)

Dam	Design Storage Capacity (Million m ³)
Wehdeh	110

Wadi Arab	16.8
Zeqlab	4
Kufranjeh	7.8
King Talal	75
Karameh	55
Wadi Shueib	1.7
Kafrain	8.5
Zrqaa Maeen	1
Allajon	2
Tanour	14.7
Wala	28.6
Mujeb	29.8
Karak	2

The total surface water use reached 325 MCM in 2023, 15.1 MCM of which are from Al- Mkeibeh groundwater wells which are used for agricultural purposes through King Abdullah Canal (KAC) (MWI, 2023). The irrigation water uses account for 51% of the total surface water use. As shown in **Figure 5**, around 149 MCM is used for irrigation purposes, followed by municipal purposes accounting for 48.01% of the total surface water use.

Figure 5: Surface water uses of different sector in MCM (MWI, 2023)

2.1.2 Ground Water Resources and their uses

There are 12 groundwater basins in Jordan, which have been delineated based on hydrogeological studies (**Figure 6**). These basins include the following: Amman-Zarqa, Azraq, Yarmouk, Dead Sea, Hasa, Jafer Hammad, Jordan Valley, North Wadi Araba, South Wadi Araba, Sarhan (referred to as Sirhan, interchangeably) and Southern Desert. Most groundwater aquifers are renewable except Disi aquifer, and part of groundwater in the Jafr aquifer (MWI, 2022). Groundwater is being pumped at double the safe yield of aquifers which resulted in aquifers depletion, groundwater levels dropping, and water quality deterioration (MWI, 2023).

Figure 6: Groundwater Basins in Jordan with their Annual safe Yield (Fanack, 2022)

The total groundwater use reached approximately 683.1 MCM in 2023 (including desalinated brackish ground water), 38.56% of which are used for irrigation purposes. As shown in **Figure 7** around 381 MCM is used for municipal and tourism, followed by irrigation purposes accounting (263.4 MCM).

Figure 7: Groundwater uses of different sectors in MCM (MWI, 2022)

2.1.3 Treated Wastewater and its uses

The total number of wastewater treatment plants is 29 with a capacity of 233 million m³ (MWI, 2022). The total amount of treated wastewater use reached 194.47 MCM in 2023, 80.37% of which are used for irrigation in the Jordan Valley (MWI, 2023). The efficiency of using treated wastewater is high as Jordan consumes around 90% of its treated wastewater.

2.1.4 Transboundary Water Resources

The total surface area of transboundary water basins and aquifers within Jordan is 135,913 Km², around 26% of which (34,973 Km²) are covered by operational arrangements (Jordan's National Report- Transboundary Water- Indicator SDG 6.5.2, 2023). **Table 4** provides a list of the surface sub/basins and groundwater aquifers shared with neighboring countries.

Table 4: Transboundary basins and aquifers (Source: Jordan SDG 6.5.2 report, 2023)

Name	Type	Surface Area (Km ²)	Shared with	Surface Area covered by an operational arrangement within Jordan
Jordan River (Jordan Valley +North Ghors + South Ghors)	Basin	2,316	Jordan, Syria, Palestine, Lebanon, Israel	2,316 with Israel
Azraq	Basin	12,150	Jordan, Syria	0
Dead Sea	Basin	1,637	Jordan, Israel	1,637
North Wadi Araba	Basin	2,944	Jordan, Israel	2,944
South Wadi Araba	Basin	5,620	Jordan, Israel	5,620
Yarmouk	Basin	1,388	Jordan, Syria	1,388
Zarqa	Basin	3,594	Jordan, Syria	0
Hamad	Basin	17,807	Jordan, Syria, Iraq, Saudi Arabia	0
Azraq-Dhulleil	Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	18,504	Jordan, Syria	0
Yarmouk	Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	1,280	Jordan, Syria	0
Amman Zarqa	Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	4,074	Jordan, Syria	0
Wadi Sirhan	Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	12,703	Jordan, Saudi Arabia	0
Hamad	Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	18,315	Jordan, Syria, Saudi Arabia, Iraq	0
Disi	Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	5,904	Jordan, Saudi Arabia	5,904
Northern Wadi Araba	Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	3,080	Jordan, Israel	3,080

Southern Araba	Wadi	Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	2,757	Jordan, Israel	2,757
Jordan Valley + Jordan Side Valleys		Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	2,453	Jordan, Israel	2,453
Dead Sea		Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	6,874	Jordan, Israel	6,874
Jafer		Confined aquifer connected to surface Water	12,513	Jordan, Saudi Arabia	0

2.2 Strategies, Policies and Regulations Governing Water Sector

2.2.1 Strategies

Due to the water sector's several challenges, the Government of Jordan (GoJ) has done several updates on the Jordan's national water strategy. In this document, we focus on the New National Water strategy (2023-2040) developed after the National Economic Modernization Vision 2033 issue. The vision aims to improve the country's economy and governance structures to ensure long-term sustainability, resilience, and prosperity.

Jordan National Water Strategy (2023- 2040)

The National Water Strategy 2023-2040 of Jordan outlines a comprehensive plan to address severe water scarcity. To achieve lasting water security, the strategy focuses on the following key pillars:

Increasing Water Supply: The Government of Jordan aims to increase water supply through:

- Implementing large-scale desalination projects, particularly the National Conveyance Project, to reduce reliance on groundwater.
- Expanding the use of treated wastewater for irrigation and industrial purposes.
- Exploring new water resources and promoting rainwater harvesting.

Managing Water Demand: The Government of Jordan aims at managing water demand through:

- Reducing Non-Revenue Water (NRW) in municipal systems through infrastructure improvements, leakage control, and addressing illegal connections.
- Promoting water use efficiency in agriculture by adopting modern irrigation techniques, cultivating less water-intensive crops, and shifting towards rainfed agriculture where feasible.
- Encouraging water conservation measures in households, industries, and the tourism sector.

Improving Water Management: The Government of Jordan aims at improving water management through:

- Strengthening the governance structure of the water sector through institutional reforms, clearly defined roles and responsibilities, and enhanced transparency and accountability.
- Ensuring financial sustainability of the water sector by achieving cost recovery through tariff adjustments, reducing operational costs, and attracting private sector investments.

- Implementing Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) to ensure the sustainable use and protection of groundwater and surface water resources.

Addressing Climate Change: The Government of Jordan aims at addressing climate change in the water sector through:

- Integrating climate change adaptation and mitigation measures into water sector planning, investments, and policies.
- Developing and implementing drought and flood management systems.

Goals for Transboundary Water Management

Recognizing that a significant portion of Jordan's renewable freshwater resources originates from neighboring countries, the strategy emphasizes the importance of transboundary water management. The strategy sets the following goals to address this aspect through:

- **Strengthening Cooperation:** This includes engaging in active dialogues and collaboration with neighboring countries and enhancing existing transboundary water management mechanisms and exploring new avenues for joint management.
- **Protecting Water Rights:** The strategy emphasizes the importance of improving the proactive role in regional cooperation to protect water rights, in addition to participating in negotiations and agreements that ensure equitable water allocation.
- **Joint Management of Shared Basins:** This includes working collaboratively in the management of shared water resources and improve coordination.
- **Data and Information Sharing:** The aim is to establish mechanisms for the exchange of hydrological data and information with neighboring countries. Promoting transparency and building trust through open communication on water resources.

2.2.2 *Policies*

After the publication of the new national water strategy (2023- 2040), several policies have been updated to integrate the changes in the national water strategy. Prior to the new strategy, the below policies were considered by the Government of Jordan:

- **Water Demand Management Policy:** Promotes efficient water use by integrating decentralized and centralized wastewater management systems, focusing on recycling and reuse to address water scarcity, improve quality, and support sustainable development.
- **Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy in the Water Sector:** Aims to reduce energy consumption and promote the adoption of renewable energy sources in water sector operations, ensuring cost savings and environmental sustainability.
- **Water Substitution and Re-use:** Encourages the reuse of treated wastewater as an alternative to freshwater resources, reducing demand on limited water supplies and supporting agricultural and industrial applications.
- **Water Reallocation:** Focuses on the equitable distribution of water resources to prioritize essential uses, improve efficiency, and address emerging water demands in a resource-scarce environment.
- **Surface Water Utilization:** Enhances the sustainable use of surface water resources through effective management practices, addressing storage, distribution, and conservation needs.
- **Groundwater Sustainability:** Seeks to protect and sustain groundwater resources by regulating abstraction, preventing over-extraction, and mitigating pollution.

- Climate Change Policy for a Resilient Water Sector: Addresses the impacts of climate change on water resources by fostering adaptation measures, improving resilience, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the sector.
- Decentralized Wastewater Management: Supports localized wastewater treatment solutions, especially in rural and suburban areas, to improve access to sanitation, protect groundwater, and enable water reuse.

As part of the efforts of the Government of Jordan to reduce the gap between supply and demand, it issued several policies. These policies are explained below.

Groundwater Sustainability Policy (2016, 2023)

The main goal of this policy is to achieve the successful integration of Jordan's Water Resources Management. The policy sets clearly defined rules to manage the scarce water resources efficiently and sustainably.

The sustainability of irrigated agriculture relying on groundwater is governed by socio-economic considerations that should be delineated into categories, whereby a set of policy measures can be designed and applied to these various categories. The agricultural sector's share of groundwater resources shall be capped in favour of other sectors that show a higher economic return per cubic meter consumed, treated wastewater of quality meets national standards and complies with public health requirements shall be increasingly used to replace freshwater resources.

Surface Water Utilization Policy (2016, 2023)

The objective of this policy is to present in detail what is envisioned for the maximum utilization and optimum use of surface water, its protection, and its management, as well as to propose measures needed towards successfully integrating all its components.

The policy sets objectives related to irrigation. The objectives are: (i) Water allocated to irrigated agriculture is dynamic, as the total amount of surface water varies. The agricultural sector's share of water resources shall be capped over a planning horizon and will favor other sectors that show a higher economic return per cubic meter consumed; (ii) Resource management shall continually aim at achieving the highest possible efficiency in the conveyance, distribution, application, and use. One such policy is the separation of bulk production from retail production and entrusting the retail function to private entities, as JVA is doing with Water Users Associations and WAJ with the corporatized utilities; (iii) Institutional arrangements and legislation in effect shall be periodically reviewed to appraise adequacy of the retail function for irrigation water being handled by the empowered WUAs.; and (iv) Appropriate water tariffs and incentives shall be introduced to promote water efficiency in irrigation and higher economic returns for irrigated agricultural products.

Water Demand Management Policy (2016, 2023)

The main objective of the Water Demand Management Policy is to maximize the utilization of the available water, minimize water losses, conserve water resources, promote effective water-use efficiencies, and adapt to the challenge of water scarcity in order to reduce the gap between supply and demand.

Some of the Policy guidelines regarding irrigated agriculture are as follows:

- Enforcement of the Substitution and Reuse policy, with the aim of managing scarce water resources efficiently and maximizing the benefits and returns, as well as maximizing the benefit

from the use of treated wastewater for non-drinking purposes and in investments that provide a high economic return.

- Provide ways and means suitable for storage of treated wastewater until time of use, thus providing a new water resource which could substitute freshwater and reuse safely in irrigation.
- Expand the use of reclaimed water for industry and agriculture, to the maximum extent possible, taking into account that the treated wastewater is blended and treated wastewater must be in terms of quality matching the standards of the World Health Organization, the Food and Agriculture Organization, and the Jordan minimum standards, so that it can also be used without mixing in specific areas and achieve full benefit for the various sectors.
- Expansion of introduction of modern technological methods and rehabilitation of old wastewater plants and the use of modern techniques for treatment to produce reclaimed water of quality that meets international standards and can be used without restrictions. Such water can be considered as an additional source of water and revenue and can contribute to additional water quantities dedicated to irrigation, allowing the expansion of irrigated agriculture and directing freshwater for drinking purposes, considering the economic, cultural, social, political, and environmental factors.
- The introduction of the best technologies and modern and advanced irrigation systems in terms of efficient water use in agriculture.
- Adopt preventive maintenance programs for irrigation systems, which lead to efficient water uses and reduction of losses. Irrigation water use and efficiency (on-farm, conveyance, and distribution) shall be regularly monitored for demand forecasting and planning purposes. Appropriate programs and procedures shall be adopted to ensure uniform flow discharge and stable pressure throughout irrigation networks.

Water Reallocation Policy (2016, 2024)

The objectives of this policy document are to create rules and present statements considered fundamental in managing the scarce water resources efficiently, protecting them, and proposing actions required for implementation; to establish sustainability, protect health, and ensure equity endurance; to protect the environment and nature; and to maintain an internationally acceptable level of economic performance.

Some of the Policy guidelines are as follows:

- Freshwater allocated to irrigated agriculture in the highlands shall be capped and eventually reduced according to medium, and long-term plans to be prepared and implemented after which the reallocation plan can be updated accordingly.
- Irrigation water in the Jordan Valley shall be increased when new or treated wastewater is increased
- Fresh water shall be replaced by treated wastewater. Thus, irrigated agriculture can be expanded only where treated wastewater is available.

Water Sector Policy for Wastewater Management and Reuse (2023)

Jordan's Water Sector Policy for Wastewater Management and Reuse (2023) is a comprehensive plan aimed at improving the management and reuse of wastewater in the country. The policy outlines a number

of strategies and initiatives to increase the amount of treated wastewater available for reuse, improve the quality of treated wastewater, and promote the use of treated wastewater in various sectors.

Some of the key features of the policy include:

- A focus on increasing the number of people connected to sewer networks and the amount of treated wastewater produced.
- The development of new technologies for treating and reusing wastewater.
- The promotion of the use of treated wastewater in agriculture and industry.
- The establishment of a regulatory framework for wastewater management and reuse.

The policy is expected to have a significant impact on Jordan's water resources management and help to ensure the sustainable use of water in the country.

Water Sector Energy Policy (2023- 2040)

The Jordan Water Sector Energy Policy (2023-2040) aims to optimize energy use within the water sector, recognizing the close interconnection between water, energy, food, and the environment (WEFE). This policy seeks to enhance the sustainability of water and energy resources by promoting energy efficiency, the integration of renewable energy, and the sustainable management of water resources. The main objectives of the policy are:

- **Energy Efficiency:** The policy focuses on improving energy efficiency across water sector operations, especially in water pumping, treatment, and distribution, which are highly energy intensive.
- **Renewable Energy Integration:** It promotes the integration of renewable energy (solar and wind) into water infrastructure to reduce reliance on conventional energy sources and lower operational costs.
- **Sustainability and Climate Resilience:** By addressing the challenges of water scarcity and energy consumption, the policy aims to make the water sector more resilient to climate change and reduce its environmental impact.
- **Cost Reduction:** The policy seeks to lower water sector costs by reducing energy consumption and promoting the use of more efficient and cost-effective technologies.
- **Diversification of Water Resources:** Encourages the use of alternative water sources, such as treated wastewater, to reduce reliance on traditional freshwater sources, aligning with broader sustainability goals.

Climate Change related policies, and plans

The Climate Change Policy outlines Jordan's updated national policy for addressing climate change from 2022 to 2050. It serves as a guide for integrating climate action across various sectors and aligning national efforts with the objectives of the Paris Agreement and Jordan's Economic Modernization Vision. The policy envisions a climate-resilient Jordan that actively participates in global efforts to reach carbon neutrality by 2050. It acknowledges the country's vulnerability to climate change impacts, especially concerning water resources, agriculture, and ecosystems. The policy focuses on two approaches:

- **Adaptation:** This involves reducing Jordan's vulnerability to climate change effects. The policy outlines specific actions across sectors like water management, agriculture, ecosystems and biodiversity, health, urban development, coastal zones, and cultural heritage. These actions are categorized by time frame (short, medium, long term) and provide justification based on urgency, feasibility, and potential co-benefits.
- **Mitigation:** This focuses on reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The policy targets major emitting sectors like energy, transportation, waste management, industrial processes, agriculture, forestry, and other land use (AFOLU). It promotes renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable transport, circular economy practices, and climate-smart agriculture.

The policy emphasizes on the importance of the below actions and interventions to achieve Jordan's climate action goals and targets:

- **Legal and Institutional Frameworks:** The policy calls for updating and strengthening legal frameworks, enhancing institutional coordination, and ensuring stakeholder engagement at all levels of governance.
- **Technology Transfer and Financing:** The policy acknowledges the importance of accessing and implementing appropriate climate technologies and securing financing for climate action. It proposes developing Technology Action Plans and a National Implementing Entity for climate finance.
- **Education, Research, and Awareness:** The policy stresses integrating climate change into education curricula, strengthening the science-policy interface, and raising public awareness through effective communication strategies.
- **Gender and Youth Mainstreaming:** The policy recognizes the importance of integrating gender and youth perspectives in all climate actions and developing targeted action plans.
- **Emerging Issues and Assumptions:** The policy acknowledges several implicit assumptions, such as the availability of political will and sufficient resources. It also recognizes the need to address uncertainties, adapt to new technologies, and account for evolving circumstances during implementation.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** The policy outlines a monitoring and evaluation framework to track progress, measure the effectiveness of interventions, and ensure accountability. This framework encompasses indicators related to agenda setting, policy formulation, and policy evaluation. It promotes a data-driven approach to assessing the environmental, social, and economic impacts of climate actions.

In addition, the Ministry of Environment (MoEnv.) has developed the National Adaptation Plan (2021). The plan identifies actions that need to be implemented to adapt to the impacts of climate change in different sectors. Considering that the agriculture sector is the largest water user, the MoEnv. has developed the climate-smart agriculture national plan. This plan assesses and prioritizes investment packages (considering differences in agroecological zones) based on their potential contribution to Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA). The proposed investment packages have a negative net carbon balance, with a total reduction potential of Greenhouse Gases (GHG) emissions of 823,665 tCO₂-eq.

2.2.3 Laws and Regulations

Water Authority Law, 1988

The Water Authority Law of 1988 framed and established the Water Authority of Jordan as the prime organization for dealing with Jordan's water resources, whether surface water, groundwater, or wastewater management. WAJ is responsible for the supervision and regulation of water supply services, water use, and infrastructure maintenance while ensuring the conservation of water resources through sustainable utilization. It is also responsible for the protection and conservation of water resources, including transboundary waters shared with neighboring Israel, Syria, and Palestine, such as the Jordan River and the Yarmouk River. The law provided WAJ with the legal power to regulate the sector, prevent illicit use of water, and charge a tariff for services provided in supplying water and treating wastewater.

The Jordan Valley Development Law, No. 30 of the year 2001

Established the Jordan Valley Authority operating under the Ministry of Water and Irrigation. The Law entitled the JVA to implement a mandate on water management, irrigation systems, and agricultural development along the Jordan Valley. JVA undertakes infrastructural development and maintenance, such as the construction of dams and canals, that supply water for agricultural purposes, land reclamation, and urban planning in the area. It plays an essential role in realizing the efficient use of water, especially through construction and operation related to the King Abdullah Canal, as well as in the promotion of sustainable irrigation. Besides its water and agricultural concerns, the JVA is also concerned with environmental concerns and exercises transboundary water management, particularly concerning the Jordan River shared with neighboring countries through agreements such as the 1994 Jordan-Israel Peace Treaty. It is within this context that the law grants the JVA the power and authority to plan, execute schemes, regulate the consumption of water, apportion the resource, and collect fees, taking into consideration full sustainable development criteria for a balanced water need in agriculture, industry, and domestic consumption in the Jordan Valley.

2.2.4 Agreements governing transboundary water resources

As mentioned previously, Jordan has three operational arrangements. These arrangements are:

- Peace Treaty between the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and the State of Israel (Peace Treaty Annex II Water and Related Matters): The 1994 Peace Treaty between Jordan and Israel. Annex II includes the allocations for each party from the Jordan River, Yarmouk River, and Araba Aquifer. As a result of the agreement a Joint Water Committee (JWC) was established to implement the agreement and address additional water matters that may arise.
- Agreement between the Syrian Arab Republic and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan: for the utilization of Yarmouk Basin. Three bilateral agreements between Jordan and Syria were made over the last 50 years regarding the use of the shared water of the Yarmouk River. Jordan began the construction of the long-planned unity dam and the permanent Adaseya diversion weir only after concluding the agreement that was signed in 2001.
- Agreement between Jordan and Saudi: Agreement between the government of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan for the management and investment of groundwater in the Saqq Al-Disi layer. In April 2015, Jordan and Kingdom of Saudi Arabia entered into an agreement for the management and utilization of groundwater in Al- Disi/ Saq layer. The agreement has four main articles. The agreement calls for the liquidation of all existing activities in the protected areas

(prohibited areas), which depends on the extraction of groundwater. Monitoring wells are constructed to monitor the quality and level of groundwater. A Joint Technical Committee (JTC) was established to coordinate the tasks assigned for each party. The main responsibilities of the JTC include: 1) supervision of implementation of the terms of the agreement, 2) supervision and observation of groundwater quantity and quality, 3) collection and exchange of information, statements, studies and analysis. While the JTC is mandated to compile and share data between the two countries, the information regarding the committee reports remains limited based on the limited authority to share this information with third parties without the written consent of both Jordan and Saudi Arabia.

The below write up provide a detailed description of each agreement.

Treaty of Peace between the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and the State of Israel (Peace Treaty Annex II Water and Related Matters)

The 1994 Peace Treaty between Jordan and Israel. Annex II¹ includes the allocations for each party from the Jordan River, Yarmouk River, and Araba Aquifer. Annex II from the Jordan-Israeli Peace Treaty explains the agreed-upon framework for managing shared water resources between Jordan and Israel. It covers allocations from the Yarmouk and Jordan Rivers, groundwater resources, water quality protection, infrastructure projects, and mechanisms for cooperation.

Annex II details the specific allocations of water from the Yarmouk and Jordan Rivers between Israel and Jordan, as follows:

Water from the Yarmouk River:

- Summer Period (May 15th - October 15th): Israel is allocated 12 MCM (million cubic meters). Jordan receives the remainder of the flow.
- Winter Period (October 16th - May 14th): Israel is allocated 13 MCM and an additional 20 MCM in exchange for transferring water to Jordan from the Jordan River during the summer. Jordan receives the remaining flow, subject to these provisions.

Both countries are permitted to utilize excess flood water downstream of the Adassiya Diversion to minimize waste.

Water from the Jordan River:

- Summer Period (May 15th - October 15th): In exchange for the additional allocation from the Yarmouk River during the winter, Israel transfers 20 MCM to Jordan from a point upstream of the Deganya gates. Jordan covers the operational and maintenance costs of this transfer.
- Winter Period (October 16th - May 14th): Jordan is entitled to store a minimum average of 20 MCM from floodwaters in the Jordan River south of its confluence with the Yarmouk River. Excess, unusable floodwaters may be utilized by both parties, including for pumped storage.

Additional Water and Groundwater:

- The agreement outlines the cooperative goal of finding additional potable water sources for Jordan, aiming for 50 MCM/year. A joint committee is tasked with developing a plan within a year.

¹ Annex 2 is available at: [The Jordan-Israeli Peace Treaty \(kinghussein.gov.jo\)](http://kinghussein.gov.jo)

- The sources detail the use and management of groundwater in Wadi Araba, with provisions for existing Israeli wells in Jordanian territory and potential future development.

Agreement between the Syrian Arab Republic and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan

Three bilateral agreements between Jordan and Syria were made over the last 50 years regarding the use of the shared water of the Yarmouk River. Jordan began the construction of the long-planned unity dam and the permanent Adaseya diversion weir only after concluding the agreement that was signed in 2001.

In 1953, Jordan signed an agreement with Syria aiming at regulating the shared use of the Yarmouk River's waters. It aimed to establish a framework for the construction and operation of water infrastructure, including a joint dam and reservoir, for the benefit of both countries. The agreement highlights the "Yarmouk scheme," a comprehensive project encompassing several key components:

- **Joint Dam and Reservoir:** The construction of a joint dam on the Yarmouk River to create a reservoir, primarily aimed at ensuring a consistent water flow for irrigation and power generation.
- **Power Generation Facilities:** The establishment of the joint Maqarin generating station near the dam and the Adasiya generating station in Jordan, highlighting the importance of hydroelectric power generation.
- **Irrigation Canal Network:** The development of an irrigation canal network, branching from the Adasiya station, to distribute water for agricultural purposes in Jordan.
- **Hejaz Railway Diversion:** The diversion of the Hejaz Railway line to accommodate the project, indicating its scale and impact on existing infrastructure.

In 1987, Jordan signed an agreement with Syria. This agreement outlines the framework of cooperation for the utilization of the Yarmouk River. The agreement prioritizes efficient water and hydroelectric power generation for the benefit of both countries. This agreement replaces a previous agreement on the same topic from 1953. The focus of the agreement is the construction and operation of Wehdah Dam on the Yarmouk River. The responsibilities of each country are specified. Jordan is primarily responsible for the financing, construction, operation, and maintenance of the dam and its related infrastructure. Syria commits to providing access for Jordanian personnel to areas within its territory necessary for the project's implementation. Syria is also responsible for compensating landowners affected by expropriation within its borders, although Jordan bears the financial burden of this compensation. Syria has the right to utilize water from all springs within its territory within the Yarmouk Basin, except those above the dam below a specific elevation. It also maintains the right to use water from the river below the dam for irrigation. Jordan gains the right to utilize the overflow from the Wahdah Dam reservoir for power generation and other purposes. The agreement stipulates a 75%-25% split of the electricity generated by the Wahdah Dam hydroelectric installation, favoring Syria. The agreement establishes a "Joint Syria-Jordan Commission," with equal representation, as a legal entity to oversee its implementation. This commission is tasked with:

- **Implementation and Dispute Resolution:** Ensuring the agreement's provisions are carried out and resolving any differences that may arise during its implementation.
- **Regulation and Supervision:** Regulating and supervising all aspects related to the project, including water usage, power generation, and maintenance activities.

The construction started just after signing the investment agreement with Syria² in 2001. The agreement seeks to encourage and protect investments made by investors from both countries in each other's territories. The agreement emphasizes creating favorable conditions for investors by providing necessary facilities and permissions. Both countries are committed to treating investments from the other country fairly and equitably, extending treatment no less favorable than that accorded to their citizens or any third country. The agreement includes provisions to protect investments from expropriation, nationalization, or any actions having similar effects without prompt and adequate compensation. A mechanism for dispute resolution is outlined, including options for conciliation, arbitration, or referral to relevant judicial bodies. The agreement ensures the unrestricted transfer of funds related to investments, including capital, profits, proceeds from liquidation, loan repayments, and income earned by foreign employees. A joint committee is established to oversee the agreement's implementation and address any challenges. For disputes between the countries regarding the agreement's interpretation or application, the process includes consultations and potential referral to an arbitration tribunal. The agreement has a duration of 10 years, subject to automatic renewal.

Agreement between Jordan and Saudi

In April 2015, Jordan and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia agreed with the management and utilization of groundwaters in the Al- Disi/ Saq aquifer. The agreement has four main articles. The agreement calls for the liquidation of all existing activities in the protected areas (prohibited areas), which depends on the extraction of groundwaters. Monitoring wells are constructed to monitor the quality and level of groundwater. A Joint Technical Committee (JTC) is established to coordinate the tasks assigned for each party. The main responsibilities of the JTC include: 1) supervision of implementation of the terms of the agreement, 2) supervision and observation of groundwater quantity and quality, 3) collection and exchange of information, statements, studies and analysis.

² The agreement is available at: [Jordan - Syrian Arab Republic BIT \(2001\) - Electronic Database of Investment Treaties \(EDIT\) \(wti.org\)](#)

3 Stakeholders Mapping and Analysis

In Jordan, the Ministry of Water and Irrigation is the main governmental body at the national level that is responsible for planning, policy, and oversight. Water Authority of Jordan (WAJ), and Jordan Valley Authority (JVA) are responsible for managing bulk water resources and capital investments. Water companies, like Miyahuna and Water Users Associations (WUAs) are responsible for service delivery, operation, and maintenance. In this section, institutional framework governing water management, particularly transboundary water management will be explained. In addition, the policy environment governing water management, and agreements governing transboundary water resources will be discussed.

3.1 Stakeholders Mapping

Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWI) is the official body on the national level responsible for the overall monitoring of the water sector, water supply, wastewater systems and related projects, planning and management, the formulation of national water strategies and policies, research and development, information systems, and procurement of financial resources. Its role also includes the provision of centralized water-related data and standardization and consolidation of data. The MWI is responsible for overall national leadership on policy, strategic direction and planning, in coordination with Water Authority of Jordan (WAJ) and Jordan Valley Authority (JVA).

Water Authority of Jordan (WAJ) is an independent entity under the responsibility of the MWI. It is responsible for the operational management of the water sector, which includes bulk water supply and retail distribution, where commercialization of distribution services has not occurred. WAJ is mandated for all operational functions of the water sector including management of water and wastewater services; regulation of construction and quality of service provision projects, operations and maintenance; monitoring of all levels of sector services; and supervision of the water utilities and water companies through the Project Management Unit (PMU).

Jordan Valley Authority (JVA) is responsible for the socioeconomic development of the Jordan Valley, primarily manages bulk water supply for irrigation, domestic and industrial purposes and promotes land development in the Valley. The JVA is also responsible for water resources development, improving the environment, hydroelectric power, tourism, industry and other beneficial uses in the Valley, as well as setting all necessary regulations to control the use of water in farm units, oversight of irrigation networks and agricultural road networks, and implementation of master and detailed plans for lands outside the planning authority of municipalities. The JVA has organized Water Users Associations (WUA's) in Jordan Valley to encourage community and private sector participation in managing public resources and to provide services for its customers.

There are other entities that are considered stakeholders in water management, and transboundary water management. These entities include:

Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA)

The Ministry of Foreign Affairs engages in diplomatic negotiations and agreements related to water sharing with neighboring countries. The ministry seeks to realize the objectives of the Jordanian foreign policy, protect the best national interest in Jordan and abroad, and rely on the sophisticated and rigorous institutional approach that commits to directives and legislation through collective action.

Ministry of Environment (MoEnv.)

The Ministry of Environment focuses on environmental protection and sustainability aspects of water resources. Environmental protection and sustainability of water resources management cannot be overemphasized. The contribution of the Ministry of Environment to transboundary water management is immense, as most projects in this sector have extensive environmental impacts that may affect biodiversity and its sustainability. The Environmental Impact Assessments taken by the MoEnv. can either improve or disqualify transboundary water projects based on their long-term environmental impacts.

Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation (MoPIC)

The Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation in Jordan performs many core functions in water management, it embeds the water strategies into the national development plans, coordinates with donors at the international level to secure funds and oversees that implementation process. MoPIC coordinates water management according to economic and social goals, organizes Public-Private Partnerships (PPP), and is involved in regional and international cooperation on transboundary water resources. In addition, the ministry aligns Jordan's efforts on water with the UN Sustainable Development Goals, largely dwelling on water sustainability and availability.

Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)

The main body at the national level is responsible for the agriculture sector. The MoA is primarily responsible for designing and implementing agriculture sector policies (crops, livestock, forestry, water harvesting, etc.), and for providing technical assistance and extension services. The MoA has several sections and departments governing different aspects in the agriculture sector. Within the MoA, there are multiple departments governing several agronomy aspects (plant production, livestock production, etc.). MoA is responsible for on-farm water management through the promotion of increasing water use efficiency. There are governmental institutions that belong to the ministry of agriculture. These include National Agriculture Research Center (NARC), Agriculture Credit Corporation (ACC), and Jordan Cooperative Corporation (JCC). NARC aims to invest the results of agricultural research, whether locally derived or adopted from other sources, in order to increase plant & animal production, enhancing its efficiency towards an optimal and sustainable use of natural agricultural resources and serving the agricultural development goals to maintain an ecological balance. ACC contributes to supporting, developing and enhancing agriculture, as well as increasing production and improving it quantitatively and qualitatively to increase living standards by means of providing loans to farmers to support agricultural activities.

Ministry of Finance (MoF)

The Ministry of Finance in Jordan plays a major role in the management of water resources by ensuring adequate allocation of budgetary resources towards water infrastructure projects and related activities. Its responsibility, therefore, becomes funding the construction, maintenance, and upgrading of water facilities like dams, treatment plants, and distribution networks. The Ministry also oversees financial planning for investments in the water sector and is mandated to raise loans and grants from international financial institutions and donors. Further, the Ministry of Finance impacts water pricing policies and subsidies to ensure that the prices are affordable to all consumers while allowing for the financial sustainability of water services. It helps to ensure that the management of Jordan's water resources is financially viable and efficient in the long term.

International Financing Institutes

International financing institutions (Such as World Bank, IFC, IMF, etc.) play a vital role in supporting Jordan's efforts to combat its worsening water crisis by providing the necessary financial and technical backing for large-scale infrastructure projects. Through their support, they help rehabilitate critical infrastructure such as dams, irrigation networks, and water treatment plants, which are essential for ensuring reliable access to clean water. They also fund climate adaptation initiatives designed to strengthen resilience against droughts, floods, and other impacts of environmental change. In addition, these institutions assist in building the capacity of national and local institutions responsible for water governance, supporting reforms that enhance transparency and efficiency.

International Donors

International donors also have a role in water management through providing funding and technical assistance to the government of Jordan to improve water security. These include, United States Agency for International Development (USAID), European Union (EU), Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA), The Japan International Agency (JICA), The Embassy of the Netherlands.

International Organizations

These include international organizations that provide technical support to improve Jordan's water sector. These include Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), United Nations Organizations like UNDP, FAO, UNEP, etc.

Entities working in the sector (water, transboundary, water management)

There are several national and international entities working on water management, transboundary water management, irrigation efficiency, climate change adaptation like INWRDAM, Blue Peace Middle East, Mercy Corps, ECO Consult, etc. These entities implement development projects that contribute directly/indirectly to water management. In addition, suppliers of technologies are considered as stakeholders as they provide technologies to Jordan's market.

Academia and Research Institutes

Academia and research institutes play an essential role in water management by providing scientific data and promotes Data to Decision (D2D) approaches, in addition to developing innovative solutions for better water management, irrigation technology, wastewater treatment and reuse. They are a main player in data collection and educating the new generation about water security besides water management and integrated water resources management.

3.2 Power- Interest Analysis

Figure 8 shows the power- interest of different stakeholders involved in water management, specifically transboundary water management. The Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWI), JVA, WAJ, MoEnv. MoPIC, MoF, MoFA, World Bank, EU, KFW, and USAID have high power. However, the interest of those entities varies. MWI, WAJ, JVA have the highest power and highest interest as they are directly involved in transboundary water issues. MWI is the core decision maker about any water management issues (national and transboundary). MoPIC also holds high interest as it has strategic interest as it is responsible for international cooperation. MoEnv. has lower interest in transboundary water issues but has high interest in environmental sustainability in which water is part of it. There national and international non-governmental organizations working on water management, and there are ones who work closely on

transboundary water management. Therefore, the interest of the organizations differs. Blue Peace and the Water Diplomacy center focuses primarily on transboundary water management. SDC holds its power as it has financial resources that contribute to improving cooperation among transboundary issues. Blue Peace has lower power, but also have high interest as they are directly linked to implementing initiatives related to transboundary water and aim at improving cooperation. International donors like the embassy of the Netherlands have the financial resources, but they have lower power than other organizations like USAID, KFW, World Bank. GIZ, INWRDAM, and other entities have moderate power and interest. Their interest is more towards national water management that indirectly impacts transboundary water issues. A fair degree of interest is also demonstrated by universities and research institutes that support research and the transmission of information, such as the Stockholm International Water Institute (SIWI), the WANA Institute, and the Royal Scientific Society. Finally, although playing a significant role on the ground, Water Utilities, Water Users Associations (WUAs), Farmers, and Local Communities show modest degrees of influence and interest in water management concerns. This illustrates their relatively limited yet crucial participation in the industry. Although they are immediately impacted by the choices and methods used in water management, they have little influence on legislation and high-level talks.

Figure 8: Stakeholders Categories Based on Power- Interest Analysis

3.3 Stakeholders Value Map

Figure 9 shows the relationships and interactions among stakeholders considering their power and interest. MWI, WAJ, JVA, and MoPIC are the core stakeholders. MWI is the core decision maker regarding water management and transboundary water issues. MoPIC is responsible for international cooperation and is therefore considered a core stakeholder in transboundary water management. The Ministry of Environment (MoEnv.) affects the decision of the MWI regarding large water projects, as it is responsible for issuing approval regarding the environmental and impact of these large projects. However, in some cases where the national priorities govern the decisions, the environmental impact assessment is not considered for example, the National Water Carrier project. Despite its negative impact on the dead sea, it has been approved as providing domestic water is a national priority. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Agriculture, and Ministry of Finance are placed as direct influencers over the transboundary

water management, they can enhance the decisions of the MWI as they are impacted by the availability of financial resources and their distribution over the national priorities of the government, such as MoF. Agricultural expansion and food security in the national level priorities might have direct impact of the MoA over the decision of MWI, while MoFA should maintain the international interest with neighboring countries. International financing institutes and international donors come in the direct influence category, their direct influence is high over governmental decisions as they provide finance, expertise, and policy advice, mainstreaming national activities, and policy decisions from international and regional perspectives, the support of the World Bank is usually linked to regional reforms strategies which includes the transboundary water management. KFW, EU, and USAID provide substantial financing resources to the Jordanian water sector, therefore, they can influence the decisions over transboundary water management by improving the water security at the national level. International organizations' influence, in most cases, is indirect as they provide capacity building in water resource management at the national level such as GIZ, JICA, UNDP. This type of support can make them more efficient and might change the government's priorities as their support has a key role in water management and governance. Academia and research centers —the third category— have an indirect influence. They serve as hubs for data collation, learning, dissemination of awareness, and scientific research. They can indirectly influence the policies. Entities such as WDC, Blue Peace and ECO Peace indirectly affect transboundary water management. They pave the road by enhancing cooperation and bridging the needs of different national and regional levels. Farmers and local communities impact the management of the transboundary waters. However, their position may vary between direct and indirect, depending on the level of awareness towards the water situation in Jordan, the political aspects of the decisions, and their interests in water availability. For example, farmers can enhance the decision of the MoA which will impact the decisions of MWI as explained before.

Legend:

- 1- The three circles represent the stakeholders' categories.
- 2- Lines with one head represent "one-way" impact on decision.
- 3- Lines with two heads represent "two ways" impact on decision.
- 4- Lines thickness represent higher impact on decision

Figure 9: Jordan Transboundary Water Management Stakeholders' Value Map

4 Political Economy Analysis

4.1 Political Factors Analysis

4.1.1 Geopolitical Relations

Jordan's historical relationships with its neighboring countries, particularly regarding shared water resources, have been shaped by a mixture of cooperation and enduring tensions. With Israel, the 1994 Peace Treaty brought about a formal water-sharing agreement, allocating Jordan a certain share from the Jordan River, and establishing a Joint Water Committee to manage water issues. This agreement marked a significant milestone in regional cooperation, and Jordan has generally maintained a consistent share of the Jordan River's water. A more recent development is the 2021 water-for-energy deal between Israel and Jordan, where Jordan agreed to supply solar power in exchange for increased desalinated water. This reflects the ongoing adjustments made to meet contemporary needs.

A more complex relationship exists between Jordan and Syria concerning the Yarmouk River. The first water-sharing agreement between the two countries was signed in 1987, but the construction of new upstream dams by Syria, along with increased water withdrawals, has reduced the flow of the Yarmouk River into Jordan. Historically, in the 1950s, the river's mean annual flow was estimated between 450 to 500 MCM, however, a recent study by Bashabsheh et. al. (2024) estimated the flow has drastically decreased between 83 to 99 MCM. This situation has been aggravated by Syria's ongoing civil war, making enforcement and renegotiation of the agreement challenging. Consequently, Jordan often receives less than its agreed share, exacerbating water shortages in the northern regions. Moreover, there is limited data sharing between the two countries on the management of the Yarmouk, with both blaming reduced flows on various factors, including climate change and upstream development.

In the case of groundwater resources, Jordan's relationship with Saudi Arabia concerning the Disi Aquifer exemplifies cooperation. The 2015 agreement between the two countries established monitoring and management systems to ensure the sustainable use of the aquifer, emphasizing regional cooperation in groundwater protection due to the scarcity of surface water. Historically, the 1950s Johnston Plan attempted to allocate the water of the Jordan River Basin among Jordan, Israel, Syria, and Lebanon, with Jordan allocated the largest share. While never ratified, the plan remains a reference point for discussions on equitable resource allocation in the region. These agreements highlight Jordan's reliance on cooperative arrangements to secure water resources but also reveal the challenges posed by political tensions that hinder effective transboundary water management.

Regional political dynamics, alliances, and conflicts have further complicated Jordan's position in water negotiations. Syria's internal conflict has hindered its ability and willingness to cooperate on shared water management, leaving Jordan to cope with erratic inflows from the Yarmouk River. While the 1994 peace treaty with Israel formalized water-sharing terms, disputes over water quantities and the timing of flows persist, especially during drought years. Jordan, as a downstream country, remains vulnerable to the control exerted by Israel and Syria over upstream water flows through diversions and dams. Additionally,

Jordan's dependence on foreign aid and its limited financial resources further restricts its ability to respond proactively to water shortages, especially when upstream countries prioritize their own needs during times of scarcity.

Recent political developments have emphasized the need for Jordan to diversify its water strategy, at least through regional cooperation and the use of alternative sources envisioned by the National Water Strategy 2023-2040. The Jordan Valley Unified Water Plan, more popularly known as the Johnston Plan, was a US-mediated water allocation proposal that, during the 1950s, sought to manage the Jordan River Basin's water resources among Jordan, Israel, Syria, and Lebanon. Named after US Envoy Eric Johnston, it aimed to distribute water from the Jordan River Basin, including its tributaries the Yarmouk, and Litani Rivers. Jordan was allocated the largest share of 55%, Israel 26%, and smaller allocations were given to Syria and Lebanon. The Plan was based on the allocation of water for the irrigable land, assuming agriculture to be the leading water user in the basin. Each country was, hence, to have full control over its share of the water, enabling even transfers outside of the basin, as practiced today by Israel to supply the Mediterranean coast, while Jordan brings in water from distant sources such as the Disi aquifer.

Over time, the plan became outdated as priorities for water use shifted from agriculture to domestic needs, and domestic water use accounted for nearly half the amount used in Jordan and Israel by 2015 (Talozi, 2019). Agricultural use has increasingly utilized recycled wastewater, thereby reducing freshwater demand. Israel also began to overdraw its allocations following the occupation of the Golan Heights and leveraging its hydro-hegemonic influence. While it was never officially ratified by all parties and was rejected by the League of Arab States, the plan did include major allocations between Jordan and Israel, and it is still considered an important reference in water negotiations within the region. Despite the importance of this agreement, the political status between the Arab countries and Israel was a barrier to the realization of the agreed-on terms, in addition, this political sensitivity between Syria and Israel and the main goal of electricity generation via the Banat Yacov Project was impossible to initiate because of its location that must pass through the demilitarized zone between the two countries. Jordan and Israel committed to resolve their differences over their rights to the Jordan basin's waters as part of the Peace Treaty 1994. As a consequence, Israel will retain all of the upper Jordan basin's waters, which amount to about 600 MCM annually. Jordan is allotted a smaller amount of the mainstream waters and a larger percentage of Yarmouk's flow in the basin's lower portion. The amount of water Jordan will be given access to is significantly less than that of the 1950s Johnston Plan (Beaumont, 1997).

The Yarmouk River is an important source in Jordan's northern regions; due to Syria's increasing consumption upstream, its inflows have drastically decreased. Jordan was allocated 50 million cubic meters per year through bilateral agreements; at present, Syria pumps more water and builds dams, resulting in less than 20 million cubic meters a year. Besides, Jordan's renegotiations or the enforcement of consistent water-sharing have been complicated by Syria's internal political instability wrought by its ongoing civil conflict. The United Nations ESCWA mentions that internal Syrian disputes affect Jordan in regular water flows, raising its vulnerability to upstream control of water. Since the 1960s, Yarmouk River flows have declined more than 85%, Syria and Jordan blame each other for the decline and have both developed their explanatory narratives: Jordan considers that Syria violated their 1987 agreement by building more dams than what was agreed on, while Syria blames climate change (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10: Sketch of the infrastructure in the Yarmouk tributary basin (Source: Zeitoun et al. 2019)

As the two countries do not share information, neither on hydrological flows or water management, it is increasingly difficult to distinguish between natural and anthropogenic factors affecting the flow regime (Nicolas Avisse, 2020). The bulk of the water abstracted from the Yarmouk Basin is used for agriculture in the Hauran Plain (which is mainly in southern Syria, though extends into northern Jordan); to a lesser extent, the abstracted water is used in what is known as the Yarmouk Triangle, the land between the confluence of the Jordan and the Yarmouk, the Lake of Tiberias, and al Himmeh/Hamet Gader which is mainly in Israel. The abstraction comes through a suite of uncoordinated infrastructure elaborated upon in Zeitoun et al. (2019) and as shown in **Figure 10**. This includes thousands of wells in Syria and Jordan (Al-Husein, 2007; UN-ESCWA/BGR, 2013; Margane, 2015), the Wehdeh Dam between Syria and Jordan, dozens of dams in Syria (discussed below), three dams in Jordan, four Israeli dams in the Occupied Golan Heights, the King Abdullah Canal in Jordan (Mustafa and Talozzi, 2018), and the 'water exchange' infrastructure (which includes the Adassiyeh diversion weir) built between the Lake of Tiberias and the Yarmouk tributary by Jordan and Israel.

In general, politically sensitive transboundary water resources, are represented primarily by the Jordan and Yarmouk Rivers. This has put Jordan in a vulnerable position of geopolitical dynamics from upstream countries, especially Syria and Israel. The base for cooperative water sharing was first provided by the "Jordan Valley Unified Water Plan", or the Johnston Plan, in the 1950s with proposed allocations that, although never officially ratified, continue to have an impact on regional water management discussions. Due to the political tension especially between Syria and Israel, partial implementation forced Jordan to sign subsequent agreements on less favorable terms for access to water. Disputes regarding the Yarmouk River further illustrate the compressed position Jordan is in. Syria's increased upstream consumption is driven by new dam constructions and greater water withdrawals. Inconsistent hydrological data from Syria into Jordan exacerbates this issue and makes it hard to distinguish between natural factors, such as climate change, contributing to declining flows, or human-induced impacts. Recent developments in Syria's political landscape have significant implications for transboundary water management with neighboring countries, including Jordan. The new Syrian government, led by Hayat Tahrir al-Sham, has expressed intentions to dismantle the socialist economic policies of the Assad era. This shift includes plans to privatize state-owned assets, attract foreign investment, and enhance international trade. Foreign Minister Asaad al-Shaibani emphasized the need for legal reforms to attract foreign investors and incentivize Syrian expatriates to return. He also highlighted the importance of lifting U.S. and European sanctions to enable

recovery, prioritizing essential services like bread, water, electricity, and fuel. In a recent interview conducted in January 2025, Syria's Minister of Water Resources, Ahmed Abu Zeid, acknowledged the severe impact of international sanctions on the water sector. He emphasized the importance of reevaluating water agreements with neighboring countries, including Jordan, to ensure mutual benefits and enhance water security for Syria and its neighbors. Abu Zeid outlined the government's broader strategy to restore control over water resources. This is an opportunity, where Jordan can negotiate the existing agreements and adjust according to needs.

As Jordan moves forward, plans such as the National Conveyor (Aqaba-Amman desalination plant) mark Jordan's active step toward autonomous reliability for water supply. Although regional cooperation remains a challenge, Jordan's concentration on internal infrastructure and alternative water solutions becomes one more indicator of Jordan's determination to tackle the critical situation with water supply in conditions of such political instability.

4.1.2 *Jordan's Commitment Toward Water Diplomacy and Cooperation*

Jordan has made water diplomacy and cooperation a national priority, aligning its efforts with the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Adopted on September 25, 2015 by the United Nations, the SDGs introduced a comprehensive framework for addressing global challenges, including **SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation**, which focuses on ensuring the availability and sustainable management of water resources. Unlike the narrower scope of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), SDG 6 tackles a wide range of issues such as water quality, wastewater treatment, water scarcity, and Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM). It features 11 indicators to measure progress, with a particular focus on transboundary water cooperation through **SDG 6.5**. This goal is measured through two critical indicators:

- **Indicator 6.5.1:** Tracks the implementation of IWRM principles, evaluating the effectiveness of policies, institutional frameworks, and cooperation to ensure sustainable water use.
- **Indicator 6.5.2:** Measures the proportion of transboundary basin areas with operational water cooperation arrangements, promoting effective management of shared resources and reducing risks of conflict and environmental degradation.

Jordan's National Water Strategy 2023–2040 reflects its alignment with SDG 6, emphasizing efficient use of available water resources, sourcing alternatives, and adopting climate-resilient approaches to secure water availability. The country's commitment is evident in its regular reporting on SDG indicators, meeting international standards for transparency, accountability, and water security. Jordan has also established itself as a proactive participant in regional and global platforms for water diplomacy. As a member of the Arab Ministerial Water Council and a partner with the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia (ESCWA), Jordan actively collaborates on harmonizing regional water policies. Initiatives such as the Blue Peace Middle East Initiative exemplify Jordan's leadership in using water as an instrument for dialogue, equity, and peacebuilding in a region where shared water resources are often a source of tension.

Globally, Jordan has formed strategic partnerships with institutions like the World Bank, particularly on large-scale projects such as the Red Sea-Dead Sea Project. This initiative, involving Israel and Palestine, not only aims to address Jordan's acute water shortages but also fosters multilateral cooperation, positioning water as a shared resource that can promote regional stability. Additionally, collaborations with organizations such as the Geneva Water Hub and the Blue Peace Middle East Initiative provide Jordan with valuable technical expertise, governance support, and confidence-building measures that strengthen its water diplomacy.

Jordan’s approach to transboundary water management highlights its dedication to long-term cooperation and good governance. This is evident in its history of bilateral agreements, starting with the Johnston Plan (1953- 1955) and extending to more recent accords such as the Disi agreement with Saudi Arabia. Mechanisms such as joint technical committees, established under agreements like the 1994 Peace Treaty with Israel and the arrangement with Syria for the Yarmouk River, underscore the importance of cooperative frameworks in resolving disputes and ensuring equitable resource distribution. While challenges remain, these mechanisms reflect Jordan’s commitment to fostering effective collaboration.

The National Water Strategy 2023–2040 reinforces Jordan’s dedication to SDG principles by addressing key areas such as transboundary cooperation, sanitation, and integrated resource management. The Swiss-Jordanian partnership through the Blue Peace initiative further illustrates the importance of dialogue and trust-building in overcoming governance challenges and ensuring sustainable management of shared water resources. This collaboration underscores the recognition of water as a strategic resource essential for peace and security.

Jordan’s sustained efforts in water diplomacy, supported by regional and international partnerships, demonstrate its commitment to addressing immediate water challenges while contributing to broader goals of sustainable development and regional stability. By adopting a cooperative and integrated approach, Jordan exemplifies how shared water resources can transform from a potential source of conflict into a platform for collaboration and mutual benefit, paving the way for peace and prosperity across borders.

4.1.3 SDG 6.5 and Existing Agreements

According to the IWRM Action Hub (2024), Jordan scored 64 in the 2020–2021 data collection cycle for SDG 6.5.1 (Figure 11), reflecting a medium-high status of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) implementation. The country demonstrated medium-high implementation levels for the Enabling Environment, Institutional Arrangements, and Finance components, while Management Instruments scored high.

Figure 11: IWRM Score for SDG6.5.1 for Jordan

With regard to Indicator 6.5.2, Jordan has submitted its National Report for 2023. According to the report, the SDG 6.5.2 indicator result is 25.7% (Figure 12). This percentage indicates the surface area of

transboundary resources covered by operational arrangements. This means, the significant area is still not covered by operational arrangements.

Figure 12: SDG Indicator 6.5.2 worldwide (UN,2023)

While there are operational arrangements, mentioned in section 2.2.4, these arrangements still face challenges and gaps remain. The below sub-sections provide an evaluation of the existing agreements in terms of institutional Support, data sharing, conflict resolution mechanism, and climate change adaptability, and enforcement. The evaluation is summarized in **Table 5**.

The Peace Treaty Between Jordan and Israel in 1994

The 1994 Jordan-Israel Peace Treaty demonstrates strong institutional support, including the establishment of a joint water committee for regular data sharing. However, it has notable gaps. The treaty lacks comprehensive provisions for water pollution and climate adaptability, raising concerns about potential disputes over water flow and quality as climatic conditions change.

It also fails to take an integrative approach to managing all shared water resources, particularly the Yarmouk River, and does not provide clear mechanisms for resolving conflicts over water allocation and quality. Provisions for stakeholder involvement, data transparency, and alignment with national water policies are weak, and there is no system for sustained monitoring or evaluation of water management practices. Additionally, the treaty does not connect water management strategies with broader economic goals, missing opportunities for joint development projects that could foster economic growth and improve resource management.

The Yarmouk River Basin Agreement with Syria

The Jordan-Syria Yarmouk Agreement faces implementation challenges due to inconsistent political relations, resulting in irregular enforcement and unresolved disputes. It lacks detailed mechanisms for dispute resolution and fails to adequately consider the economic and social impacts on communities along the river. Additionally, the agreement does not provide for joint economic projects or harmonize with the national water policies of both countries. Strengthening mechanisms for political cooperation, dispute resolution, and local stakeholder involvement, along with aligning the agreement with national strategies, is essential for improving its effectiveness. Considering the recent developments, Jordan could benefit from this and revise existing agreement and start negotiations with the new government.

Disi agreement between Jordan and Saudi

The Disi Agreement between Jordan and Saudi Arabia regulates the use of the shared Disi aquifer but has significant gaps in addressing political, economic, and environmental challenges. It lacks provisions for joint economic projects or investments that could enhance the benefits derived from the aquifer. There are no detailed mechanisms for resolving disputes over water allocation, and the agreement fails to account for the local economic impacts on communities dependent on the aquifer. Furthermore, it is not fully aligned with the national economic policies of either country, which limits its effectiveness and coherence with broader development strategies.

Table 5: Agreements and their effectiveness according to evaluation criteria

Agreement	Institutional Support	Data Sharing	Conflict Resolution Mechanism	Climate Change Adaptability	Enforcement
Jordan-Israel Peace Treaty (1994)	Includes a joint water committee for managing shared water resources.	Annual data sharing is conducted regularly.	Relies on the joint water committee, but lacks detailed mechanisms for disputes over water allocation and quality.	Does not address climate change adaptability, focusing primarily on water allocation.	Institutional arrangements ensure a degree of enforcement, though gaps remain in implementation.
Jordan-Syria Yarmouk Agreement (2001)	Establishes a Joint Commission, but its effectiveness is influenced by political relations.	Data sharing is irregular and less comprehensive.	Ad hoc mechanisms dependent on political circumstances; lacks consistent frameworks for resolving disputes.	Does not include provisions to address climate change impacts.	Implementation and enforcement are inconsistent, especially during political tensions.
Jordan-Saudi Disi Aquifer (2015)	Includes a joint technical committee for aquifer monitoring and management.	Data sharing is limited to aquifer monitoring and does not include deeper aquifer layers.	Focuses on the joint technical committee but lacks detailed provisions for addressing disputes.	Contains limited or no measures to address climate change impacts or groundwater stress.	Enforcement is constrained by the agreement's limited scope and institutional capacity.

The effectiveness of the below mechanisms in addressing transboundary water management challenges varies:

- **Conflict Resolution:** The Jordan-Israel Peace Treaty has been relatively successful in resolving disputes, supported by the Joint Water Committee's active engagement. However, the Jordan-Syria Agreement remains weak due to the lack of enforcement and limited collaboration, especially during periods of political instability.
- **Data Sharing:** While the Jordan-Israel Peace Treaty facilitates regular data sharing through its joint committee, other agreements, such as the Jordan-Saudi Disi Aquifer Agreement, are more limited in scope, focusing primarily on aquifer monitoring. The Jordan-Syria Agreement suffers from irregular data sharing, further complicating resource management.
- **Sustainable Water Usage:** Efforts under the Jordan-Saudi Agreement to promote sustainable aquifer use represent progress, but the absence of climate adaptation measures in most agreements limits their long-term effectiveness. Similarly, the Jordan-Israel Peace Treaty has faced challenges during droughts, which strain allocations and highlight the need for adaptive measures.

4.1.4 Political Landscape and Power Dynamics

Jordan's transboundary water management is a complex arena shaped by a confluence of national, regional, and international factors.

4.1.4.1 National Level Dynamics

At the national level, the government institutions responsible for water management in Jordan are powerful players in shaping policies related to water resources. The Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWI) and the Jordan Valley Authority (JVA) are the main authorities overseeing the use and management of the country's limited water resources, including the water shared with neighboring countries. MWI is in charge of developing and implementing national policies related to water resources, while the JVA oversees the administration of water in the Jordan Valley and agricultural water management.

These institutions operate within a broader system of ministries and agencies, each of which has its own influence on how water resources are governed. For example, the Ministry of Environment (MoEnv) holds sway over water resource management by ensuring that environmental considerations, such as water quality and the protection of ecosystems, are taken into account in decision-making. The Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation (MoPIC) plays a key role in coordinating international aid and funding for water projects. Similarly, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA) is involved in negotiating with neighboring countries over transboundary water agreements, such as those related to the shared water basins of the Jordan River.

The decision-making process within these ministries can sometimes be fragmented, as different actors have different priorities, particularly when it comes to managing scarce resources. This fragmentation can lead to competing interests within the government and between different ministries, making it challenging to implement a unified, comprehensive water policy. Moreover, the overlapping mandates of various governmental bodies may complicate efforts to coordinate on transboundary water issues with neighboring countries.

4.1.4.2 Regional Power Dynamics and Transboundary Water Sharing

Jordan's water resources are shared with neighboring countries, including Israel, Syria, and Saudi Arabia, making transboundary water management a politically sensitive issue. The Jordan River Basin, one of the most contested water systems in the region, exemplifies these challenges. The river and its tributaries are vital to Jordan's water supply but have also been a source of tension as nations compete for access. Political

negotiations and treaties, such as the 1994 Israel-Jordan Peace Treaty, have attempted to regulate shared water resources, though disputes over allocation and enforcement persist.

Israel's advanced water infrastructure, including desalination plants and wastewater recycling systems, gives it significant leverage in regional water politics. Its control over upstream sources, such as the Sea of Galilee and much of the Jordan River, further strengthens its strategic advantage. For Jordan, which relies heavily on these shared resources to meet domestic needs and sustain agriculture in the Jordan Valley, this power imbalance creates vulnerabilities. While agreements like the 1994 treaty allocate a fixed amount of water to Jordan, enforcement has been inconsistent, particularly during periods of drought, leaving Jordanian communities at risk.

Saudi Arabia also plays a critical role in shaping water dynamics in the region, particularly through its exploitation of the Disi Aquifer, a non-renewable resource shared with Jordan. Saudi Arabia's financial resources and focus on agricultural self-sufficiency have enabled it to invest heavily in projects that rely on the aquifer, often at Jordan's expense. Lacking the technological and financial capacity to compete, Jordan struggles to secure an equitable share of the aquifer's water while grappling with population growth and the strain of hosting refugees. This asymmetry complicates negotiations, as Saudi Arabia's economic leverage often overshadows Jordan's weaker bargaining position.

The interactions between Jordan, Israel, Saudi Arabia, and Syria highlight the intricate web of regional power dynamics surrounding water resources. Each country's approach reflects its strategic priorities: Israel's technological dominance, Saudi Arabia's agricultural ambitions, and Syria's upstream control over rivers like the Yarmouk all impact Jordan's water security. These dynamics are further complicated by broader geopolitical tensions, including the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, evolving Gulf alliances, and the fallout from the Syrian Civil War. For Jordan, navigating these relationships requires balancing diplomacy, pragmatism, and advocacy for equitable resource sharing.

International actors, such as the United States, the European Union, and regional organizations like the Arab League, also influence water management in the region. Their involvement often comes in the form of donor-funded infrastructure projects or aid packages, which can shift the balance of power. For example, initiatives like the Red Sea–Dead Sea Water Conveyance Project aim to address shared environmental challenges while fostering cooperation. However, external support may also condition aid on specific political outcomes, affecting negotiating leverage among the parties involved.

For Jordan, securing equitable access to shared water resources remains a delicate balancing act. The government relies on diplomatic relationships and strategic negotiations to navigate competing claims and shifting political climates. However, the power asymmetries—exacerbated by Israel's technological edge, Saudi Arabia's financial strength, and Syria's upstream control—pose significant challenges. Addressing these dynamics will require sustained efforts to promote sustainable water management, equitable sharing, and regional stability in the face of growing water scarcity and climate change.

4.1.4.3 Foreign Assistance and its Impact on Transboundary Water Management

Foreign assistance plays a central role in shaping Jordan's approach to transboundary water management. Jordan is highly dependent on external financial aid and technical expertise to address its severe water scarcity, which is compounded by the increasing pressures of climate change and a growing population. The country's water challenges are so acute that the government has turned to international donors and financial institutions for support in developing new water technologies, expanding infrastructure, and managing shared resources.

However, while foreign assistance can provide much-needed resources for water management, it also introduces new layers of complexity to Jordan's decision-making processes. On the one hand, foreign

assistance can help Jordan implement large-scale projects, such as wastewater treatment plants, desalination facilities, and advanced irrigation systems, that are critical to the country's long-term water security. These projects are often funded by international organizations such as the World Bank, USAID, and the European Union, which also provide technical expertise to help Jordan adopt best practices in water resource management.

On the other hand, foreign assistance can influence the power dynamics of water governance in subtle but significant ways. When foreign donors fund projects in Jordan, they often impose conditions or stipulations that may align with the donors' geopolitical or economic interests. For example, certain aid packages may require Jordan to prioritize projects that align with the donor country's foreign policy objectives or to adopt specific water technologies or management practices that benefit the donor country's industries. This can limit Jordan's policy autonomy, as the country may be pressured to adopt solutions that are not necessarily tailored to its unique needs or that may undermine its regional diplomatic strategies.

Moreover, the nature of foreign aid can create a dependency that makes it difficult for Jordan to independently manage its water resources in the long term. A reliance on external financing for water infrastructure projects might leave Jordan vulnerable to shifts in donor priorities or reductions in foreign aid. For instance, a sudden change in U.S. or European Union policy could result in reduced funding for water projects, which would significantly affect the country's ability to manage its water scarcity and its relationships with neighboring countries over shared resources.

Furthermore, foreign assistance can contribute to the fragmentation of Jordan's water policy. Donor organizations may prioritize different aspects of water management, such as infrastructure, capacity building, or environmental conservation, depending on their mandates and interests. This can lead to disjointed policy responses and an inability to implement a unified, comprehensive strategy for transboundary water management. The resulting fragmentation can further complicate Jordan's efforts to negotiate with neighboring countries or engage in joint water resource management initiatives.

4.2 Economic Factors

4.2.1 Jordan's Economic Situation Impact on Transboundary Water Management

Jordan's economic situation plays a significant role in its ability to effectively manage transboundary water resources. The country faces substantial economic challenges, primarily due to its high levels of public debt, reliance on foreign aid, and limited domestic financial resources (World Bank, 2023). These financial constraints impact Jordan's capacity to invest in and implement large-scale water management projects, particularly those involving transboundary water resources.

A significant portion of Jordan's economy is dependent on foreign aid, which is vital for funding various development projects, including those aimed at addressing the country's water scarcity issues (USAID, 2023). Transboundary water management projects, such as those related to the Red Sea-Dead Sea Water Conveyance Project, often require substantial external funding. However, the country's fiscal limitations and reliance on international aid can delay the implementation of such projects, hindering efforts to secure sustainable water solutions (World Bank, 2023).

The economic pressures faced by Jordan are further exacerbated by the effects of climate change. Projections indicate that climate change will reduce precipitation in the region, increasing water scarcity and further complicating the management of shared water resources. This adds additional strain to

Jordan's already limited financial resources, making it difficult to allocate sufficient funds for long-term water security and infrastructure development (UNEP, 2023).

Additionally, Jordan's economic challenges affect its ability to maintain and upgrade water infrastructure, which is crucial for managing the shared waters of the Jordan River, the Yarmouk River, and other regional water bodies. Cooperation with neighboring countries, such as Israel and Syria, is essential for managing these water resources, but Jordan's financial limitations often complicate negotiations and the funding of cross-border projects (World Bank, 2023).

4.2.2 *Economic Dependence on Water*

Water scarcity in Jordan has deep economic impacts, affecting multiple sectors relying heavily on water resources. The agriculture sector is highly dependent on water availability, consuming more than 50% of the total available resources, thus, it is of the most sensitive sectors to water shortage. While agriculture uses a great deal of water, it contributes minimally to Jordan's economy in terms of its GDP and is plagued by inefficient irrigation that leads to over-extraction and waste of irrigation water. As the quantity of available water decreases, crop yields to decrease and threaten food security and livelihoods in rural areas. This has made the government explore other alternatives like the use of treated wastewater and the use of crops with low water requirements; all these transitions are extremely expensive.

The industrial sector, with heavy reliance on resource-intensive industries such as food processing, textiles, and pharmaceuticals, is also affected by the water shortage. This limited access to water restricts growth and investment in many water-intensive industries. Inadequate dependable supplies deter foreign and domestic investments in industry, limit its expansion, and raise operation costs that must be passed on to the consumer. In the absence of innovative water-saving technology or adequate non-conventional water resources, such as desalinated water, Jordan's industrial growth continues to be very limited.

Other highly affected areas include urban development. Cities need to heavily invest in infrastructures such as water distribution networks and wastewater treatment facilities to handle the pressure from an increasing population, hence increasing the cost of expanding a city and its real estate. At the same time, household costs go up due to the lack of enough water, and this enhances economic inequality since poor communities cannot afford to buy water.

Water pricing mechanisms, subsidies, and their implications

Jordan's water resources are often managed without comprehensive economic value. This means that water is not allocated at the correct prices based on its economic value; hence, its use can lead to over-extraction and consequently, inefficient use. In a transboundary setting, this may worsen the conflict and reduce the incentives for cooperation.

Household Water Tariffs

Tariffs were relatively low, reflecting the subsidized approach towards guaranteeing access to all. As demand increased within the 1990s due to urbanization and population growth, there was a felt need for better management of water that necessitated the gradual revision of tariffs to adequately reflect the cost of water supply and ensure its conservation. Starting from the 2000s, however, the government's more significant tariff increases began to bite as part of extensive reforms in the water sector, amidst louder calls to reduce subsidies and enhance efficiency in water use. In 2007, the Government of Jordan (GoJ) initiated an Integrated Water Tariff Reform Program, designed to hike tariffs successively every year for the operation costs to be covered. In the decade of the 2010s, however, the water sector continued to

experience newer challenges-especially due to the Syrian refugee crisis-which again raises pressure on water resources and services. A revision of tariffs was undertaken in 2014 to balance affordability for consumers with financial sustainability of the water utilities through the introduction of progressive pricing, where higher use means a higher per-unit cost. Most recently, a new water tariff has been issued, as alignment with the new National Water Strategy 2030-2040. The aim is to achieve water security, improve supply and service provided to subscribers, and ensure the financial sustainability of the sector, which currently has a debt of approximately 2.3 billion dinars. It is feared that this could reach 4 billion Jordan Dinar (JOD) by 2030 if the necessary measures are not taken to address the growing burden. Notably, the total cost of one cubic meter of water is 2.2 JOD, and the government subsidizes different consumption categories at varying rates, averaging 64% (MWI, 2023). **Table 6** outlines the tariff categories, water use, charge, and subsidy.

Table 6: Water Tariff Categories, Ranges, Tariffs, Subsidies, and Sanitation Fees (Data Source: MWI, Water Tariff)

Category	Range (m ³)	Tariff (JOD/ m ³)	Sanitation Tariff (JOD/ m ³)
First	0-6	0.25	0.23
Second	7-12	2.8- 5.55 (increase by 0.55 JOD per m ³)	0.33- 0.83 (increase by 0.1 JOD per m ³)
Third	13- 18	6.25- 7.58 (increase by 0.7 JOD per m ³)	1.33- 3.83 (increase by 0.5 JOD per m ³)
Fourth	19- 24	10.85- 16.35 (increase by 1.1 JOD per m ³)	4.53- 8.03 (increase by 0.7 JOD per m ³)
Fifth	25-30	17.75- 37.88 (increase by 1.4 JOD per m ³)	8.88- 13.13 (increase by 0.85 JOD per m ³)
Sixth	31-42	26.55- 46.35 (increase by 1.8 JOD per m ³)	14.08- 24.53 (increase by 0.95 JOD per m ³)
Seventh	43 and above	48.55- increase by 2.2 JOD per m ³	25.73- increase by 1.2 JOD per m ³

As shown in **Table 6**, the water tariff, subsidies, and sanitation fees are different as per the category. The impact on the users is as follows:

- **Low-income Households:** In these households, low tariffs for the first category take place, making the price of water cheaper. However, the price increases sharply for bigger families or households with a higher demand for the supply of water.
- **High-Income Households:** Most high-income households are charged a higher price for the consumption of water. Since high-income households usually consume more water than low-income households, their tariff rates might incentivize measures like saving water to reduce the cost of paying such tariffs.

Despite these increases, it has been assured by the government that subsidy continuation, especially to low-income families, would continue beyond the year 2028, but most households are worried about how they are going to meet these increased tariffs since more than 70% of Jordanian households fall under those categories. Economists argued that instead of raising tariffs, the government must focus on tackling the issue of high-water loss in the distribution system, which is mainly because of leaky infrastructure. They say better management and reduction of wastage of water will ease the shortage without adding to the

financial burden of already over-burdened consumers. This restructuring in the tariff is expected to strike a balance between financial sustainability and universal access to water, though sensitive management of public opinion on the ground and infrastructure improvements lie ahead.

Water tariffs- Jordan Valley

The water pricing and allocation system in the Jordan Valley has evolved since the 1960s. Initially, water was allocated based on crop-specific quotas, with volumetric pricing introduced at 1 Fils/m³ in 1961 (World Bank, 2016). Over time, changes in national priorities and resource availability led to modifications in the system, including the introduction of the Jordan Valley Development Law No.19 of 1988, which aimed to reduce groundwater abstraction through improved urban network efficiency and public awareness programs.

Between the 1960s and the 1980s, water quotas were based on crop water requirements. For instance, from mid-April to mid-December, vegetables received 2 mm of water per day, while citrus and bananas received 4 mm and 8 mm, respectively. However, these water-intensive crops, particularly bananas and citrus, contributed to inefficiency in water use. To address this, in the 1990s, the government froze cropping patterns and introduced "vegetable allowances" to limit the expansion of banana and citrus farms. Despite this, inequalities in water access persisted, with large landowners and profitable banana farms benefiting the most (IWMI, 2007).

The 1997–1999 drought led to significant reductions in water allocations for all crops, with citrus and banana farms particularly affected. In 2004, new quotas were established to align water supply with crop water requirements. The water tariff ranges between 0.008 to 0.015 JOD per m³.

Water for agriculture is heavily subsidized in Jordan; this means that the tariff farmers pay per cubic meter is extremely low compared to all other categories. The idea here is to keep the agricultural sector sustainable as it consumes a large amount of water.

Groundwater Wells Tariff

Water Tariff from groundwater is governed by the Ground Water by-law. The groundwater monitoring by-law (No. 14) was issued in 1961 followed by the groundwater by-law No.85 in 2002, which was subsequently updated in 2014 and 2015. These by-laws aimed to address decreasing groundwater levels and water quality degradation in various aquifers around the country. They also aimed to improve water management and regulate water waste to protect subsurface water pumped for usage via drilling wells. **Table 7** outlines the water tariff according to the well type, consumption, and salinity.

Table 7: Water Tariff according to well type, consumption, and salinity (MWI, Water Tarriff for private wells)

No.	Type	Range	Salinity (PPM)	Tariff Fils/m ³
1	Industrial Wells and Private Universities	First cubic meter (m ³)		500
2	Governmental Wells- Drinking	First cubic meter (m ³)		100
3	Governmental Wells- Agriculture	First cubic meter (m ³)		25
4	Agricultural well- Selling Potable Water	First cubic meter (m ³)		250
5	Agricultural wells- Selling non-potable Water	First cubic meter (m ³)		100
6		0-150,000		Free
		150,001- 200,000		5

	Agricultural wells with special exemptions (according to license conditions)	Above 200,000		60
7	Agricultural wells with specific salinity used only for agricultural purposes	0-150,000	0	Free
		Above 150,000	1,350 – 1,500	15
			1,500-2,000	10
			Above 2,000	5
8	Agricultural wells with deepening or replacement licenses	0-75,000		Free
		75,000-200,000		10
		Above 200,000		100
9	Official universities' wells + tourist wells + production wells	First cubic meter (m ³).		250
10	Illegal wells	0-10,000		150
		10,001-30,000		250
		Above 30,000		500
11	Agricultural wells with extraction permit (excluding Azraq basin)	Permitted Quantity as per the permit		Free
		Above the Permitted Quantity		60
	Private agricultural wells in the Azraq basin	Above permitted amount- 100,000		20
		Above 100,000		60

Few economic tools are used within the Jordanian water management framework. Key tools are underdeveloped—for example, water pricing, tariffs, tradeable water rights, and the valuation of virtual water. The absence of this tool lessens the capacity for a market base with solutions promoting efficient use, particularly in shared resources with their neighboring countries. The current water tariff system of Jordan is based on residential, agricultural, and industrial/commercial purposes to ensure the goal of efficient water use, while at the same time bringing in revenue for infrastructure maintenance. Residential tariffs are progressive by nature, with lower rates applying to basic consumption to help poor households, and rising costs applying to higher usage that may place pressure on bigger families or act as an incentive toward water-saving among wealthier ones. Water is strongly subsidized in agriculture, helping small-scale farmers but simultaneously promoting less efficient use among larger farms. Much higher tariffs are applied to industrial and commercial uses, which more accurately represent the cost of supply and provide a disincentive for inefficient practices. However, these higher costs tend to burden small businesses and affect large enterprises in terms of competitiveness, leading them to invest in water-saving measures.

Water pricing, subsidy, and cost-sharing burdens are important levers for the efficiency of water use within the different economic sectors of Jordan. Water pricing can conserve water when its cost reflects its actual use, particularly in high-consumption sectors such as agriculture and tourism. Jordan has tried to implement a tiered water pricing mechanism, but the low price of water in agriculture has led to overuse and inefficiency. Subsidy reforms along with rigid pricing for high water users could improve allocation and incentivize more efficient irrigation techniques and technologies, such as drip irrigation, to agriculture.

Cost-sharing with the private sector—especially water-intensive industries—could finance projects on sustainable water, including desalination, without depending fully on government resources.

Water Pricing and its Impact on Consumption and Efficiency

Water pricing in Jordan follows a tiered structure; increased consumption shall carry over into higher tariffs, especially for non-residential users and large-scale consumers. In other words, this is a water pricing structure implemented within the framework of the 2023-2040 National Water Strategy, which shall encourage conservation, more so for high-consumption users, reflecting the full cost of the use of the water. In 2024, higher categories of water use have their tariff increased by up to JD 0.28 per cubic meter, targeting household and industrial uses of over 42 cubic meters per month. It is to make an economic incentive for conserving water but with basic access at low rates for small consumers, who benefit from heavy government subsidy support to keep rates very low (Jordan Times, 2023).

The agriculture sector, which is a significant consumer of water in Jordan, has traditionally benefited from low irrigation water prices to support food security and rural livelihoods. However, this low pricing has led to inefficiencies in irrigation practices, where water is often used without regard for conservation. This issue is particularly evident in regions such as the Highlands and the Jordan Valley, where water resources are already under strain. The inefficiencies in water use highlight the need for a shift toward more sustainable agricultural practices that prioritize water conservation.

Recognizing this challenge, the government is exploring the possibility of gradually increasing agricultural water prices to promote more efficient irrigation. The aim is to incentivize farmers to adopt water-saving technologies and better irrigation practices. However, the government is also mindful of the economic challenges this may pose to small-scale farmers and is working to ensure that any increase in water prices does not threaten their economic viability (FAO, 2023).

In addition to agricultural water pricing, Jordan's overall water pricing strategy also involves substantial subsidies to ensure water remains affordable for low-income households. These subsidies, particularly in the lower consumption brackets, cover a significant portion of the cost—up to 82%—helping to achieve social equity by ensuring vulnerable groups have access to affordable water. Despite these subsidies, the financial burden on the water sector is significant, with accumulated debt reaching JD 2.3 billion. To address this, the government plans to phase out subsidies gradually, while still protecting vulnerable populations (FAO, 2023).

Public-private Partnerships (PPPs) have also become vital in funding major water projects, such as the Aqaba-Amman Water Desalination & Conveyance Project (AAWDCO), a bankable project to carry desalinated water from the Red Sea to Amman. This sharing among private sector and international investments enables the dispersal of the financial burden while offering support for Jordan's water infrastructure development toward sustainability (UN Water, 2024).

4.2.3 Economic Costs and Benefits

Jordan's costs of non-cooperation in its transboundary water resources management are strongly linked with social stability, energy, and agriculture. With the increased impact of climate change and water scarcity worsening, Jordan's reliance on transboundary water resources like the Yarmouk River puts its agricultural productivity at risk. Limited irrigation capacity may result in crop reduction, which will impact food costs, and endanger food security and disproportionately lower-income households.

For the energy sector, water scarcity necessitates seeking other alternatives that are expensive and rely on intensive energy use, such as desalination and wastewater treatment. The National Water Carrier project is as mentioned before a project that promotes cooperation between the government, donors, private sector, and society will increase food security and economic prosperity by producing up to 300 million m³ of desalinated water per year (Ministry of Water and Irrigation, 2022). This enables farmers to cultivate formerly parched terrain and guarantee a consistent water supply for households and communities (Haddadin, 2023). However, the National Carrier's dedication to renewable energy is where its real genius rests. The project acknowledges the pressing need to fight climate change and lessen reliance on fossil fuels by utilizing Jordan's plentiful sunshine and wind energy to power the desalination process. Long-term cost reductions are anticipated, and greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution are avoided. Reducing dependency on energy imports the project can provide affordable water and promote social and economic equity (Al Batayneh, 2024).

Furthermore, remarkable social consequences are brought about by non-cooperation. Stressful water conditions worsen the political relations between Jordan and the neighboring states, say Israel, as reflected in the frequent disputes over the share of water allocation and its quality deterioration. For example, the amounts of water provided from sources shared with Israel, such as the Jordan River, would be less in drought years, which has sparked diplomatic disputes in the past (EcoMENA, 2023). Failure to address these issues jointly could undermine social stability, particularly as Jordan's urban and rural communities face an increasingly acute water shortage.

In brief, Jordan's experience epitomizes the dire need for increased transboundary cooperation. Lack of coordination not only incurs economic costs but heightens environmental and social vulnerabilities. Sustainable management strategies that strengthen cooperation with neighbors could reduce these risks by supporting more reliable agricultural productivity, reducing energy expenditure, and fostering regional stability.

4.2.4 Investment in Water Infrastructure

Jordan's water infrastructure and financial landscape are shaped various factors, including governmental budgets allocated for infrastructure projects, subsidies, and strategies for retaining its vital sectors.

- 1- Budget Allocation and Investment Trends in the Jordanian water sector: the Jordanian water sector attracts huge funding to improve its current severe water shortage. The government and its international partners have come up with several financing mechanisms that help address the sector's challenges. One of these mechanisms involves the road map for implementing the National Water Strategy 2023-2040, as well as the funding of the Jordan Water Sector Efficiency Project, which consists of a \$200 million loan from the World Bank with a \$50 million grant. In addition to the sum of all international donors' loans and grants for the improvement of water and sanitation sectors in Jordan. One major project that will elevate the sector is the Aqaba Amman Water Desalination and Conveyance Project, which aims to address water scarcity in Jordan by generating 300 million cubic meters of desalinated drinking water annually, according to the Water Ministry. The project is supported by the European Investment Bank (EIB) and will provide a EUR 200 million loan for the Government of Jordan's contribution to the Aqaba Amman Water Desalination and Conveyance Project (AAWDPC), the first confirmed financing for Jordan's largest-ever water investment project. This project is expected to cost €3 billion and create 4,000 jobs during the construction phase (Gavin, 2023).

- 2- External Investment and Funding Gaps: Jordan to cope with the increased scarcity of its water resources at the national level and from its low water budget from its transboundary water agreements is in great need of external financing support to elevate its water security. As such, the European Investment Bank (EIB) has provided great support; one example is a €70 million loan to reduce water losses and increase irrigation efficiency in the Jordan Valley. This addition to Jordan's water infrastructure certainly is quite considerable but increasing costs due to ambitious projects on desalination and transportation are making it very hard for Jordan to overcome its funding challenges. Other potential approaches to fill the funding gaps with sustainable investment models include public-private partnership models such as the As-Samra wastewater treatment plant (Jordan Times, 2023).

4.3 Social Factors

Jordanian water shortage has drastic social disparities between rural and urban settings. Rural communities, whose economies are dependent on agriculture, are more affected by water shortages because of the dependence of agriculture on water. With increased scarcity of water, there is an increase in crop failure; hence, a reduction in revenue means an increase in the prevalence of poverty. The situation is further exacerbated by a lack of access to efficient irrigation technologies and water-saving practices on the part of rural farmers. Besides, rural communities receive less investment in water infrastructure, hence more frequent water shortages compared to urban areas.

On the other hand, urban cities are likely to enjoy better water provision because governments have invested so much in the infrastructural development of urban water resources, including water distribution systems and wastewater treatment facilities. However, with rapid urban population growth driven by migration and an influx of refugees, the pressure put on urban water is immense. This therefore leads to periodic water supply even in the urban centers, with increasing costs, especially in poor neighborhoods. This increasing gap between the urban and rural setting aggravates inequality because, whereas the residents of urban, especially those in richer neighborhoods enjoy superior access to water services, their rural and poor-neighborhood counterparts suffer squarely due to water scarcity.

4.3.1 Impacts on Communities

Water scarcity and the management of transboundary water resources are critical concerns that deeply impact local communities, especially those in border regions like Jordan. These challenges have far-reaching consequences, not only on livelihoods and public health but also on regional stability, with the potential to fuel both intra-community and cross-border conflicts.

Limited access to safe drinking water water scarcity in Jordan severely restricts access to safe drinking water for many households. United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) reports that while 98% of Jordan's population has access to an improved water source, only 86% are connected to a piped network. This means that a significant portion of the population relies on alternative sources, such as water trucks or bottled water, which are often more expensive and less reliable.

For low-income families, the high cost of purchasing water exacerbates poverty and reduces disposable income for other essential needs like food, healthcare, and education. Additionally, reliance on unregulated water sources increases the risk of contamination, leading to waterborne diseases such as diarrhea and cholera, which disproportionately affect children and vulnerable populations.

Inequitable Water Distribution

The distribution of water in Jordan is highly inequitable, with urban areas generally receiving more reliable access to piped water than rural and underserved communities. In some regions, households receive water through a rationing system, with water supplied to homes only once or twice a week. This forces families to store water in tanks, which can become breeding grounds for bacteria if not properly maintained.

Such disparities in water access deepen social inequalities and create tensions between communities. Vulnerable groups, including refugees and displaced populations, are particularly affected. For example, Syrian refugees living in host communities or camps often face additional challenges in accessing sufficient water, further straining already limited resources.

Impact on Sanitation and Hygiene

Water scarcity also undermines sanitation and hygiene practices in Jordan. Limited water availability makes it difficult for households to maintain proper hygiene, such as regular handwashing, cleaning, and waste disposal. Schools and healthcare facilities in water-scarce areas often lack adequate water supplies, compromising the health and well-being of students and patients.

UNICEF highlights that poor sanitation and hygiene conditions contribute to the spread of infectious diseases, particularly among children. This is especially concerning in refugee camps and informal settlements, where overcrowded living conditions and inadequate WASH infrastructure exacerbate the risks of outbreaks.

4.3.2 Intra-Community and Cross-Border Conflicts Over Water

Water scarcity in Jordan is not only an environmental challenge but also a source of conflict. Within Jordan, communities, particularly in the north, especially in Irbid and Mafraq that have a high population density due to the Syrian refugee influxes since 2013 often experience tensions due to competition over limited water resources. The primary sources of conflict are:

1. **Agricultural vs. Domestic Use:** In northern Jordan, farmers often face frustrations with the perceived inequities in water distribution, as urban areas are prioritized over agricultural needs in areas where agriculture is heavily dependent on groundwater such as Mafraq governorate or fluctuating rainfall such as Irbid. This can lead to localized disputes between urban and rural populations, where agricultural communities argue that their water needs are being neglected in favor of domestic and industrial use.
2. **Pressure from Refugees:** The refugee influx, especially from Syria, has intensified the strain on Jordan's water supply and infrastructure. With many refugees relying on the same water resources as local communities, competition for water has further strained already limited supplies, heightening social tensions.

At the cross-border level, water management conflicts occur between Jordan and the riparian countries. These disputes persist due to fluctuating water availability and non-compliance with the agreed-upon allocations. Key issues include:

1. **1994 Peace Treaty and Joint Water Committee:** the 1994 treaty includes detailed water-sharing provision and established a Joint Water Committee (JWC) to monitor water allocation and cooperation,
2. **Seasonal Flow and Allocation:** Jordan often receives less water than agreed upon, particularly from the Yarmouk River, due to Syria's upstream activities such as groundwater extraction and damming and Israel's regulation of water flows. These discrepancies are most noticeable during drought, amplifying the competition for water.

3. **Water Quality Concerns:** the Jordan River has suffered from high salinity, pollution, and reduced water flow due to the upstream agricultural runoff and untreated wastewater from neighboring countries. The rising salinity and contamination levels threaten the water's usability, particularly in agriculture within the Jordan Valley (UN-ESCWA and BGR 2013).

The resulting tensions in water allocation and quality not only affect the livelihoods of those who depend on these transboundary waters but also have broader implications for regional peace and cooperation. The competition for scarce water resources can weaken social cohesion, particularly in communities already facing economic and social challenges. This dynamic underscores the need for sustainable water management practices and conflict-sensitive policies that can address both local and regional challenges effectively.

4.3.3 *Environmental Impacts*

Jordan's water scarcity is not only a socio-economic but also an environmental problem. The environmental impacts of Jordan's water crisis are generalized and serious. Over-exploitation has reduced major aquifers such as the Amman-Zarqa, Azraq, and Disi aquifers. It has also induced declining water tables, salinization of water supplies, and deterioration of water quality. This unsustainable exploitation of the aquifers jeopardizes the future of Jordan's very water security in the long term.

Over-development and overuse of Jordan's surface water resources by Jordan itself and by other countries upstream have greatly reduced the flow of the Jordan River, as well as that of the Yarmouk River. This diminution in water has contributed significantly to environmental degradation, especially in fragile ecosystems like the Dead Sea, which has witnessed dramatic reductions in water levels over recent decades. This situation affects not only the environment but also Jordan's tourism industry, with its heavy dependence on the Dead Sea's special natural character.

The additional threats of agricultural pollution, discharge of untreated wastewater, and industrial activities exacerbate water scarcity both in groundwater and surface water resources, further diminishing clean water for human consumption, agriculture, and industry, and degrading the ecosystems further.

Climate change multiplies these environmental burdens. Temperature increases decrease in rainfall, and higher frequency of droughts are likely to worsen Jordan's water scarcity during the next few decades through additional stress on already overexploited resources. This will further complicate the country's ability to meet water demand across all sectors and may heighten conflicts over water both domestically within Jordan and regionally with neighboring countries.

Jordan's water shortage crisis brings a complex web of economic, social, and environmental challenges. Taking part in such problems calls for an integrated solution focused on the better use of water and finding innovative ways to deal with the upcoming effects of climate change.

4.3.4 *Public Perception and Advocacy*

Civil society and advocacy groups play a crucial role in raising awareness about water scarcity and transboundary water issues, particularly in regions like Jordan, where water resources are highly stressed. These groups, such as EcoPeace Middle East, have been instrumental in fostering cross-border partnerships between Jordan, Israel, and Palestine to engage in the conservation and management of shared water resources. For example, EcoPeace's "Good Water Neighbors" program has helped facilitate municipal cooperation in addressing shared water challenges and promoting regional peace through environmental stewardship. This initiative demonstrates how civil society can build grassroots support and drive change

by identifying common vulnerabilities and benefits, thereby influencing policy and encouraging sustainable water practices across borders.

The involvement of the public in water policymaking is another emerging trend, as governments and international players increasingly recognize the need for transparency and local input in resource management. Public participation, especially from communities experiencing acute water shortages, ensures that policies are both efficient and fair. This is a core commitment to long-term success, as it fosters trust among stakeholders and ensures that the solutions developed reflect the needs at the grassroots level. For Jordan, public engagement and transparency in water governance are essential not only for ensuring the effectiveness of policies but also for addressing the social and political repercussions of water scarcity. Such involvement can help alleviate conflicts related to water allocation and access, making the process more inclusive and socially acceptable.

However, the influence of civil society in shaping water policies is often limited by challenges such as funding constraints and political restrictions (Klassen, 2020). While organizations like EcoPeace have made progress in promoting water cooperation, their dependence on external funding—often periodic and politicized—highlights the need for consistent international support. Moreover, it underscores the necessity for policy frameworks that enable the continuous and inclusive engagement of civil society in water governance. Such engagement would contribute to building a resilient and adaptable water management system that can respond to changing environmental and political conditions.

The Blue Peace Initiative has further exemplified the importance of public perception and advocacy in water governance by fostering regional cooperation. Through its training programs for journalists, the Blue Peace Initiative aims to reshape public awareness, emphasizing that water is a shared resource rather than a source of conflict. Additionally, the Blue Peace forums, where stakeholders from countries such as Jordan, Iraq, Lebanon, Türkiye, and Syria come together to collaborate on sustainable resource management, help to build a sense of shared responsibility. This participatory approach not only promotes peace but also strengthens cooperation between governments and communities. Moreover, the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus is a recent initiative that takes regional cooperation a step further, emphasizing the interconnectedness of water, energy, food, and ecosystems (Blue Peace ME, 2023; Shareweb, 2019).

5 Challenges and Opportunities

5.1 Challenges

Transboundary water management in Jordan faces multifaceted challenges that hinder effective governance and sustainable use of its limited water resources. These challenges stem from a combination of legal, institutional, social, economic, environmental, and political factors that intersect to create a complex and pressing issue. A lack of enforceable agreements with upstream neighbors, coupled with fragmented institutional frameworks, undermines coordinated action. Limited data sharing among riparian states and inconsistent information management within Jordan further exacerbate inefficiencies. Meanwhile, climate change amplifies water scarcity, exacerbating the strain on fragile ecosystems and increasing competition over shared resources. Political and regional tensions limit opportunities for cooperation, while socio-economic pressures, such as population growth and agricultural demands, stretch resources to their limits. Finally, economic barriers, including outdated pricing policies and insufficient funding, further constrain efforts to improve water management. The following sections delve into each of these challenges, examining their root causes and implications for Jordan's water security and regional stability.

Legal and Institutional Constraints

One of the most pressing challenges in Jordan's transboundary water management is the absence of legally binding and enforceable agreements with its neighboring countries. As Jordan relies heavily on the Yarmouk River and The Jordan River, the lack of strong legal frameworks enables upstream countries to unilaterally exploit these resources, leaving Jordan vulnerable to reduced water availability, unpredictable allocation, and over-extraction. The existing agreements provide mechanisms for cooperation but lack enforcement measures that allow the upstream countries to prioritize their water needs over Jordan's without consequences. These legal gaps usually limit and weaken Jordan's negotiation power and the ability to demand compliance with the agreed-upon allocation. Beyond these external legal challenges, Jordan also faces internal institutional fragmentation, which hampers effective water governance and diplomatic coordination. Some overlapping mandates of key institutions result in inefficiencies, duplication of efforts, and inconsistent policy implementation. One measure issue is the lack of centralized, clearly defined authority to oversee transboundary water negotiations weakens Jordan's diplomatic position. Addressing these legal and institutional constraints requires advanced internal governance structures, clear institutional roles, and advocating for binding and enforceable agreements.

Data and Information Sharing

The lack of real-time and transparent data exchange among riparian countries contributes significantly to the mistrust and inefficiency in managing transboundary water resources. Limited data on water flows, usage, and withdrawals obstructs cooperative efforts and fuels uncertainty. Within Jordan, inconsistencies in data collection, reporting, and analysis exacerbate these challenges, making it difficult to develop comprehensive management strategies or advocate effectively for equitable resource sharing. Without a robust framework for information sharing, both internally and regionally, decision-making remains reactive and fragmented.

Environmental and Climate Change Challenges

Jordan's water scarcity is exacerbated by environmental degradation and the adverse impacts of climate change. Decreasing rainfall, higher evaporation rates, and rising temperatures intensify the depletion of

already scarce water resources. Over-extraction of groundwater, often used to compensate for surface water shortages, leads to declining aquifer levels, salinization, and long-term damage to vital water sources. Ecosystems such as the Dead Sea are severely impacted, underscoring the urgent need for sustainable and integrated water resource management practices. Climate change not only intensifies water scarcity but also heightens competition for resources, further complicating efforts to address transboundary issues. To address these challenges Jordan must adopt a multi-faceted approach that includes sustainable water management that aims at strengthening Climate Adaptation strategies and developing climate resilient infrastructure such as flood management and drought mitigation systems including early warning systems.

Fragmented Regional Cooperation

Despite existing agreements between Jordan and its neighboring countries, the effectiveness of these arrangements is often undermined by political tensions, mistrust, and inconsistent implementation. A lack of a dedicated regional platform for sustained dialogue and conflict resolution limits opportunities for cooperation and coordination. These dynamics foster a fragmented approach to transboundary water management, with riparian countries often acting in isolation rather than collaboratively. This fragmentation prevents the development of holistic strategies that address shared challenges, such as water scarcity, drought management, and ecosystem preservation.

Social Pressures and Economic Challenges

Jordan faces significant social and economic pressures that complicate transboundary water management. Agricultural water use, while contributing minimally to the economy, is often prioritized due to its perceived importance for food security and national resilience. This prioritization can come at the expense of domestic and environmental water needs. Furthermore, the government's limited fiscal capacity restricts investments in advanced water infrastructure and technology, which could strengthen Jordan's negotiating position. Rapid population growth and the influx of refugees place additional demands on Jordan's water resources, intensifying the pressure to secure and manage shared water effectively. These socio-economic challenges create a complex backdrop against which transboundary water management must be navigated.

Several economic challenges contribute to the low efficiency of Jordan's water management system. The outdated pricing policy does not reflect the full economic value of water, notably in agriculture, where the low level of tariffs encourages over-consumption and penalizes the installation of water-saving technologies. This is compounded by the inefficiency of subsidies that distort market incentives, thereby implementing policies for water conservation and use efficiency is difficult to apply. Financial barriers include insufficient funding of infrastructure projects, and putting further limits on water management strategies. Additionally, there are fragmented institutional frameworks where there is a lack of harmonization amongst various stakeholders leading to weak financial management and fractured efforts in water governance. Addressing these economic barriers will be important for enhanced water management and sustainable use of the resources in Jordan. The following explains each barrier and their effects:

- Water prices in Jordan do not reflect the fact that the resource is scarce, consequently leading to the inefficient use of water. The low water tariff for some sectors, notably agriculture, encourages these sectors to consume larger amounts and diminishes incentives for investments in water-

saving technologies. In some areas the lack of enforcement allowed farmers to use water without paying tariffs leading to less economical value of water.

- Water use subsidies, especially in agriculture and other sectors, are another huge source of distortion of good water management policies because these mitigations make it hard to implement policies that would encourage conservation and efficiency. In addition, financial barriers, like the lack of funding, for example, for infrastructure projects radically limit the efficiency of water management strategies.
- Uneven Institutional Frameworks: Economic barriers sometimes arise because of fragmented institutional frameworks for water management in Jordan. There is no harmonization of the activities among stakeholders, which sometimes results in weak financial resource management. Thus, this undermines the entire effort in water management.
- The demand-supply problems in Jordan have made it necessary to construct mega water projects such as dams, desalination, and wastewater facilities, which have become quite vital in augmenting the supply of water towards the attainment of sustainable development. However, such mega projects require sufficient cost-benefit analysis to establish whether the project is viable economically. The financial costs that would be required from infrastructure investment are weighed against potential economic benefits accruable, including increased agricultural productivity and industrial growth. Besides this, public-private partnerships have been increasingly used in managing water resources, even as they advance efficiency and economy in the use of public funds. PPPs can successfully deliver water projects by distributing financial risks and developing cooperation between the public and private sectors. Additionally, investing in water management is generally considered to have long-term economic benefits, not strictly defined by short-run financial returns, but by sustainability and resilience to climate change, with substantial job creation that rejuvenates local economies. Second, through efficient transboundary water management premised on the cooperation of the riparian states, significant economic dividends can be reaped, and in turn, it fosters stability and reduces state conflict. This analysis will take a closer look at these diverse areas of cost-benefit analyses relating to projects and investments in water and will enhance the overall understanding of the implications such projects have on economic development and regional cooperation in Jordan.
- Jordan has a great need for external funds to do its projects. As examples of such projects, there can be mentioned the construction works of the Red-Dead Conveyance project, wastewater treatment plants, etc. External financing as well as external borrowing poses problems to Jordan. These problems are: The risk of external indebtedness, internal and external conditionality and control, dependency. Loans leads to an increase in the public debt of Jordan that limits developing sustainable job sectors with a link to the investment steadily posing the economy to much financial risk for a long time. Political sensitivity surrounds the widely sought loans because they are attached to structural adjustments that will more likely involve governance reforms as well. Overdependence upon political institutions will often tilt the balance between the short-term investments visible in the political markets versus the long-term impact of sustainability initiatives. The excessive dependence on external resources may impede the establishment of self-financing water management systems in Jordan. Besides, changing donor policies and changing geopolitics may jeopardize the availability of funds for essential programs. While internal funding for maintenance is weak, the sustainability of projects remains a pressing issue, particularly since operating costs and maintenance may not be met fully with domestic funding.

5.2 Success Stories

To improve the effectiveness of transboundary water management, it is always beneficial to learn from other success stories. **Table 8** lists different case studies and their success factors to learn from their experiences to improve transboundary water management.

Table 8: Successful Case Studies on Transboundary Water Management

Case Study	Description	Key Success Factors
Indus Waters Treaty (India and Pakistan)	The Indus Waters Treaty, which was concluded between India and Pakistan in 1960, has been regarded as one of the most successful water agreements in history. The treaty was negotiated in 1960 by the World Bank to put an end to the protracted conflict over the Indus River water. It gives jurisdiction over the waters of three eastward rivers (Ravi, Beas and Sutlej) to India and three northwestern rivers Indus, Jhelum and Chenab are catered to Pakistan. The series of water disputes have been surmounted although numerous conflicts and tensions have taken place between the states and a framework for peaceful cooperation within the countries has seemingly emerged even during hostilities. It also created the Permanent Indus Commission, an institution which enables the two countries to communicate regularly and settle disagreements over water management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ There are strong legal rights with respect to the allocations of water ▪ There is a commission established in the treaty for active and regular adjustment of the jurisdictions starting from the first day after the treaty has been signed ▪ There are guidelines and structures in place for facilitating negotiation, mediation and arbitration in efforts towards reaching a successful resolution of the dispute.
Mekong River Commission	In 1995, Cambodia, Laos, Thailand, and Vietnam signed an agreement to create the Mekong River Commission (MRC). This organization's goal is to manage the Mekong River's water resources together. The river plays a key role in the area's farming, fishing, and hydroelectric power. The MRC pushes for Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM): The MRC applies IWRM principles to balance economic growth with environmental protection. This approach plays a key role in a river basin with many different needs. ▪ Stakeholder Engagement: The MRC gets local communities, governments, and NGOs involved in

This approach tries to balance money-making projects with protecting nature and being fair to people. The MRC also helps countries share information, plan together, and work as a team on big projects like dams and watering systems.

how it makes decisions. This helps to make things open and hold people accountable. Data Sharing and Research: The commission helps member countries gather and share data. This leads to a better grasp of how the basin works and allows for smarter choices. Capacity

- Development Programs: The MRC offers training and backs local groups to boost management skills and teamwork across the region.

Orange-Senqu River Commission (ORASECOM)

The Orange-Senqu River runs through four countries in Southern Africa: Lesotho, South Africa, Botswana, and Namibia. In 2000, these nations set up the Orange-Senqu River Commission (ORASECOM) to manage the river basin together and make sure each country gets its fair share of water. ORASECOM works on shared water projects, shares data, and creates plans to handle problems like not having enough water and keeping the environment healthy. It's played a big role in helping countries talk about and agree on water projects like dams and irrigation systems that help all the countries involved.

- Joint Management Framework: ORASECOM has set up a way for countries to make decisions together about how to manage water. This helps the member countries work better with each other. Information Sharing: The group makes it easier for countries to share information and learn from each other. This leads to better teamwork on water issues in the region.
- Integrated Development Projects: ORASECOM pushes for projects that are good for more than one country. These include shared irrigation systems and water structures. Such projects bring countries closer and make them work together more.
- Adaptation Strategies: The group puts a lot of weight on practices that will work for a long time. This helps in dealing with changes in the climate and make sure there will be enough water in the future.

Colorado River Compact (USA and Mexico)

The Colorado River Compact, which was concluded in 1922, shares the waters of the Colorado River among the seven U.S. states (Arizona, California, Colorado, Nevada, New Mexico, Utah, and Wyoming) and ensures that Mexico receives its

- Flexibility in Agreements: The compact allows for amendments to be adaptable with changing conditions.
- Cooperative Conservation Efforts: The United States and Mexico nucleate a number of projects from the

share under subsequent treaties. It is one of the oldest water-sharing agreements, having faced enough issues due to rising demands for water and droughts resulting from climate change. In efforts to cope with these challenges, amendments such as Minute 319 and Minute 323 incorporated flexible rules for water allocation and cooperative conservation between the U.S. and Mexico. In these ways, the two countries have shared the burden of water shortages and jointly taken on investments in water-saving projects.

agreements of Minute 319 and Minute 323 for multiparty cooperative conservation and management of water.

- Stakeholder Involvement: Various stakeholders- indigenous communities and local governments- actively negotiate to ensure broad representation of various interests.
- Crisis Response Mechanisms: In conclusion, the compact has catalyzed a development of set procedures for managing drought or water shortages; hence, this allows for some rapid intervention during crises when both countries could be appealing to manage their water needs.

5.3 Opportunities (Strengths)

Jordan's strengths provide a solid foundation for advancing the effectiveness of transboundary water management. These strengths span policy alignment, technical expertise, innovative solutions, and a track record of regional cooperation.

Policy and Strategic Commitment

Jordan's updated national water strategy presents a significant opportunity to advance regional cooperation and enhance water security. By aligning national water policies with international frameworks, such as the UN Convention on the Law of the Non-Navigational Uses of International Watercourses, Jordan can promote equitable and sustainable allocation of shared water resources. The strategy integrates principles of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), emphasizing advanced data-sharing, joint monitoring, and transparent decision-making processes to strengthen collaboration with riparian neighbors.

Experience in Water Scarcity Management

With one of the lowest per capita water availability rates in the world, Jordan has developed extensive expertise in managing acute water scarcity. Through innovative technologies and policies, the country has successfully implemented water reuse systems, efficient irrigation methods, and advanced water conservation strategies. These practices can serve as models for neighboring countries, fostering collaboration and shared learning in managing limited transboundary water resources.

Advanced Technical Expertise

Jordan has invested significantly in building technical capacities to design, operate, and manage water infrastructure. The country's expertise in converting open water systems to closed ones and addressing challenges such as water hammer issues highlights its leadership in technical problem-solving. These capabilities make Jordan a valuable partner in implementing effective and sustainable transboundary water projects.

Established Regional and International Partnerships

Jordan's strong relationships with international donors and development agencies, including Agence Française de Développement (AFD), Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW), and the European Union (EU), enable it to secure financial and technical support for transboundary water initiatives. These partnerships not only provide resources but also foster knowledge exchange and capacity building. Jordan's active participation in regional forums further strengthens its ability to engage in multilateral discussions and drive collaborative efforts in water governance.

Institutional Frameworks and Governance

Jordan has built robust water governance institutions, such as the Ministry of Water and Irrigation (MWI) the Water Authority of Jordan (WAJ), and the Jordan Valley Authority (JVA) which are instrumental in shaping and implementing transboundary water agreements. These institutions operate within clear regulatory frameworks, ensuring accountability and facilitating the successful execution of shared water management projects.

Innovative Solutions and Technological Advancements

Jordan is at the forefront of adopting innovative solutions for water management, including desalination, wastewater treatment, and water reuse technologies. These advancements provide replicable models for managing shared water resources effectively. Additionally, the use of digital monitoring systems and hydrological modeling enhances data accuracy, supporting evidence-based decision-making in transboundary contexts.

Strong Educational and Research Institutions

Jordan's universities and research centers play a critical role in advancing knowledge and innovation in water resource management. These institutions contribute to capacity building and foster collaboration through joint research initiatives with neighboring countries. By leveraging its academic and research strengths, Jordan can drive scientific approaches to address shared water challenges.

Proven Track Record in Regional Diplomacy

Jordan's history of negotiating water-sharing agreements, such as the water provisions in the Jordan-Israel Peace Treaty, underscores its capability in regional diplomacy. The country's neutral stance and willingness to facilitate dialogue position it as a trusted mediator in resolving transboundary water disputes. Jordan's proven ability to achieve agreements provides a strong basis for future cooperation with its neighbors.

Focus on Climate Adaptation

Recognizing the impacts of climate change on water availability, Jordan has prioritized adaptation measures to enhance resilience. This includes initiatives to address shared climate challenges, particularly those affecting transboundary water resources. Jordan's leadership in promoting climate adaptation

strengthens its credibility as a partner in collaborative regional efforts to ensure sustainable water management.

Advancing Transboundary Collaboration through the WEFE Nexus

Jordan has adopted a comprehensive approach to integrating the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus into its governance and strategic planning. While there is no single standalone legal framework explicitly labeled as "WEFE," the country has embedded WEFE principles into broader policy and legislative frameworks. The National Water Strategy 2023-2040 embodies the WEFE Nexus approach by focusing on integrated resources management for water security and sustainability. The strategy aims to enhance efficiency in the water sector, augmenting water supplies with alternatives, and enhancing national and regional cooperation (NWS2023-2024). In addition, Jordan has taken important steps toward integration the WEFE Nexus approach. Below are some key steps.

- Jordan is developing a comprehensive governance framework to better institutionalize the WEFE Nexus within its ministries and different stakeholders including international donors, academia, research centers, and local NGOs. This includes creating decision support tools and techniques to integrate planning and policy coherence within the respected area of interventions of the Nexus (Water Energy Platform, 2025)
- A WEFE Nexus Hub has been established under the “Establishment and Institutionalization of WEFE Nexus Hub for MENA” project , implemented by the Inter-Islamic Network on Water Resources Development and Management (INWRDAM) and funded by Sida (Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency) as part of the UfM (Union for the Mediterranean) WEFE Program , the Hub aims to promote sustainable development by embedding the WEFE Nexus approach within institutional frameworks and operational practices. The Hub serves as a knowledge management platform that addresses the complex interdependencies between water, energy, food, and ecosystems across MENA (Middle East and North Africa) and SEMED (Southern and Eastern Mediterranean) countries. The Hub acts as a dynamic platform for knowledge dissemination, stakeholder collaboration, informed decision-making, and the identification and implementation of development projects—bridging the gap between ideas ("THINK") and actionable solutions ("DO") (INWRDAM, 2025).
- The water sector in Jordan is highly linked to the country's academia and research centers, such as the Jordan University of Science and Technology, with the Water Diplomacy Center providing research to improve governance in the water sector, as well as the new master program targeting young professionals who will be ready to make the required reform for the emerging WEFE Nexus.
- National Conference on WEFE Nexus is organized every two to three years. The first conference took place in 2019, followed by the second in 2021, and the third in 2024. The aim of the conference is to provide dialogues for policy makers, experts and other stakeholders to exchange knowledge and experiences (UJ, 2024).
- Jordan is also promoting data sharing and monitoring is vital in institutionalizing the WEFE Nexus in Jordan. This will build trust among all sectors involved, transparency, conflict resolution among the sectors, and equity sharing of the resources. This is also seen as a tool to enhance the decision-making process, as the decision will be made based on the data shared from all sectors and prioritization will be made up on real-time data to allow for adaptive measurements.

New Advancements in Syria

The new political situation in Syria offers an opportunity for improving transboundary water management between Jordan and Syria.

6 Areas for Improvement and Suggested Actions

6.1 Areas for Improvement

As presented earlier in this assessment, Jordan's transboundary water management should address the economic and political gaps by enhancing the incentive system, political commitment, regional cooperation, and governance. This will ensure the sustainable and equitable management of shared water resources in a region troubled by political and economic challenges.

Jordan has considerable economic disparities in its water management plans, especially regarding Mega water projects. Projects of desalination and water transfer, such as the Disi and the National Conveyor projects, are extremely expensive. Jordan has poor financing and, more so, projects considered to involve transboundary cooperation. This kind of project, being highly dependent on international loans for its financing, further adds to the financial burden of the country and inhibits it from developing sustainable solutions to water management. Besides, water use efficiency remains extremely low in agriculture, which is an economically extensive user of available water supply. It is exacerbated by limited economic incentives to adopt water-saving technologies or switch to less water-intensive crops, further worsening the already critical shortage of water. The economic gaps between Jordan and its co-riparian neighbors make the situation even more adverse, with negotiating power imbalances. Such inequity makes transboundary water agreements less fair and effective; in turn, it is harder to secure beneficial arrangements for Jordan. Political gaps also weaken Jordan's ability to manage the transboundary water resources. While agreements are at hand, the absence of political will usually undermines the full implementation of those agreements and their enforcement. This lack of determination may be because of the different interests of the participating countries in solving the problem, in combination with the complicated geopolitics of the region. Another big concern is regional instability. Conflicts in neighboring countries make the environment uncertain because of various fluctuations, thereby complicating long-term cooperation in terms of water management. Jordan has limited diplomatic leverage, further constraining its ability to pursue claims in negotiations, especially with upstream countries such as Israel and Syria, who hold the control power. The coordination and governance system are also highly fragmented with many agencies involved in the management of water resources. It results in inefficiencies and conflicting policies. Poor mechanisms for regional cooperation, together with the absence of an overarching institutional framework among the riparian states, impede the effective management of international shared water resources. These economic, political, and governance gaps together constitute serious obstacles to achieving sustainable water management in Jordan. **Table 9** provides a detailed list of the gaps regarding transboundary water management.

Table 9: Detailed List of Gaps in Transboundary Water Management

Area	Issue	Description
Comprehensive Transboundary Water Guideline is Lacking	Absence of Specific Guidelines	Jordan lacks a specific guideline addressing transboundary water management; existing ones are too general to be effectively applied.
	Insufficient Domestic Legal Provisions for the Resolution of Conflicts	There is no strong domestic legislation at the national level that provides transparent mechanisms for conflict resolution over transboundary water resources.

Inadequate Enforcement Mechanisms	Weak Implementation of Treaties	The systems of enforcement for transboundary water agreements are weak, offering little in terms of legal remedies for non-compliance by riparian states.
	Insufficient Penalties for Violations	Current legal frameworks do not provide strong penalties for violations of water agreements, complicating compliance and the protection of Jordan's water rights.
Gaps in Regional Cooperation and Coordination	Insufficient regional institutional frameworks	There is no comprehensive regional institution or framework to facilitate broader cooperation in managing transboundary water resources.
	Fragmented coordination among national agencies	Coordination among Jordanian governmental agencies involved in water management is fragmented, leading to inefficiencies and uneven policy implementation.
Poor Climate-Change Adaptation Integration	Ineffective climate-responsive legislation	Existing structures are not well-developed enough to cope with climate change impacts on transboundary water resources, necessitating laws that integrate climate adaptation.
	Absence of Long-Term Planning	Long-term strategic planning that considers future climate scenarios and their impact on shared resources is almost absent in transboundary water agreements.
Deficient Data Management and Sharing	Inconsistent Data Collection and Sharing	Significant gaps exist in the collection, management, and sharing of water-related data between Jordan and neighboring countries, undermining effective management.
	Absence of Data Sharing Platform	There is no single, integrated platform to ensure systematic data sharing between Jordan and its neighbors, hindering transparency and cooperation.
Inadequate Stakeholder and Public Participation	Inadequate stakeholder participation	Existing frameworks do not adequately involve local communities, NGOs, and other stakeholders in the decision-making process for transboundary water management.
	Public awareness campaigns lack	Public education and awareness campaigns on transboundary water management are lacking, leading to limited societal understanding and support for sustainable practices.
Inadequate Legal Framework for Environmental Protection	Weak environmental safeguards	Existing laws provide insufficient protection for the environmental health of transboundary water bodies, lacking provisions for sustainable management.
	Ecosystem-based management approaches absent	The frameworks miss ecosystem-based approaches that are essential for maintaining the health and viability of shared water systems.
Economic and Financial Gaps	Inadequate Financial Resources for Infrastructure	Financial resources dedicated to the development and maintenance of infrastructure for transboundary water management are inadequate.

	Lack of Economic Instruments	The framework lacks economic instruments like water pricing or tariffs to encourage efficient and sustainable use of transboundary water resources.
Weak Provisions for Addressing Emerging Challenges	Inadequate Provisions for New Technologies	Existing frameworks have weak provisions for addressing the benefits and risks associated with new technologies in transboundary water management.
	Lack of Flexibility in Agreements	Existing transboundary water agreements are rigid and unable to adapt to emerging challenges, such as shifts in water demand or environmental hazards.

6.2 Actions

The major steps towards the development of Jordan's transboundary water management include the creation of an integrated legal framework, regional cooperation, and institutional coordination. It shall further provide for setting up guidelines for transboundary water management in line with international agreements related to the matter under concern, like the UN Watercourses Convention. Besides this, mechanisms for updating bilateral and multilateral agreements with neighboring countries will have to be updated to take into consideration current challenges in climate change impacts. Other provisions include the establishment of joint committees for monitoring and information exchange, which will ensure appropriate communication and conflict resolution, and a central coordinating body that would ensure a harmonized manner of managing shared water resources. Furthermore, the mainstreaming of climate change adaptation in transboundary agreements on water resources and promotion of sustainable use of water. It also entails involving local communities in decision-making processes as well as raising public awareness of the need to adopt appropriate practices that could help in managing water supplies. For addressing the economic and financial barriers, it will be important to secure funding for infrastructure development and put in place effective pricing mechanisms for water that will enhance resource management. Also, Jordan will be in a better position to manage its transboundary waters by earning diplomatic and political support through collaboration with international institutions, including continuous monitoring and evaluation for adoption of policies as appropriate. **Table 10** outlines a detailed list of the actions to be undertaken to improve transboundary water management.

Table 10: Strategies and Actions to Improve Transboundary Water Management

Strategy	Description	Actions
Develop a Comprehensive Framework/Guideline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Develop transboundary guidelines ▪ Harmonization of National and International laws. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Formulate and put into effect specific guidelines on transboundary water that stipulates the rights, responsibilities, and obligations of Jordan concerning the management of shared water resources. ▪ In-line local laws with international water laws and conventions, of which the most important is the UN Watercourses Convention. ▪ Ensure that domestic water policies work in tandem with international

agreements, treaties, and other international regulatory documents to avoid any contradictions that would facilitate the smooth implementation of the different transboundary water agreements.

<p>Strengthen Regional Cooperation Mechanisms</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthen Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements, ▪ Establish Joint Committees on Water Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reopen and update existing water agreements with neighboring countries, to make them relevant to current realities, in particular, the impact of climate change and demographic shift. Consider new agreements where gaps exist. ▪ Set up or strengthen the existing joint committees with neighboring countries to monitor the implementation of transboundary water agreements. These committees shall facilitate communication at regular intervals, data sharing, and dispute resolution.
<p>Improve Institutional Coordination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Creation of a Central Coordinating Body, ▪ Decentralize Some Aspects of Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A central coordinating agency to oversee all aspects of transboundary water management needs to be created, or institutions built and strengthened. This coordinating body shall be empowered to harmonize the actions of the different government agencies towards a uniform approach. ▪ While remaining centralized at the top, certain duties can be distributed to the local bodies, particularly in the areas bordering the protected area, to be more responsive to the local needs and conditions
<p>Climate Change and Sustainability Mainstreaming in Policies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrate the strategies for adaptation to climate change into transboundary water agreements, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrate the strategies for climate change adaptation into agreements of transboundary water resources. This includes planning for variable water flows and increased droughts, among other climate-related impacts. ▪ Encourage the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices and water-saving techniques by offering incentives and

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promotion of Sustainable Water Use Practices 	<p>regulations. This can reduce the pressure on transboundary water resources and make it possible to ensure long-term availability.</p>
Improved Data Sharing and Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Shared Water Information System Development, ▪ Standardize Data Collection Methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establish a regional platform for sharing data on water quality, quantity, and usage by the riparian states. Such a system must be transparent and available to all interested parties if trust and cooperation are to be built. ▪ Standardize methods of data collection and reporting among the neighboring countries, ensuring uniformity and accuracy in the information that will be used for transboundary water management.
Strengthen Enforcement and Compliance Mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enhance Legal Enforcement, ▪ Periodic Review and Revision of Agreements, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Make sure that a legal mechanism for enforcement of transboundary water agreements is institutionalized with clearly spelled-out penalties for non-compliance to the agreements; this would ensure that all parties take agreements seriously, ▪ Establish a formal timeframe and process through which the transboundary water agreement shall be periodically reviewed and updated in response to changing conditions, new scientific information, technology, or any other cause related to variability in the water availability.
Stakeholder Participation and Public Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Engage Local Communities in Decision-Making, ▪ Raise Public Awareness and Promotion of Education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Involve border communities, especially local communities at borders, in planning and management by creating participation opportunities during all stages of the development of transboundary water resources to ensure that policies truly answer to the needs of those most directly involved. ▪ Start campaigns for public awareness among citizens so that they become conscious of the imperative of sustainable use of water and the difficulties of management of transboundary water. This would, in

		<p>turn, help foster a culture of conservation and responsible use of water.</p>
<p>Economic and Financial Barriers to be Addressed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Secure Funding for Water Infrastructure, ▪ Implement Water Pricing Mechanisms, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Commit to the funding required for the basic infrastructure in effective management of transboundary water, including dams, storage facilities, and monitoring systems. Secure funds from international donors, financial institutions, and public-private partnerships. ▪ Introduce or adjust water pricing mechanisms so that the full, true costs of water are reflected, while encouraging better water-use efficiency and shielding vulnerable populations
<p>Build Diplomatic and Political Support</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mobilize International Support, ▪ Water Diplomacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Consult with international institutions—the United Nations, the World Bank, and regional organizations—to secure technical assistance and funding for activities related to transboundary water management, ▪ Engage in continuous dialogue with the neighboring countries, using water as a tool for diplomacy, to build trust and cooperation in the quest for more effective and durable agreements.
<p>Monitor and Evaluate Policy Implementation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Monitoring and Evaluation Systems, ▪ Publicly Report the Progress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Robust monitoring systems must be built as transboundary water policies and agreements are implemented. Regular evaluation will help in the effectiveness assessment and reform of measures. ▪ Monitoring transparency Reports for the implementation, the success stories, challenges, and areas to learn from, shall be publicly published periodically. This shall hold parties at all ends liable for their actions.

While the political dynamics dominate transboundary water management, various other aspects, as identified above, play a huge role in this sector. The most important among them are:

- **Data Collection and Sharing, Data for Decision (D4D):** D4D is critical for transboundary water management as a tool for improving decision-making and cooperation. Reliable data on the flows of water, patterns of use, and its quality ensures that policymakers are better placed to make effective decisions concerning water allocations, use, and conservation. Sharing such data among riparian countries creates trust and transparency—two main ingredients for successful collaboration—by reducing suspicion and promoting a collaborative and cooperative way to approach the shared management of these water resources. Additionally, there is an objective basis for dispute resolution over water use, which encourages in conducting negotiations and arriving at agreements. Continuous data collection and sharing ease compliance with agreements by effectively monitoring water resources and water use, thus tracking the water use to detect over-extraction and adhere to the terms. Up-to-date data supports adaptive management—allowing adjustments in time upon changing water conditions due to climate change. More than that, data is at the core of scientific research and technology innovation; hence, it will facilitate detailed research in technology development for the implementation of innovative solutions in water management. Data from the various sectors will ensure holistic and effective strategies for water management in IWRM.
- **Multi-Stakeholder Dialogues:** Multistakeholder dialogues in TWM bring on board different perspectives: governmental, nongovernmental, civil society, and the private sector. The dialogue also makes the decision-making process participatory, where all interests are taken into consideration. Government participation assures that management is in support of national interests and collates with various governance levels in cooperation. NGOs represent environmental and social justice concerns. Communities provide practical understanding, setting solutions in a specific context; private sector actors bring innovative technologies and investments. These stakeholders can make strategies on water management more holistic, fair, and sustainable and can instill cooperation and trust. Pilot projects have an extremely important role and function in testing innovations and refining them to understand better the feasibility and impact of projects. Successful projects can then be scaled up, serving as models for broader implementation, leading to more resilient and effective water management practices.
- **Institutional Frameworks:** Gaps in institutional frameworks for transboundary water management should be urgently addressed through strengthening legal and policy frameworks using harmonization of water laws in neighboring countries, clearly defining the roles played by the institutions involved. In addition, institutional capacities are required to be built at various levels, involving capacity-building programs and adequate allocation of resources. Promoting multi-level governance through decentralization and encouragement of intergovernmental cooperation can enhance responsiveness and coordination in managing shared water resources. Sharing of data and transparency through data platforms and harmonization of techniques for data collection will enhance trust and lead to informed decision-making. In the prevention of conflicts over water resources, there should be strong mechanisms for the resolution of conflicts through joint bodies on dispute resolution and preventive diplomacy. Finally, the implementation of adaptive management practices will make institutional frameworks more resilient to ensure sustainable and equitable use of transboundary water resources.
- **Regional Cooperation:** The other key element of improved regional cooperation in the management of transboundary water resources are the strengthening of regional institutions to coordinate shared water resources at a regional level. This can be done through the formulation of joint management plans, binding agreements that set up regular communication through institutionalized meetings and shared electronic platforms, encouraging joint data collection,

enhancing transparency through shared databases, and promoting equitable mechanisms for sharing benefits so that countries build trust and have equal representation in the management of such important resources. Moreover, the enhancement of capacity building through regional training programs, technology transfer, and involvement of non-governmental actors—the so-called civil society and private sector—will further infuse the richness of their perspectives into the strategies for water management. Tapping into international aid and becoming a cosigner to global frameworks, like the UN Watercourses Convention, will further bolster such efforts toward more effective, sustainable, and cooperative transboundary water management.

A proposed roadmap is attached as Annex One to this document.

7 Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

Scarce water resources are highly dependent on cross-border agreements, coupled with the complex set of institutional, economic, and social challenges, that have shaped Jordan's political economy in terms of transboundary water management. The National Water Strategy 2023-2040 provides the roadmap to cope with water scarcity. In the process, the set of gaps and misalignments in implementation needs to be worked out to achieve the goals of long-term water sustainability.

Water supply and demand challenges in Jordan rely on water supplies stemming from its boundaries, primarily the Jordan River, the Yarmouk River, and the Disi aquifer. These supplies render Jordan insecure regarding regional conflicts over water sharing, at a time when increased demand emanates from population growth and influxes of refugees. Moreover, the impact of the agreements for sharing water resources, especially with Syria. The concerns remain over long-term water security.

The major Gaps are:

- **Institutional and Governance Weaknesses:** segmentation of water management institutions, coupled with a lack of coordination in core stakeholder functions, hampers good governance of water management. Jordan has undertaken reform measures in the water sector; however, inconsistencies in policy implementation along with incomplete legal frameworks especially in transboundary water management undermine the effectiveness of these measures.
- **Social and Environmental Pressure:** the precarious regime of water shortage in rural areas and among refugees triggers social conflicts and inequality in the supply of water. This has promoted environmental deterioration through over-extraction and pollution of water resources into critical conditions in the country, adding to climate change effects.
- **Policy Gaps and Incoherence:** while Jordan has developed several policies related to water management, there are still gaps to be filled between the national strategies and transboundary agreements. Such as the Peace Treaty 1994 and the agreement over water sharing, but the water disputes with Syria and difficulties in enforcing the agreement regarding the Yarmouk River Basin. Similarly, the Disi agreement with Saudia and the terms of over-extraction issues.

The different water strategies, policies, and laws in Jordan highlighted the need for the following actions to be taken to strengthen water management at the national and regional levels. Nevertheless, Jordan needs to implement these strategies and highlight the following:

- Jordan needs to revise and update the water treaties with neighboring countries by enhancing the diplomatic negotiations to ensure equitable water rights if needed by having an international mediation. These treaties should be updated and reformed to ensure that they are in line with the current needs of Jordan and climate and population realities. In addition, Jordan needs to promote regional cooperation and coordination in terms of good governance by enforcing joint monitoring, data sharing and exchange, and conflict resolution by engaging the UN-led initiatives or the League of Arab States.
- Legal and institutional reform: Jordan should improve the coordination among governmental bodies responsible for the management of water at the national and international levels, such as the Ministry of Water and Irrigation, the Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, and the Ministry of Agriculture. This must include a clear mechanism of water governance from policy making to regulatory frameworks and engagement mechanisms. In addition, including all related ministries in the decision-making over transboundary water management with elaborating on responsibilities and enforcement procedures including incentives and sanctions.
- Economic adaptation and improvement: Jordan should strengthen their capabilities in non-conventional water resources technologies, including the improvement of desalination, wastewater management, and grey-water reuse. The National Water Strategy 2023-2040 has set different measures to improve water-economic value such as the implementation of more desalination projects including the National Conveyer system, but this should be accompanied by measures to expand the wastewater treatment plants and water and wastewater network to be able to manage the additional water supply. Jordan has proven a successful adaptation of PPP through different projects such as the Al Samra Wastewater Treatment plant, Disi Project, and Zara Maeen. So far, most PPPs are dependent on loans from international financing institutes or support from International Donors, Jordan must re-evaluate the lesson learned and engage more local financing institutions in such projects.
- Social and Environmental Adaptation: One of the most important aspects of the social analysis is water inequality with a special focus on marginalized communities. As the water tariff is distributed to take into consideration marginalized communities, but still water delivery is still a huge concern when linked to health aspects and sanitation. Interventions might be to increase the water infrastructure in those areas and provide sanitation services. As mentioned in the discussion, Jordan has issued policies and regulations to adapt to climate change to improve the resilience of the water supply, but still, the water quality deterioration from over-abstraction and illegal discharge of wastewater and industrial products on the sanitation system needs to implement more strict sanctions of violation procedures.
- Improve Policies Alignment and Coherence: The National Water Strategy 2023-2040 action plan should be aligned with the Economic Modernization Vision 2022-2033 action plan and the relevant sector plans in a manner that economic and environmental objectives form an integral part of the formulation of water management policy. This will help identify gaps and overcome challenges. In addition, this will ensure that all actions are aligned toward sustainable water management practices.

As discussed throughout the report, the basis for successful transboundary water management in Jordan is managing its water resources strategically and placing water poverty considerations in all decision-making. Jordan's priority is to fulfill and secure sufficient water needs for more than 11 million people. This has implied focusing on finding alternative water sources at the expense of other critical themes such as governance, IWRM, and investments in transboundary waters. The following presents long-term and short-

term recommendations aimed at enhancing the political and economic management of the available water resources in Jordan.

7.2 Recommendations

To address challenges and capitalize on opportunities in transboundary water management, the following recommendations are proposed. These aim to strengthen regional cooperation, improve resource management, and build resilience in line with the principles of sustainability and equity.

1. Strengthen Economic Incentives

Jordan should implement policies that provide clear economic incentives for water conservation. For example, offering subsidies for water-saving technologies like efficient irrigation systems and imposing penalties for excessive water use can encourage responsible water management practices. These measures can reduce water wastage and optimize resource use, particularly in agriculture, which is the largest consumer of water.

2. Raise Political Commitment

High-level diplomacy, through ministerial meetings and joint monitoring committees, is essential to reinvigorate political commitment to existing transboundary water agreements. Regular dialogues can rebuild trust, address emerging challenges, and reaffirm the importance of equitable water sharing.

3. Innovative Funding Mechanisms

To fund critical water infrastructure projects, Jordan can explore public-private partnerships (PPPs) and international donor support. These mechanisms can unlock financial resources to implement large-scale projects such as shared desalination plants, transboundary pipelines, and renewable energy-driven water systems.

4. Establish a Political Process for Cooperation

A political process should be initiated that binds neighboring nations to cooperate on transboundary water issues. This can be achieved through agreements that highlight mutual benefits, such as improved regional stability, shared economic gains, and enhanced water security.

5. Improve Water Efficiency in Agriculture

Agriculture remains the largest water consumer in Jordan and neighboring states. Introducing drip irrigation systems, coupled with proper pricing mechanisms that reflect the real value of water, can drastically improve water use efficiency. These measures would also help reduce the over-extraction of shared water resources.

6. Establish a Regional Water Fund

A Regional Water Fund can be created with contributions from international donors and riparian states to finance shared water infrastructure projects. This fund can support the development of solutions like regional reservoirs, desalination plants, and wastewater treatment systems, ensuring equitable access to water.

7. Develop a Comprehensive Regional Framework

Jordan should advocate for a comprehensive regional framework for transboundary water management involving all riparian states. This framework should include mechanisms for equitable water sharing, dispute resolution, and joint monitoring. Such a system would provide a foundation for long-term cooperation.

8. Invest in Regional Stability

Broader regional stability is critical for sustained water cooperation. Jordan should support regional initiatives that address political tensions, economic disparities, and security challenges, creating an enabling environment for collaborative water management.

9. Leverage International Platforms

Jordan can engage with international forums like the United Nations and the Global Water Partnership to create alliances and gain support for its transboundary water initiatives. These platforms can amplify Jordan's voice and bring global attention to regional water issues.

10. Establish a Negotiation Unit for Transboundary Water Issues

A dedicated negotiation unit should be created to focus on transboundary water issues. This unit would specialize in preparing negotiation strategies, conducting technical and legal analyses, and ensuring Jordan's interests are represented in discussions with riparian states. Annex Two provides a proposed concept for the negotiation unit.

11. Promote Cross-Sectoral Planning and Coordination

Developing an efficient framework for cross-sectoral planning and coordination is essential for managing interconnected water, energy, and food challenges. This approach can reduce conflicts of interest and foster collaboration across sectors.

12. Create a Shared Vision and Coordinate Tactics

Jordan and its riparian neighbors should work together to establish a shared vision for sustainable water management. This includes identifying common goals, prioritizing joint investment projects, and aligning tactics to achieve long-term success.

8 Iraq's Water Resources

8.1 Supply and Demand

Iraq relies mainly on surface water, generated from the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers that store in the Reservoir Dams (Al-Ansari et al., 2021). Current estimates indicate a significant gap between water supply and demand in Iraq. According to the World Bank Data, the total available water reached around 89.9 billion m³ per year in 2022 (World Bank, 2025)³. However, current consumption for agricultural, industrial, municipal uses, evaporation from reservoirs and marshlands, and environmental flow in the Shatt al-Arab reaches 72.12 billion cubic meters per year.

From a future perspective, the available traditional water resources in Iraq are projected to decline to 55.51 billion cubic meters per year by 2035, indicating a worsening water crisis in the country (Iraqi Forum, 2023). In urban areas, approximately 73% of the population receives some level of water supply, while rural areas experience much lower coverage, ranging from 40% to 45% (IEI, 2018). While domestic use accounts for a large portion of demand, agriculture remains the largest overall consumer of raw water. Looking forward, projections show that water demand will continue to rise sharply. By 2035, the oil industry alone is expected to require 1.773 billion cubic meters of water annually, while the maintenance of the marshlands, critical for ecological and socio-economic stability, requires at least 5.305 billion cubic meters of freshwater each year. Additionally, a minimum flow of 50 cubic meters per second is necessary to prevent saltwater intrusion into the Shatt al-Arab. With a projected population reaching 60 million by 2035, domestic water demand is expected to increase from 4.6 to 6.4 billion cubic meters annually, further widening the gap between available supply and growing demand (IEI, 2018). Demand is induced by different factors as explained below:

- **Population Growth and Urbanization:** In Iraq, population growth was incessant with sustained pressure on water resources. World Bank reports indicated that by 2030, the population would exceed 50 million persons with increased demand for domestic water supply, particularly in urban areas such as Baghdad, Erbil, and Sulaymaniyah.
- **Agricultural Sector:** Agriculture continues to be the largest water user, with over 70% of utilized water by Iraq and the Kurdistan Region (MOWR, 2023). While this highlights the sector's critical reliance on water resources, challenges such as inefficient irrigation practices and the cultivation of water-intensive crops are contributing to an increasing imbalance between water supply and demand. Addressing these issues through improved water management practices and crop selection could help mitigate the strain on available resources.
- **The extraction and refining of oil are highly water-intensive processes,** requiring substantial water resources. In Iraq, oil production consumes approximately 1.5 barrels of water for every barrel of oil produced, placing the country at the higher end of the global average range of 1.3 to 1.5 barrels per barrel of oil (International Energy Agency, 2019). Given the oil sector's pivotal role in Iraq's economy, water scarcity presents a significant threat. According to the Oxford Institute, declining water availability could lead to reduced oil production, which would, in turn, impact revenue generation and economic stability. Projections by the Iraq Energy Institute (2018) indicate that the oil industry's water demand is expected to reach 1.773 billion cubic meters annually by 2035, further underscoring the urgency of addressing this growing challenge.

³ According to Iraqi forum (2023) the available traditional water resources, including inflowing surface water into Iraq, internally generated surface water, and renewable groundwater, amount to 70.86 billion cubic meters per year.

- Poor water quality in southern Iraq significantly affects water demand by reducing the availability of usable water for domestic, agricultural, and industrial purposes. Contamination from untreated sewage, industrial waste, and agricultural runoff, combined with rising salinity due to reduced freshwater flow and saltwater intrusion, makes much of the available water unfit for consumption or irrigation, forcing communities to seek alternative sources. This leads to increased reliance on groundwater, bottled water, and informal water markets, often at higher costs and with greater environmental consequences. In cities like Basra, poor water quality has triggered public health crises, fueling demands for improved infrastructure and services. At the same time, inefficient use and lack of awareness contribute to high per capita consumption, even when water is scarce or unsafe. The deteriorating situation has become a key driver of public protests and social unrest, as citizens demand better governance, accountability, and investment in sustainable water management. Ultimately, declining water quality intensifies competition for limited resources, heightening tensions between provinces, communities, and the state.

8.1.1 Surface Water Resources

The Tigris and Euphrates rivers are Iraq's primary water sources (**Figure 13**). These rivers, along with their tributaries, support drinking water, agriculture, and industrial activities. These rivers originate outside Iraq, with the Euphrates flowing from Türkiye through Syria and the Tigris from Türkiye directly to Iraq. The flow of these rivers has significantly declined due to upstream dams and water extraction in neighboring countries (Al-Ansari, 2019). Additionally, tributaries such as the Diyala River, which originates in Iran, and the Greater Zab and Lesser Zab contribute to Iraq's surface water system, primarily supporting agricultural activities and domestic use.

Figure 13: Tigris-Euphrates River Basin (source: I. E. Issa 2014)

8.1.2 Ground Water Resources

Groundwater accounts for 2-7% of available water resources (Iraq Energy Institute, 2018). Notable karst aquifers, located in the northeast and southern deserts, provide additional water. These aquifers recharge

naturally through precipitation and surface water infiltration, as well as artificially from irrigation. However, uneven hydraulic properties across regions complicate groundwater extraction and monitoring (Fanack Water, 2022). Groundwater is used primarily by rural areas and agriculture where surface water supplies are insufficient. Over-abstraction of groundwater has occurred in some areas, particularly in the Kurdistan Region (MOWR, 2022). The significant groundwater basins are in the western desert, the Jezira region, the Mesopotamian Plain, and the Kurdistan region (FAO, 2021). These basins are used for drinking water supply, irrigation, and some industrial uses. With the recent increase in dependency on groundwater resources, most of these basins are facing a decline in the water table, higher salinity, and pollution, especially in Baghdad and Basra.

8.1.3 Non-Conventional Water Resources

Treated Wastewater

Iraq faces significant challenges in managing its wastewater due to aging infrastructure, population growth, and insufficient investment in water treatment facilities (Al-Madhhachi et al., 2022). Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are often outdated and unable to meet the increasing demand for clean water. The reuse of treated wastewater is limited but holds potential for agricultural irrigation, industrial processes, and groundwater recharge (JCCME, 2013). However, untreated or poorly treated wastewater discharge into rivers and soil poses environmental and health risks. Efforts are being made to upgrade WWTPs and promote policies for sustainable water reuse (Al-Furaiji & Al-Khafaji, 2021).

Water Desalination

Desalination is increasingly seen as a critical solution to address Iraq's freshwater scarcity, particularly in southern regions where salinity levels in rivers like the Tigris and Euphrates are rising (Al-Madhhachi et al., 2022). Current desalination efforts are primarily focused on small-scale projects, such as brackish water treatment for local communities (Iraq Energy Institute, 2018). Large-scale desalination plants remain underdeveloped due to high costs, energy requirements, and technological limitations. Future plans include integrating renewable energy sources (e.g., solar power) to make desalination more sustainable and economically viable (Al-Furaiji & Al-Khafaji, 2021).

8.2 Strategies and Policies

Iraq water management framework is shaped by a set of key policy documents, strategies, and plans. These policies are the baseline for the water crisis management and for improving transboundary water to achieve usage in agriculture, industries, and urban development. The following sections summarize the most important policy documents, brief description and main highlights.

The Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG) is the official executive body governing the semi-autonomous Kurdistan Region, located in northern Iraq. Operating under the federal structure of the Republic of Iraq, the KRG exercises legislative, executive, and judicial authority within its region, as outlined in the Iraqi Constitution of 2005.

The National Water Strategy of Iraq (2015-2035)

The National Water Strategy of Iraq (2015-2035) provides a comprehensive framework for addressing water governance, infrastructure development, and international cooperation over the coming decades. This strategy underscores sustainable water management practices, aiming to reduce unsustainable water use in agriculture, enhance urban water systems, and bridge the growing gap between water supply and demand across the country, including the Kurdistan Region. As an integral part of Iraq, the Kurdistan Region

aligns its water management efforts with the national strategy to ensure coherence and shared progress in addressing water challenges.

Key Highlights of Iraq’s National Water Strategy:

- The strategy outlines a long-term vision for managing Iraq's water resources, addressing both domestic needs and transboundary water issues with upstream countries such as Türkiye, Syria, and Iran.
- It highlights Iraq’s vulnerability to water scarcity due to reduced flows from the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, climate change impacts, and aging water infrastructure.
- The strategy emphasizes the importance of good water governance, efficient irrigation methods, and equitable sharing of water resources with neighboring countries.
- It prioritizes the development of water storage infrastructure and focuses on demand-side management, including raising public awareness about water conservation and promoting sustainable practices.

The Kurdistan Regions’ water strategy complements and aligns with Iraq’s national water strategy. This ensures that the Kurdistan Region contributes to the broader national goals while addressing its unique regional challenges. The water strategy of Kurdistan serves as a roadmap for sustainable water management, emphasizing irrigation efficiency, water conservation, and the construction of dams to enhance water storage capacity. These efforts are in harmony with the national strategy’s focus on sustainability and infrastructure development.

Key highlights:

- The strategy calls for upgrading domestic water supply and treatment systems to ensure safe drinking water for communities, reflecting the national priority of enhancing water infrastructure.
- The strategy stresses the need for public awareness campaigns on water conservation and the development of water recycling programs, especially in urban areas, supporting the national strategy’s focus on demand management and sustainable practices.

Iraq’s Water Resources Governing Laws

Several laws regulate water resources in Iraq and govern their management. Each of these laws plays a critical role in shaping Iraq's water governance framework, addressing issues such as water allocation, pollution control, infrastructure development, and sustainable use. However, enforcement and implementation remain areas for improvement to ensure the effective management of Iraq's water resources. Below are the most important ones:

1. Irrigation Law No. 83 of 2017: This law focuses on improving irrigation systems and managing water distribution for agricultural purposes. It aims to enhance water-use efficiency and reduce wastage in the agricultural sector.
2. Ministry of Water Resources Law No. 50 of 2008: This law establishes the legal framework for water resource management in Iraq. It outlines the responsibilities of the Ministry of Water Resources, including the regulation, operation, and administration of water use by different sectors such as agriculture, industry, and municipal services. It also includes provisions against pollution and unsustainable water use.

3. Coastal Exploitation Law No. 59 of 1987: This law addresses the use and protection of coastal water resources. It regulates activities along Iraq's waterways and ensures sustainable use of these resources.
4. Irrigation Projects Implementation Law No. 138 of 1971 (Amended): This law provides guidelines for the implementation of irrigation projects. It supports the development of infrastructure to improve water distribution for agricultural purposes.
5. Maintenance of Irrigation and Drainage Networks Law No. 12 of 1995 (Inactive): Although this law was designed to ensure the maintenance of irrigation and drainage systems, it has not been effectively implemented due to various challenges. Its objectives include reducing water losses and ensuring the sustainability of water infrastructure.

Iraq's Agriculture Strategy (2015-2025)

Iraq's agricultural strategy is essential for addressing the inefficient use of water in agriculture. It emphasizes the alignment of agricultural production with sustainable water management practices. Also promoting modern irrigation technologies and crop diversity.

- 1- The strategy addresses the critical link between water and agriculture, given that more than 70% of Iraq's water goes to agriculture.
- 2- Emphasizes the need for improvement in farming water-use efficiency through modern irrigation systems while the continuity of water is down-trending due to upstream damming and climate change.

UNESCO's Mesopotamian Marshlands Conservation Strategy (2004)

The rehabilitation of the marshlands in Iraq is part of the UNESCO Marshlands Conservation Strategy relating it to the general national perspective on managing water. It calls for sustainable water utilization and international cooperation as essential elements needed for ecosystem protection. The main highlights include:

- This strategy focuses on the restoration and protection of the Mesopotamian Marshlands, one of UNESCO's World Heritage Sites, which is crucial for Iraq's biodiversity and the protection of water resources.
- Highlights the ecological value of the marshes to local fisheries and to agriculture and eco-tourism.
- Underlines the necessity for sustainable water management of marshlands to be sustained as they depend on the flow from the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. This calls for sufficient international cooperation to be released into the marshlands from upstream sources.

8.2.1 Transboundary Water Agreements

While Iraq heavily depends on transboundary rivers such as the Tigris and Euphrates, the overall number of formal and binding agreements for the sharing of water is negligible. Most of these agreements are either old or partly implemented, while comprehensive treaties providing for the fair and predictable allocation of water from upstream countries like Türkiye, Iran, and Syria are virtually nonexistent. Below is an indicative list of the historical transboundary water agreements and cooperative initiatives that involve Iraq and the Kurdistan Region:

- 1946 Agreement Between Iraq and Türkiye: This was one of the earliest water agreements between Iraq and Türkiye, aiming to regulate the use of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. The agreement outlined that Türkiye is required to notify Iraq of any major construction projects that might affect the flow of these rivers.
- 1987 Protocol Between Türkiye and Syria: This protocol guarantees a minimum flow of 500 cubic meters per second of water from the Euphrates River to Syria. Although Iraq was not a direct party to this agreement, it is indirectly affected due to Syria's position as an intermediary riparian country along the river system.
- 1989 Agreement Between Iraq and Syria: This agreement allocated specific water shares for Iraq and Syria from the Euphrates River. According to the agreement, Iraq is entitled to 58% of the total annual flow of the Euphrates entering Syria from Türkiye, while Syria receives the remaining 42%. This agreement played a significant role in regulating water distribution between the two downstream countries.
- 1975 Algiers Agreement (Iraq-Iran): While primarily focused on resolving border disputes, this agreement included provisions related to shared water resources, particularly concerning the Shatt Al-Arab waterway. It addressed issues of navigation and sovereignty over the waterway but did not establish comprehensive transboundary water management mechanisms.
- The Joint Technical Committee on Tigris and Euphrates (1983): This committee was established to promote cooperation among Iraq, Türkiye, and Syria regarding the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. Its objectives included fostering technical collaboration, facilitating data sharing, and advancing negotiations on equitable water-sharing arrangements.
- Framework Agreement Between Iraq and Türkiye (2024): In 2024, Iraq and Türkiye signed a framework agreement aimed at enhancing cooperation in water resource management. This agreement focuses on improving technical cooperation, joint research, and data sharing. It is important to note that the most recent Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) prior to this framework was signed in 2014 and entered into force in 2021.
- Water Initiatives by the Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG): While informal discussions and cooperative initiatives have been attributed to the KRG in relation to transboundary water management, no official documentation or verified sources are available to confirm these efforts. Therefore, further clarification and evidence are needed to substantiate claims about the KRG's role in such initiatives.
- 1990 Correspondence Between Iraq and Iran (Rafsanjani-Saddam Talks): There is no formal agreement on transboundary water resources between Iraq and Iran following the 1975 Algiers Agreement. However, correspondence between Iranian President Akbar Hashemi Rafsanjani and Iraqi President Saddam Hussein during the period 1990–1991 significantly influenced bilateral discussions regarding the Shatt Al-Arab waterway. These talks shaped the positions of both countries on water-related issues, though they did not result in a binding agreement. Further references and sources are needed to elaborate on this point

9 Stakeholders Mapping and Analysis

9.1 Stakeholders Mapping

Ministry of Water Resources

Before the 2003 change in Iraq, the ministry was known as the Ministry of Irrigation. The ministry was divided into five separate commissions and eleven state-owned companies. This was eventually reduced by the Coalition Provisional Authority to six Directorates according to the Ministry website. According to Law No.50 Of 2008, the establishment of the Ministry of Water Resources (MoWR) in Iraq aims to create the legal and technical framework for the institutionalization of water resources management in the country. The main tasks of the ministry are to plan for the investment in water resources in Iraq; to regulate the utilization of ground and surface water to achieve the perfect use of water resources; to develop water resources; and to determine water sources and uses.

Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)

Responsible for water use in farming through effectively working for efficient irrigation facilities. The promulgating Law No.10 of 2013 included 14 articles divided into 3 sections, aimed at re-establishing the Ministry of Agriculture. The goals of the ministry are to achieve agricultural development by empowering production, rendering services in the field of plant and animal production, and developing the work in the fields of protection, guidance, cooperation, and agricultural training. To achieve these goals its tasks are: to establish, plan and monitor the implementation of agricultural policy; create and develop centers of services in the field of production, both animal and agricultural; manage irrigation systems (both drip or sprinkler); modernize agricultural sector, cooperate with similar structures, in Iraq and abroad; strengthen relationships with other countries to develop local agriculture and propose laws relating to agriculture and its protection.

Ministry of Environment (MoEnv.)

Handles environmental protection, particularly concerning water quality and pollution. The ministry's mandates are to protect and conserve the environment, as well as protect the residents of Iraq from environmental pollutants and environmental risks to human health. Other duties include the development of environmental policies and programs, as well as the creation and enforcement of environmental standards (FAO, FAOLEX, 2018).

Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA)

Has a significant role in managing the transboundary water resources of Iraq—the Tigris and Euphrates rivers—through international diplomacy and negotiations. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA) is necessary for cooperation and securing agreements with upstream countries, principally Türkiye, Syria, and Iran. Their key responsibilities are diplomatic negotiation and international cooperation, conflict resolution, and policy coordination. The MoFA website indicated that one of their tasks is to promote integrated water resources management within Iraq and neighboring countries and leverage international support to Iraq. By effectively managing its role in transboundary water diplomacy, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Iraq can help secure sustainable and equitable water resources for the country, contributing to national stability and development.

- The main ministries involved in water management in the Kurdistan Region are integral parts of Iraq's broader governmental framework, working in alignment with national strategies and

policies. These ministries include: Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources (MAWR): Responsible for water resources management, it encompasses irrigation projects, water distribution for agricultural purposes, and general water resource planning.

- Ministry of Municipalities and Tourism (MoMT): This ministry is concerned with infrastructural and actual provision of water supply and sanitation services in urban areas. Water treatment plants, distribution networks, and wastewater treatment facilities are managed by it.
- Ministry of Environment (MoEnv.): The Ministry of Environment is the body responsible for protection and conservation of water resources. It provides guidelines and policies meant to avoid water pollution and promote its sustainable use.

These ministries collaborate in the management of regional water resources involving issues of water supplies, quality, infrastructure development, and environmental protection. In addition to the aforementioned ministries, there are several directorates operating across Iraq, including the Kurdistan Region, that play a significant role in water management. These include:

- General Directorate of Water GDW: GDW is responsible for managing and distributing water all over in Iraq. Besides, it coordinates the functioning of water treatment plants with distribution networks to meet the standards of water quality.
- General Directorate of Sewerage GDS: This directorate is responsible for treating wastewater and providing sewerage services all over Iraq.
- Directorate of Water and Sewage DWS: The DWS belongs to the Ministry of Municipalities and Tourism (MOMT) in the Kurdistan Regional Government. Responsible for water supply, treatment, distribution, and management of wastewater in the Kurdistan Region.
- Erbil Water Directorate: This is the directorate dealing explicitly with the capital of the Kurdistan Region, Erbil, and managing the local water infrastructures and services.
- Agribusiness and Industry: Agribusiness and industry are two of the biggest water users in Kurdistan and, at the same time, two sectors that can regulate considerable improvements regarding water use efficiency and sustainability. The sectors can reduce their demands on water through the adoption of modern practices and technologies, easing the pressure on the transboundary water resources for regional stability. Their work is so vital to the sustainable development of Kurdistan and, of course, to the broader management of shared water resources.

International Financing Institutes

These include financing institutes that contribute to the construction of big national projects. These include World Bank, Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW), etc. These institutes play a vital role in supporting Iraq's efforts to combat its worsening water crisis by providing the necessary financial and technical backing for large-scale infrastructure projects. Through their support, they help rehabilitate critical infrastructure such as dams, irrigation networks, and water treatment plants, which are essential for ensuring reliable access to clean water. They also fund climate adaptation initiatives designed to strengthen resilience against droughts, floods, and other impacts of environmental change. In addition, these institutions assist in building the capacity of national and local institutions responsible for water governance, supporting reforms that enhance transparency and efficiency.

International Donors

These include international agencies that provides funds to Iraq to improve its water management through technical assistance, grants, etc. These include, United States Agency for International Development

(USAID), European Union (EU), Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), etc. However, it is important to recognize the central and leading role of Iraqi governmental entities, particularly the Ministry of Water Resources, in planning, managing, and executing strategic water projects. The ministry has not merely been a recipient of international support but has also spearheaded significant efforts to develop water infrastructure, enhance resource efficiency, combat desertification, and adapt to climate change impacts. Additionally, the ministry has played an active and crucial role in negotiating Iraq's rights to the shared waters of the Tigris and Euphrates basins.

United Nations Organizations

The United Nations has made a significant contribution to water management in the country, Iraq, and the Kurdistan Region as a whole. It supports capacity building through the training of local authorities on water management and institutional strengthening. UNDP, for example, finances and executes infrastructure works on water supply and sanitation systems and provides technical assistance for sustainable practices. It promotes IWRM and climate change adaptation strategies. The UN organization is highly engaged in raising public awareness, enforcement of community involvement, and assisting in the formulation of policies and responses to emergencies. On the other hand, improving water security, enhancing resilience to climate change, and making sure that water is managed equitably are some of the key comprehensive approaches the UN has undertaken. Some of the most important projects are Emergency Water Supply 2010, Wastewater Treatment Project 2017, and Transboundary Water Cooperation since early 2000.

Entities working in the sector (water, transboundary, water management)

There are several national and international entities working on water management, transboundary water management, irrigation efficiency, climate change adaptation like Blue Peace Middle East, Mercy Corps, ECO Consult, etc. These entities implement development projects that contribute directly/ indirectly to water management.

Other Entities

Many NGOs have been working in Iraq towards improving water management. Some of these organizations are the International Committee of Red Cross (ICRC), UNICEF, Oxfam, World Food Program (WFP), The Asia Foundation, Global Communities, Action Against Hunger (ACF), Mercy Corps and others. Those NGOs work towards meeting humanitarian, health service, and educational needs within Iraq, in addition to environmental protection within Iraq including the Kurdistan Region of Iraq. Their efforts are in place vital to alleviate the conflicts' effects, help the displaced, and bring sustainable development.

Academia and Research Institutes

The role of academia and research institutions in advancing transboundary water management in Iraq and Kurdistan is significant, as they provide much-needed scientific data for decision-making. This means that they are vital drivers of innovative solutions in water management, irrigation technology, and waste management. Additionally, they are centrally important in educating future generations on water security and IWRM. An example is the "Al Nahrein Center for Strategic Studies". The center provides the necessary studies and research for water management and is also a member of the negotiating delegation with neighboring countries regarding Iraq's share of transboundary waters.

9.2 Power- Interest Analysis

In the context of transboundary water management in Iraq, various stakeholders play crucial roles, each with differing levels of influence and interest (**Figure 14**). These stakeholders are pivotal in shaping water policies and managing resources at both national and regional levels. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs also holds significant sway due to its role in international negotiations and agreements. Riparian countries sharing transboundary water resources with Iraq have a substantial impact on its water availability, as they control the upstream flow of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. Türkiye and Iran, in particular, have constructed numerous dams on these rivers, significantly reducing the volume of water flowing into Iraq. This has not only diminished water supply but also exacerbated water quality issues, with salinity being a major concern. Additionally, Syria affects Iraq's water availability through its own dam projects and water extraction activities, further compounding the challenges faced by Iraq in managing its shared water resources. International organizations such as the World Bank, United Nations organizations, USAID, the European Union, and the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) provide essential funding, technical assistance, and policy guidance, thereby exerting moderate influence on water resource management in Iraq.

Governmental bodies, including the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Environment in both Iraq and the Kurdistan Regional Government, are involved in implementing policies and managing specific aspects of water resources. While their influence is less pronounced, they maintain a moderate level of interest in ensuring sustainable water management practices.

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) such as Save the Tigris Campaign, Water Keepers Iraq, and other international NGOs (ICRC, UNICEF, Oxfam, Mercy Corps) play a vital role in advocacy, community engagement, and on-the-ground project implementation. These organizations demonstrate strong commitment to water resource management and conservation despite their limited influence over policy decisions.

Local entities, including farmers, agricultural associations, tribal leaders, traditional authorities, and local governments, are directly affected by water policies. They are essential for grassroots-level implementation and compliance with water management practices.

Academia and research institutes, along with strategic centers like the Al Nahrein Center for Strategic Studies, contribute to transboundary water management through research, policy analysis, and strategic recommendations. These institutions play a supportive role in shaping evidence-based policies and fostering informed decision-making.

Figure 14: Stakeholders' Management Strategies

9.3 Stakeholders' Value Map

As shown in **Figure 15** many stakeholders have direct and indirect influences because their goals and values are also in the national interest. The more powerful the stakeholder the more likely they are to be towards the center since they can influence the government to make certain decisions and implement international laws and policies in the region. The diagram indicates that MWR, MoFA, MoEnv., and several other government-associated organizations are core stakeholders. Their interest is determined by their political role and Iraqi and Kurdistan laws and legislation. However, legal entities in Iraq, such as the Higher Court and Supreme Court, are not considered core stakeholders in the power-interest matrix. Despite this, they influence various entities by acting as references for protecting Iraq's interests and laws. This, in turn, directly impacts the decision-making process, as well as the interpretation and enforcement of existing water laws to ensure compliance with legal standards. The Ministry of Environment has a central role with direct responsibilities related to transboundary water management. Some of the transboundary water projects in Iraq have been greatly influenced by decisions from MoEnv. as the water quality and population health are part of their new mandate. The World Bank and UN organizations mainly UNDP belong to the category of direct influence, as they influence governmental decisions by providing finance, expert advice, and policy advice that influences many of the activities and policies put into action by governments affect international organizations often impact transboundary water management indirectly, contributing to the enhancement of water resource management and capacity development at the national level. The support of these organizations consequently eases up the processes and even alters government priorities. The government, however, can negotiate with these organizations to tune their central activities closer to national needs. Academia and research centers fall under the category of indirect influence. These are data-collecting, education-providing, and awareness-spreading centers of scientific research, which influence the decision-making process indirectly. The influence of public organizations, NGOs, and the local community in managing transboundary waters is normally indirect, although this may differ depending on several factors. Their impact also depends on their awareness of Iraq's water issues and political and private interests. In the case of Iraq and the Kurdistan Region, this dynamic is also entangled with the socio-political infrastructure inherent to the region. Some are ruled by traditional tribal systems, and others are ruled by more traditional Arabic laws, which often creates a mixture of regulatory environments that inhibit unified management efforts for water.

Figure 15: Iraq Stakeholders Value Map

10 Political Economy Analysis

10.1 Political Factors Analysis

10.1.1 Geopolitical Relations and Transboundary Water Negotiations

The Tigris and Euphrates River Basin Negotiations with Türkiye

Transboundary water management is a critical issue for Iraq due to its heavy reliance on the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, which are governed by upstream countries such as Türkiye, Syria, and Iran. Regional cooperation is essential for managing these shared water resources, but geopolitical tensions, weak enforcement mechanisms, and inconsistent diplomatic efforts have hindered progress. Below are key case studies and frameworks addressing Iraq's transboundary water challenges.

The Southeastern Anatolia Project (GAP) and Its Impact on Iraq

Türkiye's Southeastern Anatolia Project (GAP), launched in the 1970s, is a large-scale initiative that includes the construction of numerous dams and irrigation systems in the upper basins of the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. The project consists of 22 major dams, including four primary and ten secondary dams on the Euphrates River, as well as eight main dams on the Tigris River. Collectively, these reservoirs have a storage capacity of approximately 100 billion cubic meters—nearly three times the combined storage capacity of dams in Iraq and Syria. Upon completion, Türkiye will control around 80% of the Euphrates River's waters.

Before the GAP project, the annual flow of the Euphrates River was approximately 31.83 billion cubic meters. However, due to the construction of dams and water diversion systems, the flow has decreased to about 23 billion cubic meters, with projections suggesting it may drop further to 15 billion cubic meters in the future. This reduction has significantly impacted downstream countries like Syria and Iraq. For example, Syria's water storage from the Euphrates has been reduced, leaving Iraq with only about 8 billion cubic meters annually—far below its estimated need of 13 billion cubic meters.

The altered hydrological dynamics have had severe consequences for Iraq, particularly in agriculture. The irrigated agricultural area in the Euphrates basin has shrunk from approximately 650,000 hectares to just 240,000 hectares due to reduced water availability. Rising salinity levels and soil degradation have further exacerbated the situation, transforming once-productive regions into barren land.

The Atatürk Dam and Its Effects

The Atatürk Dam, a cornerstone of the GAP project, has had profound environmental, economic, and social impacts on downstream countries, especially Iraq. By regulating the Euphrates River, the dam has drastically reduced water flow into Iraq, damaging agriculture, ecosystems, and energy production. These changes have contributed to widespread crop failures, increased soil salinization, and the spread of crop diseases, severely affecting livelihoods in Iraq's agricultural regions.

The Algiers Agreement and Iraq-Iran Water Management

Iraq and Iran share several rivers, including the Karkheh and Karun, which are vital for eastern Iraq and the Mesopotamian Marshes in the south. Over the years, Iran has constructed multiple dams and diverted water from these rivers for domestic use, significantly reducing inflows to Iraq.

The 1975 Algiers Agreement, while primarily focused on border demarcation, included provisions for cooperation over shared water resources. However, political and military conflicts between Iraq and Iran in subsequent decades undermined the agreement. Iran's construction of dams on the Karun and Karkheh rivers has severely diminished water flows to Iraq, contributing to the degradation of the Mesopotamian Marshes. Diplomatic relations remain complex, with Iran prioritizing its domestic needs over regional cooperation.

Due to the absence of a binding legal framework or joint mechanism, Iraq often faces unilateral water management decisions by Iran, exacerbating its water scarcity challenges. Addressing this issue requires a robust legal framework and sustained diplomatic engagement to ensure equitable water-sharing.

The Joint Technical Committee (JTC) on Transboundary Water Management

Established in the early 1980s, the Joint Technical Committee (JTC) provided a platform for Iraq, Türkiye, and Syria to discuss shared water resources, particularly the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. Initially, the JTC focused on gathering data and fostering technical collaboration to build trust and lay the groundwork for future agreements.

However, political tensions and conflicting national priorities have limited the JTC's effectiveness. Türkiye's GAP project, in particular, has heightened tensions, as Iraq and Syria view reduced water flows as a threat to their national water security. In recent years, little progress has been made toward formalizing water-sharing agreements or establishing legally binding frameworks. Without enforcement mechanisms, multilateral platforms like the JTC remain ineffective.

History with Syria

In 2002, Iraq and Syria reached an agreement on water-sharing, but Syria failed to adhere to its commitments. Instead, Syria initiated irrigation projects on the Tigris River, diverting water for agricultural use. One notable project, "The Great Tigris Project," involved constructing a pumping station to transfer water from the Tigris River to the Ain Diwar canal at a flow rate of 38 cubic meters per second. A 25-kilometer canal was built to irrigate an area of 15,400 hectares, with water pumped into the Al-Maliki Dam

at a rate of 45 cubic meters per second. From there, the Al-Rumaylah Canal branches off, spanning 37 kilometers and flowing into the Jawadiyah Dam.

These actions have negatively impacted areas such as Al-Jawadiyah, Al-Yarubiyah, and the southern part of the Kertchouk plateau. In 2011, Iraq proposed a new agreement to replace the existing framework, but discussions ended without resolution.

History with Iran

Iraq and Iran have a long history of disputes over shared water resources. Iran's upstream dam construction and diversion of tributaries like the Karun and Karkheh rivers have worsened Iraq's water scarcity, leading to economic strain and social unrest in agricultural regions. Iran justifies its actions by citing its own water shortages and energy needs, often prioritizing internal development over regional cooperation.

While Iraq has pursued diplomatic approaches, emphasizing dialogue and proposing joint technical committees to monitor river flows, progress remains limited. Mistrust, competing national priorities, and structural barriers continue to impede comprehensive solutions. External factors, such as international sanctions on Iran, further complicate collaborative efforts. Recent discussions highlight the need for integrated water resource management (IWRM) approaches, but implementation remains challenging without stronger commitment from both sides.

10.1.2 Iraq's Commitment towards Water Diplomacy and Cooperation

In 2023, Iraq demonstrated a significant commitment to water diplomacy and cooperation by officially joining the Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (known as the UN Water Convention). This step aims to enhance transboundary water management, contributing to sustainable development, regional stability, and peace. Iraq's accession to the convention reflects its broader strategy to address ongoing challenges in managing shared water resources, particularly the Tigris and Euphrates rivers, which are vital to the country's agricultural, economic, and domestic needs. The move underscores Iraq's intent to improve water governance, advocate for equitable water-sharing arrangements, and foster greater cooperation with upstream neighbors, including Türkiye and Iran, both of which exert considerable control over these rivers.

Iraq's decision to join the convention was driven by the escalating water scarcity issues exacerbated by upstream water management projects, such as Türkiye's Southeastern Anatolia Project (GAP) and Iran's water diversion schemes. The GAP project, in particular, has been a source of tension between Iraq and Türkiye, as it significantly reduces the flow of the Euphrates and Tigris rivers into Iraq. By adhering to the convention, Iraq seeks to leverage international legal frameworks to advocate for fairer water distribution and ensure that upstream countries adhere to principles of equity and cooperation.

It is important to highlight that Iraq has undertaken significant coordination efforts between the federal government and the Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG) to address shared water challenges. Joint committees, operational coordination rooms, and technical agreements have been established to facilitate collaboration on water management. These efforts reflect a commitment to overcoming institutional fragmentation and fostering unified approaches to water governance, despite ongoing challenges such as limited resources, political tensions, and varying priorities between the central government and the KRG.

Furthermore, successive Iraqi governments, including the Ministry of Water Resources, have actively engaged in negotiations to secure equitable water-sharing agreements for the Tigris and Euphrates basins. Iraq has signed memoranda of understanding (MoUs) with Türkiye and Iran and participated in international forums to advocate for its rightful share of transboundary water resources. These diplomatic

efforts demonstrate Iraq's proactive stance in addressing water scarcity and ensuring sustainable resource management, even in the face of geopolitical complexities and upstream development projects.

In addition to international and intergovernmental efforts, Iraq has worked on improving domestic water management practices. This includes enhancing infrastructure for water storage, distribution, and conservation, as well as implementing policies that promote sustainable agricultural practices and water-efficient technologies (Al-Ansari & Knutsson, 2020). These combined efforts aim to strengthen Iraq's capacity to manage its water resources effectively while addressing the pressing challenges posed by climate change, population growth, and upstream water management decisions.

10.1.3 Political Landscape and Power Dynamics

The political landscape surrounding Iraq's water resources is shaped by a combination of local dynamics, regional influences, and international funding and donor activities. These elements collectively impact Iraq's water diplomacy and its efforts to secure a fair share of transboundary water resources from the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. Below, the key factors influencing Iraq's political power dynamics are categorized into local, regional, and international spheres:

Local Dynamics

The local power dynamics can sometimes conflict with the broader national agenda, complicating Iraq's water management strategies (Ollis, 2016). The central government's control over water resources, as well as its ability to implement water-related policies, is often undermined by the challenges of governance in areas with competing political interests. These issues are particularly relevant in southern Iraq, where water scarcity is more pronounced due to reduced river flows. As such, local power structures and the influence of political elites in these regions contribute significantly to Iraq's approach to water diplomacy.

Both the Tigris and Euphrates rivers flow through the Kurdistan Region before reaching southern Iraq, giving the KRI strategic leverage over upstream water flows. The KRG has pursued independent dam-building projects, such as the Dukan and Darbandikhan dams, which Baghdad views as unilateral actions undermining national water security. Conversely, the KRG accuses Baghdad of neglecting its water needs while prioritizing downstream provinces.

Regional Dynamics

Iraq's political relationships with neighboring countries—particularly Türkiye and Syria—are central to the regional dynamics of water diplomacy. The Tigris and Euphrates rivers originate in Türkiye and Syria, and both upstream countries hold significant influence over the water flow that reaches Iraq. The regional power dynamics are therefore driven by Iraq's efforts to negotiate equitable water-sharing agreements with Türkiye and Syria, both of which have significant control over the headwaters of the rivers.

Despite Iraq's reliance on international legal frameworks such as the UN Convention, the lack of binding agreements with upstream countries like Türkiye has rendered these frameworks less effective. Türkiye's refusal to join the UN Watercourses Convention has posed challenges for Iraq in its quest for equitable water rights (United Nations, 1997). Political tensions, regional security concerns, and competing interests over water resources have often resulted in stalled negotiations, further complicating Iraq's diplomatic efforts.

The regional political context is also influenced by broader geopolitical factors, including the role of external powers and the shifting alliances in the Middle East. These regional dynamics can either support

or undermine Iraq's water diplomacy, depending on the political stances taken by neighboring states and international actors involved in the region.

International Funds and Donors

International funds and donors have played a critical role in supporting Iraq's water management initiatives, both in terms of technical support and financial resources. The United Nations, World Bank, and various regional development agencies have provided funding for water-related projects in Iraq. These donors have emphasized the importance of sustainable water management, environmental conservation, and equitable water-sharing among countries in the Tigris-Euphrates basin.

Through such partnerships, Iraq hopes to strengthen its water governance capacity, although the effectiveness of these efforts will depend on the ability of international donors to facilitate meaningful cooperation among regional stakeholders.

10.2 Economic Factors

Several areas in Iraq and KRG lack adequate economic considerations in water management. These gaps have led to inefficient water use, reduced productivity, and increased vulnerability to water crises.

10.2.1 Water Pricing Mechanism, Subsidy System, and their Implications

In Iraq water has frequently been regarded as a public asset rather than a commercial commodity. However, this approach has led to inefficiencies in water resource management, economic sustainability, and equitable access. The water tariff structure in Iraq and the Kurdistan Region is complex, often characterized by inefficiencies that hinder effective resource management. While water tariffs are designed to recover the costs of water supply, infrastructure maintenance, and service provision, low tariff rates and subsidies have created significant challenges. Below is an analysis of the current water tariff regime and its implications, taking into account ongoing efforts by the Ministry of Water Resources to address these issues. The present Water Tariff Regime is explained below:

- **Subsidized Tariffs/ Low Income Houses:** The water tariff is highly subsidized by the government both in the country as a whole and internally in the Kurdistan Region. The approach aims to keep water at an affordable price for poor households. These subsidies cover a large share of the operational and capital costs, placing fiscal burdens on public budgets and decreasing financial resources that could be spent on investment in water infrastructure and services. To address this, the Ministry of Water Resources has initiated gradual reforms, including the reactivation of the Council of Ministers' decision to enforce the Law on Agricultural Water Fees. This step represents a significant effort to promote responsible water use and enhance the sustainability of water resources in Iraq.
- **Flat rate pricing/ Agriculture and Industries:** Water is charged on a flat-rate system in many regions that are not equipped with metering systems or irregular service delivery. Whereby, consumers pay a fixed fee irrespective of actual consumption. This sort of pricing may result in lower efficiency and over-consumption in certain industries, like agriculture. In areas equipped with water meters, consumption-based billing is applied, ensuring greater fairness and encouraging efficient water use. The government is actively working to modernize water tariff policies to improve resource management and ensure equitable water distribution among different consumer groups.
- **Limited Metering and Usage-Based Pricing/ High consumption users such as big industries and Wealthy households:** The lack of metering systems, which should have enabled more accurate and usage-based billing, is one of the issues in Iraq and Kurdistan. Without meters, charging consumers

based on actual consumption becomes difficult, which exacerbates inefficiency in water use and further complicates the progress toward more progressive pricing models. Despite these challenges, the government is prioritizing the installation of water meters and improving monitoring systems as part of its broader strategy to enhance water management.

- **Agricultural Water Use:** Agriculture is usually subsidized by lower water tariffs in both Iraq and Kurdistan. Subsidized rates related to agricultural water use do not correspond to the real cost of water, treatment, and distribution. While these subsidies aim to ensure food security and stabilize the agricultural sector—a cornerstone of the national economy and a major source of employment—they can inadvertently encourage inefficient water use and reduce the incentive for adopting water-saving technologies. Globally and within Iraq, food security remains a priority, underscoring the need to balance subsidies with measures that promote sustainable water management and long-term agricultural resilience, stabilize the agricultural sector, which serves as a cornerstone of the national economy and a major source of employment.
- **Revenue Shortfalls:** Low tariffs, coupled with limited cost recovery in the water sector, have resulted in revenue shortfalls, thus undermining the capacity of both local governments and utilities to maintain and extend the water infrastructure. This results in deteriorating water supply system disruptions and poor water quality across many regions. To address these challenges, the government is implementing measures to improve revenue generation, including the gradual introduction of usage-based tariffs and targeted subsidies for vulnerable populations. These efforts aim to strike a balance between affordability and financial sustainability, ensuring adequate funding for infrastructure maintenance and development. Additionally, partnerships with international financial institutions are being explored to support large-scale investments in modernizing water infrastructure, particularly in underserved rural areas. The Ministry of Water Resources emphasizes its ongoing commitment to improving water infrastructure across Iraq. For example, significant projects have been launched to secure regular water releases for critical ecosystems like the Mesopotamian Marshes, ensuring their ecological, economic, and social sustainability. These initiatives demonstrate the government's dedication to addressing water scarcity and promoting equitable access to resources.
- **Water Scarcity and Overuse:** The non-availability of a progressive, usage-based tariff structure has caused water overuse. This is important in the context of emerging water scarcity, which has been further accentuated by climate change, upstream activities, and inefficient water management practices.

The Ministry of Water Resources is actively working to implement tiered pricing structures, enhance metering systems, and improve the monitoring of water consumption to promote responsible water use. Alongside these efforts, public awareness campaigns and targeted support for water-efficient agricultural practices are being prioritized to address water scarcity and ensure equitable access to this essential resource.

10.2.2 Economic Impacts

Over the years, the economic landscape of Iraq and the Kurdistan Region has been closely shaped by water scarcity, and the imbalance between supply and demand emerging as a critical detriment of the economic stability and growth. In recent years, both regions have faced significant challenges in aligning supply with growing demand across all sectors. These imbalances have fomented inflationary pressures that reduce industrial production levels and further increase the economic gap between regions. This imbalance between demand and supply contributed to the rise in the cost of living in less competitive local industries.

The heavy reliance on imported supplies to meet domestic requirements has worsened the economic vulnerabilities, making it susceptible to fluctuations in the external markets and geopolitical tensions. In such a context, addressing these imbalances becomes rather vital for sustainable economic growth and ensuring stability in the long run.

Based on the “Land Between the Rivers” report of the World Bank 2017 the impact of the demand-supply over the economic landscape of Iraq and Kurdistan is defined as follows:

Rural Livelihoods

Iraq and KRG are facing serious rural-urban migration due to the impact of water scarcity on the agricultural sector. Iraq and KRG depend on Agriculture as a backbone for rural employment. The water scarcity impact on agriculture has pushed the rural population to migrate to cities which increased the pressure on urban water systems and contributed to the increase of unemployment rates.

Figure 16 illustrates the decline in agricultural employment in Iraq, including the Kurdistan region, the downward trend reflects the challenges in sustaining agriculture due to water scarcity, inefficient irrigation systems, and climate change.

Figure 16: Employment in agriculture in Iraq, including Kurdistan Region of Iraq, 2000–2017 (% of total employment) (Source: Jongerden et al., 2019)

Agricultural Productivity and Food Security

The imbalance between supply and demand in the agricultural sector has reduced agricultural productivity. This forced Iraq and KRG to rely on food imports, which strains its budget. According to the World Food Program (WFP), approximately 30% of Iraq’s food is now imported, leading to higher inflation and increased food insecurity.

Public Health and Water Quality

Water scarcity and poor quality have contributed to public health challenges. For example, poor water management has led to contamination and the spread of waterborne diseases. This is significantly linked to economic costs related to health care and loss of productivity (WHO,2020).

Decline in Freshwater Fisheries

Historically, freshwater fish production in Iraq, including the Kurdistan Region, has depended on rivers, lakes, and marshes that have fallen under the threat of the current water crisis. As shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** fisheries in Iraq grew steadily from 2008 to 2014 due to aquaculture expansion and private sector investment, but declined from 2014 to 2018 because of water shortages, pollution, rising salinity, and security-related infrastructure damage.

Figure 17: Total fisheries production (tons) in Iraq between 2008-2018 (World Bank, 2020)

11 Challenges and Opportunities

11.1 Challenges

Geopolitical Tensions

One of the primary challenges is the geopolitical tension among Iraq, Syria, and Türkiye regarding water rights. Türkiye's Southeastern Anatolia Project (GAP), which includes a series of dams on the Euphrates and Tigris, significantly impacts Iraq's water supply. Türkiye's control over the headwaters of these rivers has reduced the flow of water into Iraq, especially during periods of drought. Iraq has raised concerns over the unilateral construction of dams by Türkiye, which affects its water security (Al-Ansari et al., 2014), and has also taken significant steps to address these challenges through diplomatic engagement and cooperation.

Iraq has demonstrated a strong commitment to water diplomacy by officially joining the UN Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (UN Water Convention) in 2023. This move underscores Iraq's intent to improve water governance, advocate for equitable water-sharing arrangements, and foster greater cooperation with upstream neighbors like Türkiye and Iran. Additionally, Iraq has pursued negotiations and signed memoranda of understanding (MoUs) with Türkiye to enhance technical cooperation, joint research, and data sharing. These efforts reflect Iraq's proactive approach to securing its water rights and mitigating the impacts of upstream developments.

Climate Change and Water Scarcity

The region's vulnerability to climate change exacerbates the problem of water scarcity. Iraq is already one of the most water-scarce countries in the world, and climate change predictions indicate a decline in rainfall, higher temperatures, and more frequent droughts (UNDP, 2019). These changes reduce the amount of available water from the Tigris and Euphrates rivers and make it more difficult to maintain equitable water distribution among all stakeholders. Kurdistan Region of Iraq is particularly affected due to its mountainous terrain, which is more susceptible to changes in precipitation patterns.

Coordination and Institutional Capacity

Weakness in the enforcement of water-related laws and policies in Iraq can be attributed to several factors, including inadequate coordination between relevant ministries, insufficient institutional capacity, and a lack of specialized personnel needed to implement existing legislation. Additionally, fragmented governance structures, limited financial resources, and political instability further hinder effective enforcement. The absence of robust monitoring mechanisms and outdated infrastructure also contribute to challenges in ensuring compliance with water regulations. These factors collectively highlight the need for comprehensive reforms to strengthen enforcement and promote sustainable water management practices across the country.

Conflicting Water Use

Another issue is the conflicting use of water resources. Agriculture is a significant sector in Iraq, including in the KRI, and the over-extraction of water for irrigation purposes is a major contributor to the depletion of available water resources (Al-Qasim & Al-Khaddar, 2018). In addition to agricultural demands, urbanization and industrial growth in both Iraq and the KRI have led to an increasing need for water, putting further strain on already limited resources. This competition between various sectors has made it difficult to ensure sustainable water management practices.

Legal and Regulatory Challenges

The lack of a comprehensive and binding legal framework for transboundary water management in the region complicates cooperation. While Iraq, Türkiye, and Syria have engaged in several bilateral discussions and agreements on water-sharing, these have not resulted in a long-term solution. For instance, the 1987 agreement between Iraq and Türkiye on the Euphrates River was never fully implemented, and the cooperation between Syria and Iraq on the Tigris River has been sporadic (Al-Ansari et al., 2014). Furthermore, the KRI's semi-autonomous status has led to a fragmented approach to water management, with KRI sometimes pursuing its own water policies without fully aligning them with national efforts.

Economic Challenges

The water sector in Iraq faces several economic challenges. These challenges include:

1) Inadequate Investment in Water Infrastructure

Chronic under-investment in water infrastructure has characterized both Iraq and Kurdistan, especially in irrigation systems, wastewater treatment plants, and water distribution networks. Most of the existing systems face significant losses result from leakages and inefficiencies.

The Ministry of Water Resources is actively working to modernize water infrastructure through phased strategies that prioritize national needs and climate resilience. Initiatives include lining irrigation canals, upgrading pumping stations, and improving water-use efficiency to ensure sustainable operation. Maintenance and operational planning are conducted within available financial resources, aiming to optimize expenditure and maximize the benefits of investment budgets. Additionally, the Ministry is seeking to enhance partnerships with the private sector and international organizations to secure funding for strategic projects and develop long-term solutions for water security.

However, obtaining funding remains challenging due to conditions imposed by donor organizations, such as stringent reporting requirements, fund disbursement mechanisms, and oversight criteria that may not align with national institutional frameworks. Furthermore, the perception of Iraq as a wealthy oil-

producing country has limited its eligibility for funding earmarked for resource-scarce nations. This overlooks the financial pressures Iraq faces, including large expenditure commitments, fluctuating oil prices, and the need to finance infrastructure and structural reforms. Addressing these barriers requires a concerted effort to harmonize national policies with donor requirements and attract sustainable investments.

2) Neglect of Agriculture Water Efficiency

Agriculture uses more than 70% of Iraq's and Kurdistan's water supply, while the irrigation methods continue to be very inefficient. Extensive use of flood irrigation wastes enormous amounts of water (FAO,2019). On the other hand, economic policies have not provided sufficient incentives to adopt modern and efficient water technologies like drip or sprinkler irrigation. The FAO identified this as the key factor in improving the use of water; without any proper pricing mechanisms or fiscal incentives to enable farmers to apply such technologies the progress remains slow.

While progress has been slow, the Ministry of Water Resources is implementing measures to promote sustainable agricultural practices. These include encouraging the cultivation of less water-intensive crops and introducing pricing mechanisms and fiscal incentives to support the adoption of water-saving technologies. Such efforts aim to balance food security with the need for long-term water conservation and improved agricultural productivity. However, greater emphasis on integrating economic considerations into agricultural water management is essential to achieve meaningful progress

3) Unregulated Industrial Water Use

Most of the industrial sectors, especially the sectors for oil and energy production, consume enormous volumes of water in Iraq and Kurdistan. However, industrial consumption is rarely regulated, and little or no economic cost is ever attached to the volume of water consumed. As an example, the oil sector, which is the backbone of Iraq's economy, requires very large amounts of water in extracting and processing oil. In turn, however, there is no mechanism instituted for charging industries for the use of water which means industries lack fiscal motivation for installing water-saving technologies. Recycling of wastewater would reduce some of the water pressures, but there is very little economic investment in or incentives for industries to put in place recycling technologies. UNEP reports that the use of wastewater recycling in industrial processes could greatly reduce water demand; this has largely not happened due to a lack of economic incentives.

4) Weak Public Private Partnerships (PPPs)

Underutilization of PPPs in Water Management as most economic strategies still fail to consider the value of PPPs in developing water infrastructure. In most regions, governments cannot afford to finance every project on the water supply list; private sector involvement would fill the gap. However, ambiguous policies and weak regulatory frameworks on the ground discourage the private sector from participating in water management. Reports from the OECD spell out how PPPs can play a critical role in mobilizing the capital and expertise required for infrastructure development, but this has not yet reached its full potential in Iraq and the KRG. In addition, reports from the World Bank emphasized the weak investment frameworks as the investment climate is unattractive due to the political situation for Iraq and Kurdistan, which has raised barriers to foreign investment water projects. Uncertainty in the regulatory framework, political instability is too high for both international and local investors to participate in the development of water infrastructure. The ongoing update to Iraq's National Water and Land Resources Strategy aims to address

this gap by promoting stakeholder engagement, including the private sector. A clear framework with defined incentives, stable legal provisions, and innovative financing mechanisms will be essential to attracting investments and achieving sustainable development in the water sector.⁵) Failure to Integrate Climate Resilience into Economic Planning

It is quite evident that the increase in temperatures, decrease in rainfall quantities, and increased drought frequency have not been well integrated into the economic planning of water resource management. The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) reports minor attention is paid to the development of economic policies that consider the financial cost implications of climate change in the long term. For example, the investment in drought-resistant infrastructure, climate-resilient water management systems, and early warning are inadequate, making Iraq and Kurdistan even more vulnerable to further water crises. In addition, the lack of funding for climate adaptation, even though, the international donors and development organizations have budgeted for funds on climate adaptation projects, Iraq and the KRG have not properly harmonized their economic policies in a way that attracts and utilizes such funds to its fullest potential. The Green Climate Funds (GCF) offers the opportunity for financing climate adaptation; however, with the lack of clear-cut national policies prioritizing climate resilience, Iraq and Kurdistan have not been able to tap into such resources.

11.2 Coordination and Governance

Within the unified federal framework of Iraq, both the federal government and the Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG) play critical roles in managing shared water systems. To ensure effective and sustainable water governance, alignment between the federal government and the KRG in policies, strategies, and implementation processes is essential. Highlighted below are key areas of strength, opportunities for improvement, and ongoing efforts to enhance coordination between the federal government and the KRG.

Overall Alignment in Water Management Strategies

The National Water Strategy of Iraq (2015-2035) and the KRG's Water Strategy (2017) demonstrate significant alignment in their overarching goals. Both emphasize enhancing water-use efficiency, modernizing infrastructure, and addressing transboundary water management challenges with upstream countries such as Türkiye, Syria, and Iran. These strategies prioritize sustainable water use, advanced irrigation systems, and climate resilience. International organizations like the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the World Bank have acknowledged the efforts of both governments in advancing water governance and infrastructure development. Furthermore, there is consensus on promoting water conservation and raising public awareness about sustainable water practices.

Despite these shared objectives, formal coordination during the implementation phase remains limited, leading to uneven progress in infrastructure development, water conservation, and agricultural reforms. For instance, initiatives to modernize irrigation systems and adopt water-efficient agricultural practices lack coherence across the country. Additionally, while both entities recognize the importance of transboundary water cooperation, there is room for improvement in integrating the KRG into international water negotiations. Strengthening collaboration in this area is crucial to securing equitable water-sharing agreements and presenting a unified national stance.

Coherence in Agricultural Water Management

Both Iraq's Agriculture Strategy (2015-2025) and the KRG's water management policies align on improving agricultural water-use efficiency and adopting modern irrigation technologies. There is mutual agreement on reducing subsidies for water-intensive crops, which represents a step toward more sustainable

practices. However, the implementation of these policies faces challenges due to insufficient coordination and weak enforcement of economic incentives. Financial support for farmers to adopt water-saving techniques remains inadequate, hindering progress in achieving policy objectives. Addressing these gaps will require stronger collaboration and alignment between federal and regional authorities.

Infrastructure Investment and Funding Mechanisms

Both the federal government and the KRG acknowledge the urgent need for investments in water infrastructure, including irrigation systems, wastewater treatment plants, and distribution networks. Despite this recognition, funding allocation and project execution remain inconsistent due to limited access to national and international financing. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) has highlighted the absence of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) in the water sector and the lack of unified approaches to attract investments. Bridging these gaps will require stronger collaboration to create an enabling environment for investment and infrastructure development. Efforts to harmonize funding mechanisms and leverage international partnerships can significantly enhance progress in this area.

Environmental and Ecosystem Management

Both governments have emphasized the importance of environmental protection and ecosystem restoration, as outlined in the National Environmental Strategy (2013-2017) and UNESCO's Mesopotamian Marshland Conservation Strategy (2019). Climate change is recognized as a significant risk to water scarcity, necessitating the integration of climate resilience actions into long-term water management practices. While progress has been made, the implementation of environmental policies remains inconsistent, and joint conservation initiatives between the federal government and the KRG are limited. According to the UNDP (2020), climate adaptation strategies are not yet fully integrated into cohesive national frameworks, underscoring the need for enhanced cooperation in this area. Building on existing efforts, such as collaborative projects in the Mesopotamian Marshlands, can serve as a foundation for broader alignment.

Transboundary Water Management

Both the federal government of Iraq and the KRG emphasize the importance of transboundary water cooperation and securing equitable water-sharing agreements. Coordination between the two entities in transboundary water negotiations occurs through permanent joint committees established to address issues related to shared water resources with upstream countries, such as Türkiye and Iran. These committees include representatives from the KRG, who actively contribute to national negotiation teams and participate in all discussions concerning transboundary water management.

While the federal government leads negotiations with upstream countries, the KRG plays a significant role by contributing expertise and regional insights through its representation in joint committees and national delegations. This collaborative approach underscores the shared responsibility of both sides in managing Iraq's water resources. However, there remains room for improvement in formalizing communication mechanisms and ensuring a unified national stance on transboundary water issues. Strengthening this coordination will be vital to bolstering Iraq's negotiating power and achieving favorable outcomes in regional water diplomacy.

Economic Considerations and Funding Mechanisms

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2019) notes that both governments aim to shift subsidies toward more sustainable practices, such as water-efficient irrigation and crop diversification. However, the

World Bank (2020) highlights the absence of a unified economic framework between the federal government and the KRG. The lack of water pricing mechanisms and joint financial incentives undermines efforts to promote water efficiency. Additionally, the KRG often faces greater funding challenges compared to the federal government, leading to inconsistencies in water infrastructure development and policy implementation, particularly in rural areas of Kurdistan where access to national resources is limited.

To address these challenges, it is essential to develop a coordinated economic framework that aligns federal and regional policies. This includes introducing water pricing systems, phasing out subsidies for non-essential uses, and incentivizing water-efficient technologies in agriculture and industry. Targeted support for vulnerable communities can ensure equitable access to affordable water while fostering sustainable practices.

11.3 Opportunities

There are several opportunities that Iraq and the Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI) can leverage to improve transboundary water management, focusing on cooperation, legal frameworks, technological advancements, and international partnerships. These opportunities, if utilized effectively, could help address the challenges posed by water scarcity, political tensions, and climate change in the region.

Shared Strategic Goals for Water Management

Both Iraq's National Water Strategy and the Kurdistan Regional Government's (KRG) Water Strategy align on critical objectives for addressing water management challenges. These strategies prioritize enhancing water-use efficiency, modernizing irrigation systems, and addressing transboundary water issues with upstream countries, including Türkiye, Syria, and Iran. The emphasis on improving water efficiency reflects the growing recognition of water scarcity and the need for sustainable management practices (World Bank, 2020). Both governments focus on advancing modernized infrastructure, which includes upgrading aging irrigation systems and improving water distribution networks, which is crucial for supporting agricultural productivity and meeting urban water demands.

Further support for these initiatives comes from international organizations, such as the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the World Bank, which have been active in promoting water governance and financing infrastructure development (UNDP, 2020). The involvement of these organizations helps build technical and financial capacity, contributing to effective water management practices in Iraq and Kurdistan. Moreover, both governments are increasingly recognizing the importance of public awareness campaigns to promote sustainable water practices. Public education on the benefits of water conservation and the adoption of water-efficient agricultural techniques is essential to ensuring that water management strategies are supported at the grassroots level.

Agreement on Agricultural Water Efficiency

The promotion of agricultural water-use efficiency is a central theme in both Iraq and the KRG's strategies. As agriculture consumes a significant portion of available water resources, both governments are focused on reducing water wastage through the introduction of modern irrigation technologies, such as drip irrigation and sprinkler systems, which deliver water directly to crops and reduce evaporation losses (FAO, 2019). These technologies are critical for improving crop yields while minimizing water consumption, especially in regions facing water scarcity. Additionally, both Iraq and the KRG have agreed to reduce subsidies for water-intensive crops, such as rice and wheat, encouraging farmers to adopt less water-

demanding crops, contributing to a more sustainable agricultural system. The shift towards crop diversification is expected to make agriculture more resilient to climate impacts, especially in the face of recurring droughts and reduced water availability.

Recognition of the Need for Infrastructure Investment

Both the central government of Iraq and the KRG recognize the urgent need for substantial investments in water infrastructure. This includes modernizing water storage facilities, upgrading irrigation networks, and ensuring reliable water distribution to both urban and rural areas. However, financial constraints remain a significant challenge in both regions. The lack of sufficient funding and the absence of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) in the water sector (OECD, 2021) hamper the progress of infrastructure projects. Nonetheless, there is a clear opportunity to attract investment by developing coordinated plans and aligning goals between the federal government and the KRG, creating a unified strategy that would make Iraq and Kurdistan more appealing to potential investors. Effective use of international aid and technical support from organizations like the World Bank and the UNDP could also accelerate these necessary infrastructure improvements.

Commitment to Environmental and Climate Resilience

Both the National Environmental Strategy and Action Plan (2013-2017) and UNESCO's Mesopotamian Marshland Conservation Strategy (2019) underline the importance of environmental protection and climate resilience in managing water resources. The implementation of these strategies offers an opportunity for both governments to focus on ecosystem-based solutions that restore vital wetlands, improve groundwater recharge, and protect biodiversity, particularly in the Mesopotamian marshlands. Given the region's susceptibility to climate change, both the federal government and the KRG are increasingly aware of the need to incorporate climate resilience into their long-term water management strategies. Climate-resilient agricultural practices, such as drought-resistant crops, efficient irrigation systems, and the restoration of degraded ecosystems, are critical to ensuring the sustainability of water resources and enhancing food security (UNDP, 2020).

Focus on Transboundary Water Cooperation

A major opportunity lies in strengthening transboundary water cooperation between Iraq, the KRG, and neighboring countries. Both Iraq and the KRG have expressed a commitment to pursuing equitable water-sharing agreements with upstream countries, particularly with Türkiye, Syria, and Iran, which control the headwaters of the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers. However, there remains a lack of formal coordination between the federal government and the KRG in transboundary water negotiations, which limits Iraq's bargaining power in securing favorable agreements. A joint, coordinated approach between the federal government and the KRG could enhance Iraq's ability to negotiate with upstream countries, ensuring more equitable access to shared water resources. Establishing a unified national position on transboundary water issues is essential for Iraq's overall water security and for protecting the country's strategic water interests (SIWI, 2021).

Economic Shift Toward Sustainable Water Management

Both the Iraqi government and the KRG aim to shift subsidies away from water-intensive crops and toward sustainable agricultural practices, such as the promotion of water-efficient irrigation methods and crop diversification (FAO, 2019). This policy shift presents an opportunity to align economic incentives with sustainable water management objectives, reducing the financial burden on the water sector and

promoting long-term water conservation. Moreover, the introduction of water pricing mechanisms and financial incentives for farmers adopting sustainable practices could encourage the widespread use of water-efficient technologies. In addition, international financial institutions like the World Bank could play a role in supporting this shift through targeted funding programs that incentivize the adoption of more efficient water-use practices across Iraq and the KRG.

Additionally, the new MoU that has been signed between Iraq and Türkiye regarding joint water projects. This offers an opportunity for better negotiations between the two countries. Iraq joining the UN Convention: this step is very beneficial for Iraq and shows its commitment toward water diplomacy and cooperation. Iraq can benefit from the technical assistance and support to enhance its water diplomacy and negotiations capacity.

12 Areas for Improvement and Suggested Actions

12.1 Gaps

Water management in Iraq and Kurdistan lacks adequate economic and political considerations in several significant areas which create inefficiencies and reduce productivity while increasing vulnerability to the water crisis. Below are the main areas where political and economic considerations are missing or insufficient in water management. The integration and coherence of water management policies across Iraq and Kurdistan are crucial for addressing the overall growing water challenges. Areas of alignment exist; however, a variety of gaps in national and regional strategies limit the overall effectiveness of water management. These gaps are summarized as follows:

Enforcement and Implementation of Water Laws

Weak enforcement of water-related laws is one of the key challenges facing water resource management in Iraq. However, attributing this shortcoming solely to the factors mentioned in the paragraph—such as inadequate regulations on water extraction and waste processing—overlooks the deeper, systemic issues at play. In addition to these factors, the weakness in enforcement can be largely attributed to the lack of effective coordination among relevant ministries and the shortage of specialized personnel needed to implement existing legislation. This highlights that the challenges are not limited to institutional capacity constraints but extend to a complex set of structural factors, including fragmented governance, overlapping mandates, and insufficient technical expertise. Addressing these gaps requires comprehensive reforms to ensure the effective implementation of water laws and improve overall water governance. In this context, it is hoped that the upcoming update to Iraq's National Water and Land Resources Strategy will include a thorough evaluation of the legal and regulatory frameworks governing the water sector. Such an assessment would represent a significant step toward addressing current shortcomings and enhancing the efficiency of strategy implementation, ultimately contributing to more sustainable water management practices.

Absence of Binding Transboundary Water Agreements

Iraq does not have binding transboundary water-sharing agreements with its upstream neighbors, especially with Türkiye and Iran. Although the 1987 Protocol between Türkiye and Syria stipulates a minimum flow to Syria, such a legally binding agreement does not exist with Iraq. The same holds true for its numerous dam construction and river diversion projects, mainly concerning the Karkheh and Karun

rivers, by Iran, which have reduced the water flows to Iraq, despite the absence of formal agreements regulating these actions.

With no binding agreements yet, these have enabled upstream countries to persist in unilateral water policies that substantially reduce the water available to Iraq, creating shortages in agriculture and urban supply and causing environmental degradation. As an example, this includes the Mesopotamian Marshes. In the absence of a legal framework, Iraq has very narrow scope for recourse to insist on a fair share of the water.

Lack of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM)

Iraq and the KRG have not adopted a fully integrated approach to Integrated Water Resource Management, which is the whole concept of managing water resources holistically. While there is, within both governments, a water strategy aimed at developing infrastructure to raise efficiency, there is limited integration of environmental, social, and economic factors into decision-making processes. Poor practice of IWRM results in fragmentary water management; protection of the ecosystem, urban planning, and agricultural policies all are made in isolation from each other. This also affects areas like the Mesopotamian Marshes more than others, where the poor state of the environment is directly related to poor water management and cross-sectoral coordination.

Limited Data Sharing and Transparency

There is a severe lack of data sharing and transparency between Iraq, the KRG, and the upstream countries. The water monitoring systems of Iraq are also outdated, and there is very little sharing of important hydrological data, crucial for good management and negotiation in transboundary contexts. Neither Türkiye nor Iran has provided regular data regarding water flows, dam operations, or water quality. As a result, the absence of real-time data and lack of transparency detract from Iraq's capacity in the negotiation of equitable water-sharing agreements. Furthermore, Iraq is at a disadvantage in transboundary water negotiations because of the absence of accurate and timely data on water availability, flows, and usage.

This gap further denies effective planning and decision-making in domestic water management, particularly in regions such as the KRI, which are highly dependent on localized data to deal with these limited resources.

Insufficient investment in Water Infrastructure

Both Iraq and the KRG are underinvested in various water infrastructures, including irrigation systems, treatment plants for wastewater, and water distribution networks. Prolonged conflicts, political turmoil, and corruption have together conspired to make water infrastructure in Iraq woefully outdated, with significant volumes of water leaking away because of inefficiency. This impacts the economy negatively due to a lack of investment in modern infrastructure, which increases water scarcity through a reduction in efficiency in agricultural and urban water use. In the KRG, with an acute shortage of water, deficient infrastructure has meant a greater reliance on overextraction from rivers and aquifers, further depleting this already scarce resource of water, and undermining any notion of its sustainable management.

Stakeholder Participation Formalization

The limited involvement of local communities, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and other stakeholders in water management decisions remains a significant gap, reducing societal support for sustainable practices and leading to policies that often overlook the needs of those most affected. While

the Ministry of Water Resources (MoWR) has made efforts to enhance participation—such as awareness campaigns, integrating farmers into irrigation planning through Water Users' Associations (WUAs), and hosting educational seminars on water crises and climate change impacts—these measures have not yet fully addressed the lack of formalized mechanisms for stakeholder engagement.

The absence of formal channels for regular consultation with stakeholders undermines the consistency, transparency, and inclusivity of water management decision-making processes. Without structured systems in place, the voices of local communities, NGOs, and other key actors are often marginalized or excluded altogether. To address this gap, it is critical to establish formalized mechanisms that ensure meaningful and sustained stakeholder participation Climate Change Adaptation Gaps

Iraq has yet to fully integrate climate change adaptation into its water management policies, but significant efforts are being made by the Ministry of Water Resources to address this critical issue. While national strategies acknowledge the impacts of climate change, such as rising temperatures, reduced rainfall, and increased drought, more work is needed to establish a robust framework for mitigating these long-term effects on water availability. The Ministry of Water Resources has been actively working to enhance adaptive capacity through comprehensive water resource management policies and the implementation of projects aimed at improving water use efficiency and reducing the negative impacts of climate change. These efforts include promoting sustainable irrigation practices, investing in climate-resilient infrastructure, and developing early warning systems to address water scarcity challenges.

However, without sustained and substantial investments in advanced technologies, such as improved water storage systems, and innovative water conservation measures, Iraq remains vulnerable to the prolonged consequences of climate change. Continued progress in these areas is essential to mitigate increasing water scarcity and prevent declines in agricultural productivity. Highlighting these ongoing national efforts provides a more balanced and accurate representation of Iraq's response to climate change challenges, showcasing the country's commitment to adapting and building resilience in the face of evolving environmental pressures.

Table 1: Evaluation Criteria for power and interest of stakeholders presents a detailed analysis of incomplete or missing legal and institutional frameworks.

Table 11: Legal and Institutional Gaps

Gap	Description	Impact
Absence of Comprehensive Transboundary Guidelines	The Iraqi and KRG legislations do not precisely address how transboundary waters should be managed. Iraq is indeed a party in the process of transboundary water negotiations with upstream countries like Türkiye and Iran, but no legally binding agreements regulate the use of international rivers such as the Tigris and Euphrates.	The absence of legally binding agreements, whereby upstream countries may adopt and utilize a unilateral approach to water management through the construction of dams, despite the influence on Iraq downstream. The ultimate result is a decline in flow, therefore worsening scarcity in agriculture, urban uses, and natural environmental ecosystems, such as the Mesopotamian Marshes.
Inadequate Water Pricing	There is a lack of holistic legislation concerning water pricing and economic incentive application in Iraq and the KRG.	The absence of clear legal frameworks usually leads to overconsumption and general inefficiency in its use,

and Economic Incentives	No unified laws and regulations appear to exist which may increase the valuation of the water resource.	particularly in agriculture. Lacking economic motives, no reasonable adaptation of water-saving technologies, such as irrigation systems, has been widely seen. This led to water resources, putting more pressure on the supply/demand balance (FAO, 2019).
Weak Institutional Capacity (UNDP, 2020)	Institutional capacity remains weak for water resources management across both Iraq and the KRG. Poor coordination due to the fragmentation of roles and responsibilities within the ministries and agencies, such as the Ministry of Water Resources, Ministry of Agriculture, and the Ministry of Environment, results in ineffective governance.	No coordination among the agencies negatively impacts holistic water management strategies. For example, water conservation in agriculture entity not properly linked with nationwide water strategies; hence, efficiencies in both water use and policy enforcement are not realized.
Absence of Unified Legal Framework for Groundwater Management	In Iraq, including the KRG, there is a lack of an integrated legal framework for the management and allocation of groundwater. While there exist certain surface water laws and policies, there has not been regulation with respect to the extraction, monitoring, or sustainable use of this source.	over-extraction and decline in groundwater are increasing, especially within the KRG areas where agriculture and domestic uses increasingly rely on the resource. Lack of regulation could lead to long-term gross water scarcity with the threat of undermining sustainability (World Bank, 2020).
Absence of Binding Enforcement Mechanism for Water Use and Pollution control (MOWR, 2019)	Due to the weak legal framework and lack of institutional capacity, most existing laws related to water use and pollution control are weak. Although the newly presented Water Resources Law in Iraq in 2019 called for provisions to regulate the use of water and fines against illegal activities, it is still weak in its implementation across the country.	The lack of enforcement mechanisms for illegal water usage and pollution, especially coming from industrial and agricultural sources, has become threatening. This has contributed to declining water quality and added to challenges associated with water management, especially in regions where clean water is already scarce, such as southern Iraq and the KRG.

Among the major legal and institutional gaps in the management of water in Iraq and the Kurdistan Region mentioned above, undermine their capacity to address effectively water shortage, In addition, the limited institutional frameworks for climate change adaptation and legal protection of the ecosystem and the environment, as well as the lack of IWRM legal framework, in addition to limited Public-Private partnership opportunities are hindering effective water management and transboundary agreements within Iraq and Kurdistan.

12.2 Actions

Considering the gaps mentioned above, there are actions/ measures that need to be taken to improve transboundary water management. These actions are listed in **Table 12**.

Table 12: Areas for Improvements, Actions for Improvement, and Recommendations

Area for Improvement	Action	Recommendation
Comprehensive National Water Policy Framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Develop a unified national water strategy for Iraq and KRG. ▪ Establish a formal collaboration mechanism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coordinate regional and federal efforts to align priorities. ▪ Create a joint water governance committee to ensure coherence and proper allocation.
Strengthen legal transboundary water management frameworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Engage in multilateral negotiations. ▪ Establish Data Sharing and monitoring mechanisms with upstream countries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Secure binding water-sharing agreements using the available international laws like UN Convention. ▪ Enhance transparency in water management by joint hydrological data collection and sharing.
Water Pricing and Economic Incentives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enforce water pricing system for agriculture and industrial sectors. ▪ Provide subsidies for water-efficient irrigation technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create economic incentives for efficient water use, ▪ Encourage farmers to use modern irrigation systems by offering financial support.
Groundwater Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improve monitoring systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use technologies to track groundwater levels.
Institutional capacity and PPPs approaches.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide training on new technologies, governance, collaboration, and transboundary water management. ▪ Establish a legal framework for PPPs in water management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strengthen the capacity of stakeholders responsible for water management and clarify roles and responsibilities to avoid duplication of efforts and strategies. ▪ Attract private sector investments by introducing legal frameworks and providing a competitive environment.

12.2.1 Integrating Economic Considerations in Water Management in Iraq and Kurdistan

Iraq and Kurdistan must reform the structure of water tariffs so the use of available water resources would be sustained and achieve better service delivery. The main points to consider in any reform:

- **Introduce a usage-based tariff:** This refers to charging the consumers according to their actual water use which would raise the financial incentives to conserve water. In addition, it would add further value to pricing across service provision costs for most users by increasing the reward for water economizing, and for investment in water-saving technologies, especially in agriculture.
- **Gradual Elimination of Subsidies:** While an abrupt elimination would provoke political and social resistance to the reforms, their gradual reduction for non-essential water use would contribute to fiscal adjustment and create incentives to serve water use efficiency.
- **Improvement of Metering and Monitoring:** Increased installation of water meters and monitoring of water consumption will enable proper billing and the application of a tiered pricing structure where higher consumption is charged at progressively higher rates.
- **Targeting Subsidies on Vulnerable Groups:** Instead of across-the-board subsidies, targeted support for poor households and rural communities should ensure that the most vulnerable groups continue to access a sufficient volume of low-priced water while avoiding unnecessary subsidies for wealthy consumers.
- **Subsidize Water-Efficient Agriculture:** Prices on agricultural water need to be set consistent with the full cost of providing the water service while incentivizing farmers to adopt efficient irrigation practices that can help reduce over-extraction and excessive use of water.

12.2.2 Approaches Toward Economic Sustainability and Efficiency

The economic aspect of water management practices should be considered to better manage the water resources in Iraq and the Kurdistan Region. This includes water pricing mechanisms, promoting water-efficient agricultural and industrial practices, modernization of water infrastructure, alignment of water policy with climate resilience goals, international cooperation, and leveraging various financing opportunities towards the sustainability and economic viability of the water management system. Addressing these gaps would not only help in soothing the present crisis for water but would also highly contribute towards economic stability and growth in the long run.

- **Invest in Modernization of Water Infrastructure:** Iraq and KRG suffer from aging and inefficient water infrastructure, leading to significant water losses. This would include irrigation systems, water treatment plants and distribution systems, and wastewater treatment plants. This would reduce leakages and improve the overall supply reliability. The OECD (2021) underscores the importance of PPPs in funding water infrastructure, particularly in developing economies.
- **Implement industrial Water Pricing and Recycling Initiatives:** the industrial sector currently lacks economic incentives to conserve water. Introducing a price-incentive system and recycling initiatives would encourage more sustainable practices. According to the UNEP (2020) implementing water recycling and incentive systems in the industrial sector could reduce freshwater use by up to 30%.
- **Incentives Climate Resilience in Water Management:** climate change's impact on water scarcity in Iraq and KRG is exacerbating. Aligning water management strategies with climate adaptation plans will enable the region to better mitigate the economic impact of climate variability. UNDP (2020) emphasizes the need for proactive climate resilience policies in water management.

- **Strengthen Economic Integration in Transboundary Water Agreements:** Iraq is highly dependent on upstream water flows. Long-term water scarcity needs agreements that ensure equitable and sustainable water-sharing agreements. SIWI (2021) stated that transboundary cooperation that includes economic incentives for all parties is key to reducing conflict and improving regional water management.
- **Promote the Economic Value of Ecosystem and Eco-Tourism:** The degradation of the ecosystem has significant economic costs, particularly for communities that rely on the marshlands for their livelihoods. Iraq and KRG should invest more in this aspect by valuing the ecosystem as economic assets. The UNESCO (2019) report on Iraq’s marshlands suggests that restoring these ecosystems can create economic opportunities and improve water management.

12.2.3 Technical solutions and Actions

Water Management and Economic Improvements

- **Smart Agriculture:** Advanced irrigation technologies applied together with water pricing will reduce water waste and enhance agricultural productivity. The adoption of crops that require less water will make farming resistant to drought and water shortage; hence, the agricultural sector will be contributing to economic growth in a sustainable manner. This potentially enables Iraq to contribute to long-run food security and economic stability by investing in more efficient practices.
- **Improved Industrial Water Use:** Water recycling in industries like oil extraction and refining could lower operating costs and demands on freshwater. More effective water management would ensure sustainable industrial development for Iraq's economic reliance on its oil sector. Recycling and efficient water use can enhance productivity within various industries and help contribute toward the sustainability, thus helping to ensure improved economic performance for Iraq.
- **Better Water Infrastructure and Employment:** Public-private partnerships in water infrastructure can, in turn, improve the delivery and efficiency of water services while providing jobs both in the construction as well as operation and maintenance of such water systems. Modernization of water infrastructure allows Iraq and the KRG to capture employment opportunities along with co-benefits like reduced water losses, increased access to water, and greater economic resilience.
- **Climate Resilience and Adaptation:** Climate change adaptation-inclusive investment in climate-resilient water infrastructure and drought-resistant crops will protect Iraq's agriculture and industry from future climate-related risks. Through adoption of the climate resiliency, Iraq will be able to adapt to increased water shortages that in turn will translate into economic stability, especially for vulnerable sectors such as agriculture.
- **Enhanced Transboundary Water Diplomacy:** Intensification of diplomatic efforts to ensure that binding transboundary agreements on the sharing of water resources with upstream countries are concluded to secure more reliable water supplies feeding Iraq's agriculture and industries. Stable water agreements will provide Iraq with the water security to underpin its economy and prevent costly disruptions to key industries.

Technical Actions

Table 13 provides a list of actions to be implemented to cover different technical aspects regarding water management.

Table 13: Actions and Research for Technical Aspects

Topic	Gap	Future Opportunities
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<p>Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of comprehensive studies of IWRM in Iraq and KRG. Insufficient data on the interaction of agriculture, industry, and domestic water uses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Develop integrated approaches involving environmental, economic, and social parameters. Interdisciplinary research to balance water use in different sectors. (World Bank, 2020, FAO, 2019)
<p>Groundwater Management</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inadequate information on availability, abstraction rates, and replenishment potential. Limited research on the impacts of over-extraction and aquifer depletion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Groundwater assessments and forecasting of sustainable extraction rates. Develop MAR systems to artificially supplement groundwater supplies. (World Bank, 2020)
<p>Climate Change Impact on Water Resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Poorly modeled long-run impacts of climate change on water availability. Inadequate research on climate-resilient infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Climate modeling of temperature and precipitation impacts. Develop drought-resistant irrigation and improve water storage. (UNDP, 2020)
<p>Water-Energy-Food Nexus</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of understanding of interconnections among water, energy, and food sectors. Lack of research on the impact of water scarcity on agriculture and food security. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research on water, energy, and food resource use efficiency. Develop crops requiring minimal water. (SIWI, 2021)
<p>Transboundary Water Cooperation and Diplomacy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of review on diplomatic strategies to secure binding agreements for sharing water. Lack of research on the effects of dam projects in upstream states. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research on strategies for cooperation. ▪ Research on effects of upstream dams on rivers flow in upstream states.
<p>Water Quality and Pollution Control</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limited studies on industrial and agricultural pollution affecting water quality. Insufficient data on wastewater treatment plant efficiency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Study water pollution and ways to prevent or attenuate it. Explore new perspectives for water recycling and reutilization. (UNESCO, 2019)
<p>Water Use Efficiency in Agriculture</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of cost-benefit analysis of modern irrigation for small-scale farmers. Limited studies on crop selection during water scarcity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Study cost-effectiveness of drip and sprinkler irrigation. Promote crop diversification and drought-resistant crops. (FAO, 2019)

Public Participation and Community Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limited research on community-based traditional water use practices. Limited study on the effectiveness of water-saving awareness programs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Study optimal community involvement mechanisms in water governance. Design and assess education courses targeting sustainable water use. (World Bank, 2020)
Economic Consequences of Water Scarcity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limited research on the economic consequences of water scarcity at various levels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research the economic impacts of water scarcity and formulate policies for sustainable growth. (World Bank, 2020)
Technological Innovation in Water Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of research on remote sensing, AI, and data analytics for water resource monitoring. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exploit new water monitoring and management technologies. (OECD, 2021)
Rain Water Harvesting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of awareness, inadequate infrastructure, and limited government incentives. Pilot projects and community-based initiatives have shown promise, but widespread adoption requires policy support and investment in storage systems (Al-Madhhachi et al., 2022). ▪ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rainwater harvesting is an underutilized strategy in Iraq despite its potential to alleviate water shortages. The country's arid and semi-arid climate limits rainfall, but capturing rainwater during the wet season could support agriculture, domestic use, and groundwater replenishment (Al-Ameri, 2020).

13 Conclusions and Recommendations

13.1 Conclusions

Water resource management in Iraq and the Kurdistan Region represents one of the most critical challenges facing the nation today. The interplay of water scarcity, aging infrastructure, weak transboundary agreements, and the growing impacts of climate change underscores the urgent need for coordinated action at both national and regional levels. Despite these challenges, Iraq has demonstrated remarkable resilience and commitment to addressing water management issues through diplomacy, policy reforms, and strategic investments. These efforts reflect Iraq's dedication to ensuring sustainable water security, fostering regional stability, and protecting the vital interests of its people.

Iraq's accession to the UN Water Convention in 2023 marks a significant milestone in its commitment to strengthening transboundary water cooperation. This landmark decision highlights Iraq's proactive approach to engaging with upstream countries such as Türkiye and Iran, with the aim of securing equitable water-sharing agreements and promoting sustainable development. Diplomatic efforts have been further reinforced through the signing of framework agreements and memoranda of understanding (MoUs), which emphasize joint technical collaboration, data sharing, and capacity building. These initiatives underscore Iraq's readiness to build bridges of cooperation and address shared water challenges in a spirit of mutual benefit.

At the national level, Iraq has made commendable progress in modernizing its water governance frameworks and enhancing institutional capacity. Initiatives such as the National Water Strategy (2015-2035), rehabilitation of irrigation systems, and promotion of water-efficient agricultural practices demonstrate Iraq's commitment to improving water-use efficiency and reducing wastage. The Ministry of Water Resources has played a pivotal role in spearheading these efforts, working closely with international organizations and stakeholders to align national priorities with global best practices. Furthermore, efforts to strengthen coordination between the federal government and the Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG) reflect a shared vision for unified water governance and equitable resource allocation.

Despite these achievements, significant challenges remain. Structural inefficiencies, insufficient investment in water infrastructure, and the absence of legally binding transboundary agreements continue to hinder progress. Addressing these gaps requires sustained collaboration, innovative solutions, and a unified national strategy that brings together all stakeholders—federal and regional governments, civil society, the private sector, and international partners. Strengthening public-private partnerships (PPPs), leveraging international funding mechanisms, and fostering community engagement will be essential to accelerating infrastructure development and promoting sustainable water use practices.

Climate change poses an additional layer of complexity, with rising temperatures, reduced rainfall, and increased drought frequency exacerbating water scarcity challenges. Iraq's commitment to integrating climate adaptation strategies into national policies—such as investments in drought-resistant crops and resilient water infrastructure—demonstrates its forward-thinking approach to mitigating these risks. By prioritizing climate resilience, Iraq can safeguard its agricultural and industrial sectors, ensuring long-term economic stability and social well-being.

Looking ahead, Iraq's continued leadership in regional water diplomacy will be crucial to achieving equitable and sustainable water-sharing arrangements. Establishing a unified national position on

transboundary water issues, supported by transparent data-sharing mechanisms and strengthened institutional frameworks, will enhance Iraq's bargaining power and foster trust among regional stakeholders. At the same time, ongoing efforts to modernize water infrastructure, improve governance, and promote public awareness campaigns will lay the foundation for a more resilient and prosperous future.

In conclusion, Iraq's journey toward sustainable water security is marked by both challenges and opportunities. Through its unwavering commitment to diplomacy, innovation, and collaboration, Iraq has taken meaningful steps to address its water management challenges and protect its vital resources. By continuing to build on these efforts and fostering partnerships at all levels, Iraq can overcome its water-related challenges and secure a sustainable path forward for generations to come. This collective endeavor reflects Iraq's vision of a future where water serves as a cornerstone of stability, prosperity, and peace.

13.2 Recommendations

13.2.1 Short-Term Recommendations

The short-term actions outlined below are considered in the strategic plans and programs being implemented by the Ministry of Water Resources. These initiatives reflect a clear vision that takes into account national needs, regional challenges, and international dynamics. The Ministry takes significant efforts in developing and executing practical and sustainable solutions to ensure sound water management and enhance regional cooperation. Below are the key recommendations and their alignment with ongoing efforts:

Strengthen Diplomatic Engagement

Iraq has consistently demonstrated its commitment to enhancing water diplomacy through continuous engagement in direct and ongoing negotiations with neighboring riparian countries in the Tigris and Euphrates basins. As a partner in the Blue Peace Initiative in the Middle East, the Center for Water Diplomacy highlights Iraq's openness and readiness to build bridges of cooperation with these nations. These efforts aim to serve mutual interests and ensure fair and equitable water distribution in the two river basins. While significant progress has been made, such as the recent memorandum of understanding between Iraq and Türkiye for joint water projects, more efforts shall be devoted to help securing legally binding agreements and negotiating improved water apportionment deals. This will help mitigate geopolitical tensions and promote sustainable transboundary water management.

Improved Water Use Efficiency in Agriculture

Recognizing the critical importance of modernizing irrigation systems, the Ministry has adopted and implemented comprehensive projects to promote advanced irrigation technologies, such as drip irrigation and sprinkler systems, across various regions of Iraq. These initiatives aim to reduce water losses, enhance agricultural productivity, and transition toward less water-intensive crop varieties. By addressing inefficiencies in traditional flood irrigation methods, these projects contribute to more sustainable agricultural practices while ensuring long-term water security.

Improve Water Infrastructure

The Ministry is actively working to upgrade and rehabilitate water infrastructure, including dams, water distribution networks, and wastewater treatment facilities. Ongoing projects focus on reducing water losses, improving supply reliability, and ensuring equitable access to water resources. Despite financial and technical challenges, the Ministry continues to execute vital projects to modernize aging infrastructure and

enhance the sustainability of water resources. Efforts include rehabilitating dams, repairing leakages in distribution systems, and implementing measures to minimize wastage.

Improve Data Sharing and Transparency

Accurate and updated data are essential for effective water resource management. To this end, the Ministry has developed plans to enhance water monitoring systems and improve data collection mechanisms in coordination with relevant stakeholders. However, the lack of transparency from upstream countries in sharing hydrological data remains a significant obstacle. The Ministry is actively addressing this challenge through diplomatic channels, advocating for greater transparency and trust-building in transboundary water negotiations. Establishing real-time joint monitoring systems and fostering collaborative data-sharing frameworks with upstream nations will be critical to achieving sustainable outcomes.

Public Awareness Campaigns

The Ministry has launched numerous awareness campaigns targeting communities and stakeholders to emphasize the importance of water conservation and efficient water use practices. These initiatives include educational programs, media campaigns, and community outreach activities designed to engage diverse societal groups. By promoting behavioral change and encouraging participation in water-saving efforts, the Ministry aims to foster a culture of sustainability and shared responsibility for achieving water security. These efforts are ongoing and will continue to expand to ensure broader societal involvement in addressing Iraq's water challenges.

13.2.2 Long-Term recommendations

- **Pursue Legally Binding Transboundary Agreements:** Iraq fully recognizes the importance of securing comprehensive and legally binding agreements with neighboring riparian countries, particularly Türkiye and Iran, regarding the equitable sharing of water resources in the Tigris and Euphrates basins. However, achieving such agreements requires mutual commitment from all parties, not solely Iraq's efforts. While Türkiye and Iran are not parties to the 1997 UN Watercourses Convention, Iraq continues to employ diplomatic and legal tools to enhance transboundary water cooperation. This was exemplified by the recent framework agreement with Türkiye and ongoing negotiations with Iran to reach similar understandings. Despite upstream development projects posing significant challenges, Iraq relies on direct negotiation, regional dialogue, and collaboration with international organizations to ensure fair and equitable distribution of shared water resources. Future efforts should focus on securing bilateral or multilateral agreements that guarantee predictable water flows and reduce unilateral actions by upstream countries.
- **Adoption of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) Principles:** The Ministry of Water Resources has already adopted the concept of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) as a core approach within its national policies. Through coordinated efforts across sectors—such as agriculture, industry, municipal water supply, and the environment—the ministry seeks to achieve optimal and sustainable use of water resources. Policies have been introduced to rationalize water consumption, particularly in agriculture, through the adoption of modern technologies that reduce water losses and promote efficient use. Public awareness campaigns have also been launched to encourage sustainable water practices. However, the successful implementation of IWRM requires collective commitment from all sectors. The ministry is actively

working to strengthen intersectoral collaboration to ensure that water management aligns with national priorities and sustainability goals.

- Investment in Climate-Resilient Infrastructure: Iraq faces significant challenges due to the impacts of climate change, including increased drought frequency and altered flow patterns in the Tigris and Euphrates rivers. To address these issues, the Ministry of Water Resources has adopted policies to enhance resilience, such as developing water-harvesting dams, improving irrigation techniques, and optimizing the use of available resources. These initiatives aim to mitigate the adverse effects of climate-induced water scarcity. However, such projects require substantial funding, necessitating the mobilization of local and international investments. To this end, the ministry is actively engaging with international institutions to secure financial support for climate-resilient infrastructure projects, ensuring long-term water security and sustainability.
- Enhancing Coordination: Efforts are underway to strengthen joint governance mechanisms to ensure unified policies and strategies for water management. By fostering collaboration and aligning regional and federal objectives, Iraq aims to achieve more effective and equitable management of its water resources. This coordination is essential for addressing shared challenges and ensuring that water policies reflect a cohesive national vision.
- Development of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): Recognizing the need for substantial investment in large-scale water infrastructure projects, such as desalination plants and wastewater treatment facilities, the Ministry of Water Resources is exploring alternative financing mechanisms. Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) are being considered as a viable solution to bridge the funding gap. As part of the ongoing update to Iraq's National Water and Land Resources Strategy, the ministry is reviewing the legislative and regulatory frameworks governing the water sector to create an enabling environment for private sector participation. By attracting domestic and international investments, PPPs will play a critical role in accelerating the development of water infrastructure and improving service delivery across the country.

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